

Review

Organic and perovskite solar cells based on scalable slot-die coating technique: Progress and challenges

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ABSTRACT

In recent times, organic and perovskite solar cells (OSCs and PSCs) has garnered considerable attention due to the rapid advancement of their impressive photovoltaic performance, achieving power conversion efficiencies exceeding 19% and 26%, respectively. Various industrially scalable methods such as blade coating, spray coating, and slot-die coating have been employed to manufacture these promising solar cells, yet the efficiency of devices produced by these methods tends to be lower than those prepared in laboratory scales. To create pinhole-free and high-quality active layer in scalable devices, controlling the crystallization process is required. Therefore, the quality of the active layers plays a pivotal role in constructing efficient and stable solar cells. Among the scalable methods, the slot-die coating method is emerged as particularly attractive for large-scale and cost-effective production of both OSCs and PSCs. Thus, in the current work, we present the strategies to control the morphology of organic and perovskite films prepared by slot-die coating method, such as drying conditions, precursor engineering, solvent engineering, surface modification, and additive engineering, temperature controlling, sequential processing, and ternary blends. Also, the effect of slot-die-coated charge transport layers on the OSC and PSC efficiencies and stabilities has been investigated. Finally, the challenges and potential of commercialization of these promising solar cells, improving their efficiency, quality, and sustainability in the future, are discussed.

Introduction

Global warming caused by the ever-increasing energy consumption, which is mainly supplied by non-renewable fossil fuels, has more than ever made the need to accelerate the global installation of PV modules and reduce its costs tangible. Currently, solar cells based on crystalline silicon have taken over the photovoltaic market thanks to their well-established technology, long-term stability (over 25 years), and high efficiency (up to 26.7%) [1]. However, the silicon solar cell is still expensive because most of the cost goes into the thick silicon wafer. Therefore, during the last decades, many studies have been conducted to achieve a more cost-effective technology based on thin film solar cells. Humans have produced 1.5×10^{12} tons of CO₂ since the steam engine sparked the industrial revolution. As a result of population growth and

industrialization, 36×10^9 tons of CO₂ are produced each year. Solar cells are an effective method for reducing global CO₂ emissions. Extensive research has focused on perovskite (PVSk) photovoltaics because of their distinct characteristics, including affordable material costs, compatibility with solution processing, appealing device physics, and high efficiency. These attributes, when coupled with advanced production techniques, have the potential to reduce manufacturing costs compared to alternative printed, coated photovoltaics, and traditional photovoltaic technologies [2,3].

Recent advances in perovskite and organic solar cells (schematics of the solar cells have been depicted in Fig. 1-a) offer unique properties and promise the emergence of next-generation photovoltaic technologies. Metal halide perovskites with the general formula of ABX₃, where A is a monovalent cation (e.g., MA⁺, FA⁺, Cs⁺), site B is a divalent cation (e.g.,

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Pb^{2+} , Sn^{2+}), and X is a halide (e.g., I⁻, Br⁻, Cl⁻) [4], as promising materials with a high absorption coefficient [5], tunable band gap [6], the low exciton binding energy [7], and high diffusion length [8] have emerged for solar cell application just above a decade ago. Its efficiency in 2009, which was first used as a light sensitizer with the MAPbBr₃ structure in dye-sensitized solar cells, was about 3.8%, while it showed poor stability under light irradiation due to dissolving in used liquid electrolytes [9]. Following this, the perovskite solar cells (PSCs) experienced a very rapid improvement that brought these devices as a new category of emerging photovoltaic technology to compete in efficiency with silicon-based solar cells in the chart of Best Solar Cells Efficiency (presented by the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL)) [10,11]. The high efficiency (up to 25.5%), along with relatively low-priced and low-temperature fabrication, processes attracted the interest of many research groups across the globe.

On the other hand, the first organic solar cells (OSCs) were invented in 1959, when a single layer of anthracene was used as the photoactive layer [12]. The low dielectric constant of anthracene, which does not allow the generated excitons to separate into free electron-holes, resulted in very low efficiency. In 1986, inventing of the concept of bilayer organic solar cells by Tang and the introduction of the donor and acceptor into the photoactive layer provided the conditions for the separation of excitons [13]. Subsequently, the bulk heterojunction (BHJ) structure was developed in the 1990s, where the donor polymer and fullerene derivative were physically combined to form a sufficient donor/acceptor interface to separate excitons [14,15]. Nowadays, this

structure remains one of the most effective configurations in organic solar cells. Recent advancements in donor and acceptor materials [16, 17] have led to achieving high efficiencies of up to 19% in organic solar cells [18]. This notable efficiency, coupled with additional benefits such as lightweight construction, mechanical flexibility, cost-effectiveness, and rapid energy payback, positions organic solar cells as a compelling alternative to traditional silicon-based solar cells [19–24].

Emerging thin film photovoltaic systems based on perovskite and organic solar cells face a severe challenge, the transition from laboratory scale to industrial scale [25,26]. The technologies applied to these systems are mainly based on solution-processed methods [27], which interestingly enable compatibility with flexible substrates and roll-to-roll (R2R) manufacturing. High-speed fabrication and high pattern accuracy delivery can be counted among the advantages of the R2R continuous process [28]. R2R manufacturing technologies include gravure printing, flexographic printing, knife-over-edge coating, and slot-die coating [29]. Among them, meeting the need for a high degree of patternability in large-area fabrication and efficient use of materials makes slot-die coating unique. In addition, this method is well applicable for coating not only organic and perovskite inks, but also other device layers such as charge transport layers and contacts.

The slot-die coating method for fabricating solar cells offers several environmental benefits compared to other methods. Slot-die coating is highly efficient in material usage, reducing waste significantly compared to techniques like spin coating, which often involves excess solvent and material loss. The method's precision in material deposition

Fig. 1. a) Schematic of perovskite and organic solar cells. b) Scheme of a slot-die coater illustrating an ink transfer to the coating head from a syringe pump system and deposition of a wet layer on the surface of the substrate. c) The flow of solution in both the upstream and downstream directions is governed by the interplay between the pressure gradient and the shear force at the interface between the substrate and the liquid. d) A stable coating window in slot-die coating ensures the production of films without any defects [33]. (c-d) Printed with permission from Ref [33].

also minimizes the need for toxic solvents and allows for cleaner production processes [30]. In contrast, other methods like spray coating and inkjet printing can result in higher material waste and solvent usage. Overall, slot-die coating's compatibility with roll-to-roll production and its efficient material use make it a more environmentally friendly option for large-scale solar cell manufacturing compared to other deposition methods.

Moreover, the slot-die coating method for solar cells presents significant economic advantages in terms of manufacturing costs and scalability. This technique is particularly efficient for large-scale production, as it integrates well with roll-to-roll manufacturing processes [31]. This adaptability is crucial for producing solar cells on a commercial scale, where continuous processing is needed to maintain cost efficiency and high throughput [32]. One of the key economic benefits of slot-die coating is its material efficiency. Unlike spin coating, which wastes a significant amount of material, slot-die coating precisely deposits the necessary amount of material, reducing waste and lowering overall material costs. This precision also contributes to the reproducibility and consistency of the manufactured solar cells, further enhancing their commercial viability. Additionally, slot-die coating is more scalable compared to other methods such as inkjet printing or vacuum deposition. While inkjet printing offers fine control over small-scale production, it faces challenges in scaling up to larger areas required for commercial applications. Vacuum-based processes, although avoiding the use of toxic solvents, are typically more complex and costly to implement on a large scale [32].

Slot-die coating is a one-dimensional coating technique in which ink

is transported to a steel coating head via a pump system (as depicted in Fig. 1-b). The ink is expelled through a narrow slot along the length of the coating head, positioned in close proximity to a substrate. Movement of either the substrate or the coating head leads to the deposition of a wet film. To regulate the striped pattern and the quality of the layer edges, the coating head is outfitted with a meniscus guide (a well-designed mask, i.e. the shim), which is a critical component of the apparatus for achieving an evenly distributed film [33]. The thickness of the applied film can be finely tuned with a precision of just a few nanometers by modulating both the movement speed of the substrate and the ink flow rate from the coating head. This capability of slot-die coating enables the deposition of extremely thin films, ranging from tens of nanometers, to considerably thicker films measuring tens of microns.

In this review, the recent progress in strategies for adjusting ink rheological properties and optimizing the morphology of slot-die coated perovskite and organic active layers and interfacial layers will be presented. Since the slot-die coating technique has great potential to commercialize organic and perovskite solar cells, summarizing the critical achievements in slot-die-coated organic and perovskite solar cells by distinguishing the key aspects of blend morphology control and trying to pave ways to achieve high-quality active layers is necessary. Moreover, it is a timely review of the latest progress in these emerging photovoltaic technologies. To begin with, the effects of various approaches such as solvent engineering, drying conditions, sequential processing on morphology forming and crystallization of the films deposited by slot-die technique will be discussed, as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. The contents presented in the review.

Subsequently, the performance development of slot-die-coated organic and perovskite solar cells will be thoroughly reviewed. Finally, to improve their performance, the crucial hurdles needing to be overcome will be addressed.

A deep understanding of slot-die theory is essential for comprehending the interplay between the operating parameters of a slot-die system, which influences the creation of a stable coating. In slot die coating processes, a significant consideration is determining the operating limits in order to establish the suitable range for various operating parameters such as coating speed, flow rate, vacuum pressure, liquid viscosity, coating gap, and surface tension. Optimal coatings of high quality can only be attained within a specific coating window, where exiting this window can cause the formation of defects. As the slot thickness to length ratio is typically small, the flow of the solution can be predicted by the lubrication approximation and the Hagen-Poiseuille flow equation [34]:

$$\Delta p = \frac{12\mu LV}{b^3}$$

where L and b are the channel length and width, respectively, V and μ are the solution flowing rate and viscosity, respectively, and Δp is the pressure drop in within a slot-die head. The solution flow between the upstream and downstream lips and the meniscus positions are not solely governed by the Poiseuille equation because of the presence of relative motion between the moving surface and the slot-die head, which causes the shear force and a linear variation along the flow channel profile (Fig. 1c), known as Couette flow [35]. Therefore, the equilibrium between the solution flow described by Poiseuille equation and Couette flow determines the positions of both upstream and downstream menisci, where they should stay stable during the coating process (not to move towards the slot-die exit or to expand beyond the channel) to achieve high-quality defect-free coatings.

Fig. 1d demonstrates how the manipulation of operation parameters of a slot-die coater can impact the relative positions of the upstream and downstream menisci, leading to the establishment of a stable coating window across a wide range of operation parameters. Here, the gap to thickness ratio is determined by solution flow rate, coating speed, and coating gap (the distance between the lip and the substrate), where increasing coating gap and coating speed, and/or reducing solution flow rate increase the ratio of gap to thickness. The assessment of operational boundaries entails an intricate balance of opposing forces affecting the coating bead, as capillary, viscous, vacuum pressure, inertial, gravitational, and elastic forces. These forces are notably impacted by geometric parameters and material characteristics, rendering their precise assessment a challenging endeavor.

Organic solar cells

Fullerene-based acceptors have been prevalent in organic solar cells (OSCs) for over two decades, owing to their advantageous properties, including high electron mobility and affinity, solubility, and compatibility with a wide range of donor polymers [36–38]. However, efficiency enhancement of the fullerene-based OSCs faces limitations such as instability of morphology, limited tunability of energy levels, and most importantly, low optical absorption due to the forbidden dipole low-energy transitions in fullerenes [39–41]. Many efforts have been made to overcome these limitations and further increase the efficiency of OSCs, which led to the introduction of a new class of acceptor materials based on polymers and small molecules, the non-fullerene acceptors (NFAs) [42–45]. Rapid advances in NFAs and high tunability of optical properties through molecular structure engineering have replaced fullerene acceptors with them. After slow progress in the efficiency of fullerene-based OSCs before 2018, introducing new polymer donors [46–50] and new NFAs [51–53] in recent years has made a significant improvement in efficiencies from 11.5 % in 2017–19.17 in 2022

[54].

However, there are several critical challenges that OSCs need to overcome for commercialization. First, the manufacturing technique should be suitable for large-area devices. Spin coating as a conventional technique to fabricate small-area devices, utilizing the centrifugal effect to dry the wet film, is not compatible with the requirements of continuous manufacturing. Considering the fact that the conditions of fabrication determine the morphology of bulk heterojunction and film formation and drying behavior depend on fabrication technique, it is vital to look for film optimization strategies to fabricate large-area devices. Moreover, these fabrication strategies should be compatible with non-fullerene acceptors that exhibit different aggregation and packing behaviors compared to fullerene acceptors [55–60]. To deal with this problem, the slot-die technique allows continuous deposition of a large variety of inks, which is compatible with large-area and roll-to-roll (R2R) fabrication. The only major challenge of this technique is to achieve a stable meniscus, which is possible by adjusting mechanical parameters such as flow rate, ink viscosity, the distance between the coating head and the substrate, and the substrate velocity. In addition, since slot-die coating requires a longer time to deposit the films compared to spin coating – it can lead to ink gelation. Hot slot-die coating can overcome this challenge, where the coating head is connected to a thermo-couple and provides additional temperature. Second, toxic halogenated solvents with low boiling points are used to fabricate high-performance devices that require an internal atmosphere, solvent additives, and complex post-treatment techniques and should be replaced by green solvent formulations [41,61–65]. Other challenges are related to developing engineered donor and acceptor materials to form a thick active layer that provides large-area of defect-free, homogeneous, and high-efficiency active layers [41,66–68].

In addition, it is well elucidated that the charge dynamics determining the performance of OSCs are governed by the active layer morphology [69]. The separation of charges and their transfer is influenced by the bulk heterojunction structure, which can be classified into ordered crystallites, relatively pure acceptor and donor domains, and mixed amorphous domains [70,71]. By overcoming the challenges along with adjusting and optimizing the morphology, it is possible to improve the performance of the device by balancing the separation and transfer of charge carriers [72]. The kinetics of film formation and thermodynamic miscibility of donors and acceptors are among the critical factors that should be investigated to achieve an ideal morphology [73–76]. This part will discuss the requirements and optimization strategies including chemical approaches, such as solvent engineering and additive engineering, and physical approaches such as thermal controlling for the slot-die-coated active layer and charge transport layers. Moreover, molecular structures of all the mentioned solvents, donors and acceptors are shown in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4. Additionally, the photovoltaic parameters of slot-die-coated active layer and charge transport layers for OSCs and submodules are summarized in Table 1 and Table 2, respectively.

Active layer

Chemical engineering: solvent and additive engineering

Solvent engineering is one of the decisive strategies in optimizing the morphology of the organic active layer. Since the time of the drying process strongly depends on the solvent evaporation rate, the choice of the solvent determines the crystallization and phase separation of the film [77,78]. Thus, the solvent with a low evaporation rate provides sufficient time for the migration of acceptor and donor molecules and forms a thermodynamically stable morphology. On the other hand, rapid evaporation of the solvent immobilizes the acceptor and donor molecules, which leads to kinetically frozen morphologies. Today, chloroform (CF) and chlorobenzene (CB) are mainly used as solvents in high-efficiency OSCs due to their good solubility [77,79]. Accordingly, Proller et al. [80] presented a system based on in situ measurement for

Fig. 3. The molecular structures of the donors discussed in this review.

Fig. 3. (continued).

Fig. 4. The molecular structures of acceptors discussed in this review.

Fig. 4. (continued).

analyzing the process of morphology formation and investigating the effect of the drying speed of the slot-die-coated P3HT:PCBM active layer processed with CB solvent. They used in situ grazing incidence wide angle X-ray scattering (GIWAXS)[81–83] to investigate the crystallization process and development of order in P3HT polymer and in situ grazing incidence small angle X-ray scattering (GISAXS)[84,85] to investigate the aggregation process of PCBM and development of domains in slot-die-coated P3HT:PCBM films. The results showed that the progress of the structure is independent of drying conditions and occurs in 5 stages where at the first stage, the P3HT polymer crystallizes in the edge-on direction (Fig. 5a, b). Rapid crystal formation leads to

disordered crystal orientation and increased spacing of lateral PCBM clusters. Phase separation of the active layer is determined by the P3HT crystals that separate and aggregate PCBM molecules. In addition, they observed that the growth rate of the slot-die-coated layer differs from that of the blade- and solution-cast-coated samples, where slower solidification kinetics improves device performance.

With this regard, Xue et al.[77] utilized two different devices based on low-miscibility D18:Y6 and high-miscibility PM6:Y6 dissolved in various solvents of CF, CB and their combination (MX) to understand the effect of the kinetic process of film formation on the active layer morphology and performance (Fig. 5c). As the solution phase

Table 1
Photovoltaic parameters of slot-die-coated active layer for OSCs and submodules fabricated by different controlling morphology method. PCE_i = initial PCE.

Controlling morphology method	Configuration	Temperature (°C)	Solvent	Additive	V_{oc} (V)	J_{sc} ($mA\ cm^{-2}$)	FF (%)	PCE (%)	Device area (cm^2)	Thickness (nm)	Stability	Reference
Chemical engineering	ITO glass/PEDOT:PSS/ZnO//PBDB-TSF/IT-4F/PFN-Br/MoO ₃ /Al	RT	CB	DIO	0.88	20.6	71.7	12.9	0.1	95	—	[33]
	PET-ITO/Ag-mesh/PH1000/ZnO/PBDB-TSF/IT-4F/PFN-Br/ MoO ₃ /Al				0.86	20.8	66.7	12.01	0.1	N/A	—	
	PET/Ag-grid/PH1000/PTB7-Th;p-DTS(FBTTH2)2:PC ₇₁ BM/ MoO ₃ /Al	RT	o-XY	—	0.73	18.4	61.9	8.28	1.25	N/A	—	[82,104]
	PET-ITO/ZnO/PTB7-Th;p-DTS(FBTTH2)2:PC ₇₁ BM/MoO ₃ /Al				2.71	3.89	49.2	5.18	20	N/A	—	
	ITO glass/PEDOT:PSS/DPPBT:PCBM/LiF/Al	100	CF: DCB	—	0.75	14.0	0.52	5.5	N/A	100	—	[87]
	PET-ITO/AZO/P3HT:PC ₆₁ BM/MoO ₃ /Ag	RT	o-XY	—	0.58	9.8	54.2	3.10	0.3	150	—	[105]
	PET-ITO/AZO/PTB7:PC ₇₁ BM/MoO ₃ /Ag				0.77	14.0	57.0	6.14	0.3	70	—	
	PET-ITO/AZO/PTB7:PC ₇₁ BM/MoO ₃ /Ag				0.75	14.14	53.5	5.7	2.0	N/A	—	
	ITO glass/PEDOT:PSS/P3HT:PCBM/Ca/Al	30	CB	—	0.55	8.23	68.8	3.11	N/A	150	—	[145]
	ITO glass/PEDOT:PSS/BTR:PC ₇₁ BM/Ca/Al	RT	TO:THF	—	0.91	11.2	72.3	7.46	0.1	N/A	—	[106]
					2.76	1.84	65.9	4.8	10	N/A	—	
	PET-ITO/ZnO/PTB7-Th:PC ₇₁ BM/MoO ₃ /Ag	RT/air flow	DCB/methanol	—	0.76	17.9	64.9	8.89	1.04	110	—	[146]
					4.56	2.77	57.3	7.25	15		~85 % of PCE_i after 5000 bend cycles at R= 5mm	
	PET-ITO/ZnO/PBDB-T:ITIC/MoO ₃ /Ag				0.86	16.9	65.2	9.52	1.04		—	
					5.10	2.79	60.6	8.64	15		~90 % of PCE_i after 5000 bend cycles at R= 5mm	
	PET-ITO/PBDTTTz:PC ₆₀ BM/V ₂ O ₅ /PEDOT:PSS/Ag	90	o-DCB:CN	—	0.81	7.64	52.9	3.28	1	400	—	[147]
	PET/Ag-grid/PEDOT:PSS/ZnO/PDTSTTz-4:PCBM/PEDOT:PSS/Ag	70	o-DCB:CN	—	0.68	8.9	57.0	3.5	1	420	—	[148]
								R2R				
	PET/Ag-grid/PEDOT:PSS PH1000/ZnO/P3HT:PCBM/PEDOT:PSS 4083/PEDOT:PSS F010/Ag	RT	CB	—	0.5	6.82	48.1	1.68	0.526	470	—	[149]
											~70 % of PCE_i after 20 h at 80 °C under continuous AM1.5	
										~80 % of PCE_i after 20 h at 80 °C under continuous AM1.5		
PET/Ag-grid/PEDOT:PSS PH1000/ZnO/P3HT:PCBM/PEDOT:PSS 5010/Ag	RT	CB		0.5	6.68	55.1	1.86			~93 % of PCE_i after 20 h at 80 °C under continuous AM1.5		
										~88 % of PCE_i after 20 h at 80 °C under continuous AM1.5		
										~95 % of PCE_i after 5000 bend cycles	[150]	
PET foil-IMI/ZnO/OPV12:PCBM/ PEDOT/ZnO/Ba(OH) ₂ /pDPP5T-2: PCBM/MoO _x /Ag	RT	CB (OPV12:PCBM)/CB:DCB (pDPP5T-2:PCBM)	—	3.92	2.25	65.0	5.7	10	160 (OPV12:PCBM)/80 (pDPP5T-2:PCBM)			
PET-ITO/AZO/P3HT:PCBM/PEDOT:PSS/Ag	65	o-XY	—	0.55	8.94	62.0	3.05	0.104	120	—	[151]	
		o-XY:THN		0.56	9.14	67.0	3.42			—		
	80	anisole:THN		0.57	9.09	65.0	3.37			—		
ITO glass/PEDOT:PSS/ P3HT:PCBM/Al	80/N ₂	CB	—	0.58	8.93	52.0	2.72	1	N/A	—	[152]	
		DCB		0.57	8.17	53.0	2.49		N/A	—		
		CB:DCB		0.57	9.95	55.0	3.12		N/A	—		
ITO glass/ZnO/PCDTBT:PC ₇₁ BM/MoO ₃ /Ag	RT	DCB	—	0.90	12.4	60.1	6.72	0.1	70	—	[153]	
				4.35	10.2	51.1	4.56	47.2	100	—		
ITO glass/ZnO/PTB7-Th:PC ₇₀ BM /MoO ₃ /Ag	RT	CB	DIO	2.36	4.98	62.0	7.3	4.15	125	—	[154]	
				2.37	4.87	58.0	6.7	16.6		—		
ITO glass/PEDOT:PSS/ P3HT:PC70BM/LiF/Al	RT/85	CF	DIO	1.54	2.1	55.0	2.09	9.0	100	—	[155]	
PET/IMI/ZnO/PBTZT-stat-BDIT-8:PC ₆₀ BM/ PEDOT:PSS/AgNWs	RT	o-XY:THN	—	0.8	8.8	59.0	4.1	0.1	290	—	[156]	
				14.9	9.6	57.0	4.3	68.76		—		

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

Controlling morphology method	Configuration	Temperature (°C)	Solvent	Additive	V_{oc} (V)	J_{sc} (mA cm ⁻²)	FF (%)	PCE (%)	Device area (cm ²)	Thickness (nm)	Stability	Reference
	PET/Ag/ZnO/PEDOT:PSS/PBDTBT/PC ₆₀ BM/Ag	RT	GBY:CN	—	0.84	13.3	50.6	8.96 R2R	0.04	100	~88 % of PCE _i after 5000 bend cycles & ~89 % of PCE _i after 240 h in air	[158]
	ITO glass/ZnO/P3HT:IDTBR/ PEDOT:PSS/Ag	80	CB:BrA	—	0.69	9.8	64.9	4.4	59.5	200	—	[159]
	ITO/PEDOT:PSS/LGC-D073: PC ₇₀ BM/BCP/Ag	RT/N ₂ blowing	CB	DIO	0.82	11.3	62.0	5.82	24	100	—	[160]
	ITO glass/ZnO/PBDB-T-SF:IT-4F/MoO ₃ /Al	RT	CB	DIO	0.87	19.5	52.0	8.95	0.12	100	—	[161]
	ITO glass/PEDOT:PSS/ PTzBI:N2200/PFN-Br/Ag	RT/120	MTHF	DIO	0.83	15.3	70.0	8.88	0.1	110	—	[162]
	PET/Ag/ZnO/PBDB-T:ITIC/HTL Solar/ CPP PEDOT:PSS	RT	CB	DIO	0.86	12.1	49.0	5.07	0.05	190	~100 % of PCE _i after 900 h in air (dark, ambient air)	[163]
	ITO glass/PEI/ PV2000:PCBM/MoO ₃ /Al	60/120	o-XY	—	3.88	66.5 Isc	59.0	6.40	23.7	250	~0 % of PCE _i after 144 h in air (light soaking stability)	[164]
	ITO glass/PEI/ PV2000:PCBM/PEDOT:PSS/Al				4.04	67.96 Isc	65.3	7.56			~91.7 % of PCE _i after 1000 h in air (light soaking stability)	
	ITO glass/ZnO/QX-3:tPDI2N-EH /MoO _x /Ag	RT	TO:DPE	—	1.09	12.4	54.0	7.3	N/A	60	—	[165]
	ITO glass /ZnO/PEIE/PPDT2FBT:PC ₆₀ BM/MoO _x /Ag	RT	o-XY:DPE	—	0.78	14.6	74	8.48	0.09	N/A	—	[166]
	ITO glass/ PEDOT:PSS/PTzBI-Si:N2200/C60-N/Ag	RT/130	CB	—	0.87	4.6	51.1	2.04	0.04	N/A	—	[167]
			MTHF		0.88	17.6	75.8	11.7			~96.8 % of PCE _i after 480 h in N ₂	
	PET-ITO/Ag/ZnO/PBDTBT-T:ITIC/PEDOT:PSS/ CPP PEDOT:PSS	RT	CB	DIO	0.8	10.3	39.0	3.18	3.24	300	—	[168]
	ITO glass/ZnO/	RT	CF	—	0.85	23.5	64.5	13.2	0.152	80–90	—	[169]
	PDTBT2T-FTBDT:BTP-4F/MoO ₃ /Ag											
	ITO glass/PEDOT:PSS/PM6:Y6/PFN-Br/Ag	RT/100	CF	—	0.84	25.6	75.5	16.2	N/A	N/A	—	[78]
			CF:CN		0.83	22.5	62.1	11.9			—	
			CB		0.79	15.9	53.9	6.85			—	
			TO		0.79	9.10	54.2	3.95			—	
	ITO glass/ZnO/D18:Y6/MoO ₃ /Al	RT	CB	—	0.82	24.0	68.4	13.4	0.04	110	—	[77]
			CF		0.84	27.4	73.9	17.1			—	
			CF:CB		0.83	26.1	70.3	15.2			—	
	ITO glass/ZnO/PM6:Y6/MoO ₃ /Al	RT	CB	—	0.8	16.4	58.5	7.7	0.9	110	—	[79]
			o-XY		0.78	12.6	54.5	5.3			—	
			TMB		0.76	15.1	55.3	6.3			—	
	ITO/PEDOT: PSS/PM6:ITIC/PFN-Br/Ag	RT/100	CB	—	1.04	15.1	55.9	8.77	0.04	125	—	[90]
				DIO	1.04	16.1	57.2	9.59			—	
	ITO glass/ZnO/PTB7-Th:PC ₆₁ BM/MoO ₃ /Ag	RT/N ₂ blowing	CB	—	0.77	14.7	38.7	4.90	0.1	10–100	~72.8 % of PCE _i after 450 h in 60 % RH at 25 °C	[102]
				DIW	0.77	15.8	42.7	5.51			~96.1 % of PCE _i after 450 h in 60 % RH at 25 °C	
					3.08	3.58	49.5	4.95	10		—	
	ITO glass/ZnO/PTB7-Th:EH-IDTBR/MoO ₃ /Ag			—	0.99	14.1	52.9	7.66	0.1		~34.1 % of PCE _i after 450 h in 60 % RH at 25 °C	
				DIW	1.01	14.8	55.9	8.54			~46.8 % of PCE _i after 450 h in 60 % RH at 25 °C	
					3.89	3.14	50.2	6.15	10		—	

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

Controlling morphology method	Configuration	Temperature (°C)	Solvent	Additive	V_{oc} (V)	J_{sc} (mA cm^{-2})	FF (%)	PCE (%)	Device area (cm^2)	Thickness (nm)	Stability	Reference	
Physical engineering	ITO glass/ZnO/PM6:Y6/MoO ₃ /Ag			—	0.75	23.7	65.3	11.7	0.1		~77.8 % of PCE _i after 450 h in 60 % RH at 25 °C		
				DIW	0.74	26.0	67.1	13.1	~86.2 % of PCE _i after 450 h in 60 % RH at 25 °C				
	ITO glass/PEDOT:PSS/PM6:L8-BO/PDINO/Ag	RT/100	o-XY	—	4.49	6.3	41.8	11.9	10	110	—	[144]	
		40/100		TO:2-MeTHF	—	0.87	25.4	77.2	16.9		0.04		—
	ITO glass/SnO ₂ /PDIN-H/ PTQ10:BTP-4F-12/MoO _x /Ag	40/100	TO:2-MeTHF	—	0.85	22.1	64.8	12.1	0.14	93	—	[170]	
	ITO glass/ZnO/ PPDT2FBT:PC ₆₁ BM/MoO _x /Al		o-DCB:CN	—	0.80	15.9	0.62	7.27	0.1	150–200	~80 % of PCE _i after 388 h at 85 °C under dark N ₂ at	[171]	
	ITO glass/ZnO/PBDB-T:PZT-γ/MoO _x /Al	130	o-XY	—	0.87	24.7	69.6	15.0	0.04	100	—	[172]	
		100		CB	—	0.89	24.7	60.1	13.3		—		
	ITO glass/PEDOT:PSS/P3HT:PC ₇₁ BM/Bi:In:Sn	RT/85	CF	DIO	0.57	7.69	55.0	2.4	3.0	100	—	[155]	
	ITO-PET/Parylene/AgNWs//SnO ₂ /PV2000:PCBM/PEDOT:PSS/Ag	40	o-XY	—	1.54	2.09	55.0	2.1	9.0	250–400	—	[173]	
				—	3.85	10.8	58.2	4.85	7.5		90 % of PCE _i after 500 bend cycles		
	ITO glass/ZnO/PV-X/MoO ₃ /Ag	70	ink	—	0.69	22.6	69.0	11.0	0.3	120	—	[174]	
	PET-ITO/AZO/PTB7:PC ₇₁ BM/MoO ₃ /Ag	60	o-XY	—	0.68	4.23	34.7	1.0	0.3	85	~75 % of PCE _i after 250 h in N ₂	[114]	
				—	0.76	13.6	62.9	6.49	~82 % of PCE _i after 250 h in N ₂				
	PET-ITO/ZnO/PV2000:PC ₇₁ BM/MoO ₃ /Ag	RT	o-XY	DIO	CN:DIO	0.86	3.61	44.5	1.36	90	200	~82 % of PCE _i after 250 h under continuous illumination AM1.5	[175]
												—	
	PET-TCO/ZnO/PV-X/MoO _x /Ag	60/120	Ink	—	5.40	2.71	42.5	6.2	47.04		—	[176]	
	PET-ITO/ZnO/PBDB-T:ITIC/MoO ₃ /Ag	120	CB	—	0.86	15.3	53.0	7.0	0.3	170	—	[113]	
				CB	DIO	0.90	16.2	56.0	8.20		—		
	ITO glass/SnO ₂ /PBI-Y/ PM6/Y6Cl2/MoO ₃ /Ag	50/100	o-XY	—	0.78	22.3	60.2	10.4	0.12	N/A	—	[177]	
		RT		CF:CN	—	0.85	22.6	67.8	13.07		1.0		N/A
	PET-ITO/PEDOT:PSS/D18-N-p:L8-BO/PNDIT-F3N/Ag	RT	DCB	—	0.80	10.6	48.0	4.06	1.0	250	—	[178]	
	ITO glass/ZnO/P3HT:ICBA/ PEDOT:PSS/Ag	RT	DCB	—	0.80	10.6	48.0	4.06	1.0	250	—	[179]	
	PET-ITO/PEDOT:PSS/PPDT2FBT:PC ₆₁ BM/SnO ₂ /Ag	RT	CB	—	0.73	10.8	49.0	3.9	0.14	N/A	—	[180]	
	ITO glass/ZnO/PM6:Y6/MoO ₃ /Al	RT	o-XY	—	0.78	12.6	54.5	5.3	0.09	110	—	[79]	
		100		—	0.81	26.6	70.3	15.2	—				
	ITO glass/ZnO/PBDB-T:i-IEICO-4F/MoO ₃ /Al	80	CB	—	0.9	19.6	68.1	12.2	0.04	110	—	[181]	
	ITO glass/ZnO/PPDT2FBT:PC ₇₁ BM/MoO ₃ /Al	RT	o-DCB	—	0.62	7.3	0.52	2.35	0.1	280	—	[182]	
80		—		0.78	14.8	0.66	7.61	250	—				
ITO glass/ZnO/PM6:BTR-Cl:CHI007/MoO ₃ /Al	100	o-XY	—	0.82	27.0	74.1	16.3	0.04	100	—	[126]		
			—	0.79	29.0	66.7	15.4	0.04		300		—	
PET-ITO/ZnO/PM6:BTR-Cl:CHI007/MoO ₃ /Al			—	0.81	26.9	67.8	14.8	1	100	—			
			ITO glass/ZnO/PM6:BTR-Cl:Y6/MoO ₃ /Al	—	0.82	26.7	71.0	15.6		0.04		100	—
PET-ITO/ZnO/PM6:BTR-Cl:Y6/MoO ₃ /Al			—	0.767	29.2	61.7	13.8	0.04	300	—			
			—	0.81	26.4	65.9	14.1	1		102		—	
ITO glass/ZnO:PEIE/PBDB-T: ITIC/MoO ₃ /Ag	120	DCB	—	0.88	17.5	64.9	10.0	0.1	90	—	[183]		
PET-ITO/ZnO:PEIE/PBDB-T: ITIC/MoO ₃ /Ag			—	0.86	14.2	58.13	7.11		N/A	—			
			—	0.86	14.2	58.13	7.11			—			
ITO glass/ZnO/PTB7-Th:PC ₇₁ BM:COi8DFIC /MoO ₃ /Al	RT	CB	DIO	0.7	25.9	64.9	11.9	0.1	120	—	[137]		

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

Controlling morphology method	Configuration	Temperature (°C)	Solvent	Additive	V_{oc} (V)	J_{sc} (mA cm ⁻²)	FF (%)	PCE (%)	Device area (cm ²)	Thickness (nm)	Stability	Reference
	PET-ITO/ZnO/PTB7-Th:PC ₇₁ BM:COi8DFIC/MoO ₃ /Al	80			0.58	28.8	59.5	9.29	0.14		—	
	ITO/PEDOT:PSS/PTB7-h:IEICO-4F/AZO/Ag	60	CB:CN	—	0.7	22.3	58.0	9.4	0.1	90	~50 % of PCE _i after 600 h at 85 °C in N ₂	[184]
	ITO/ZnO/PTB7-Th:IEICO-4F/ PEDOT:PSS&MoO ₃ /Ag	35	CB:CN	—	0.7	24.2	64.0	11.1	0.1		~80 % of PCE _i after 600 h at 85 °C in N ₂	
	PET/silver-grid/PEDOT:PSS/ZnO/PTB7-Th:COi8DFIC:PCBM/MoO _x /Ag	RT	o-XY	—	0.69	22.9	59.0	9.63	1	150	—	[185]
		80			0.68	16.6	43.1	4.82	1	110	~99 % of PCE _i after 1000 bend cycles at R= 10 mm & ~103 % of PCE _i after over 6000 h in N ₂	
	ITO glass/ZnO/SMD2:ITIC-Th/WO ₃ /MoO ₃ /Ag	80			3.46	4.93	59.1	10.09	25	110	—	[186]
	PET-ITO/ZnO/SMD2:ITIC-Th/WO ₃ /PEDOT:PSS/Ag	160	CB	DIO	0.88	19.3	68.3	11.6	0.04	200	85 % of PCE _i after 143 h in 85 % RH at 65 °C	
	ITO glass/PEDOT:PSS/P3HT:PCBM/Al	80	CB	—	0.6	8.77	58.0	3.07	1	50	—	[187]
	PET-ITO/AZO:PEIE/P3HT:PCBM/ MoO ₃ /Al	130	CB	—	0.56	8.02	51.0	2.29	5	N/A	—	[188]
	ITO glass/ZnO/PCDTBT:PC ₇₀ BM/MoO ₃ /Al	70	o-DCB:CB	—	0.60	7.28	0.6	2.69	0.3	150	—	[189]
	ITO glass/ZnO/PM7:IT4F/MoO ₃ /Al	RT	CB	DIO	0.87	10.7	39.6	3.69	5.6	110	—	[190]
		40			4.40	1.8	40.2	3.18	35.2		—	
		60			0.86	20.4	57.3	10.0	0.95		—	
		100			0.87	21.0	62.9	11.6			—	
	ITO glass/ ZnO/DRCN5T:PC ₇₁ BM/ MoO ₃ /Ag	50	o-XY	—	0.87	21.3	68.5	13.2		100	—	[191]
		60			0.85	20.0	63.3	10.7			—	
		70			0.94	13.5	52.0	6.60	0.3		—	
	PET-ITO/ZnO/PM6:Y6/MoO ₃ /Ag	80		—	0.93	14.8	55.7	7.6		200	—	[108]
		100			0.93	12.3	51.5	5.9			—	
		120			0.71	16.5	43.1	4.8	0.8		—	
	ITO glass/ZnO/ PBDB-T:PZT-γ/MoO _x /Al	50	o-XY	—	0.71	16.7	47.1	5.5		100	—	[172]
					0.72	17.8	42.2	5.4			—	
	ITO glass/PEDOT:PSS/ZR1-C3:L8-BO/PFNBr/Ag	RT	THF	—	0.9	21.8	46.7	9.19	0.04	130	—	[192]
		130			0.87	24.7	69.6	15.0			—	
	PET/Ag-grid/PEDOT:PSS PH1000/ZnO/PM6:Qx-1/MoO _x /Ag	RT	o-XY	DIO	0.89	16.6	42.3	6.29	N/A	113	—	[121]
		80			0.89	22.5	57.0	11.3	1		—	
					0.89	21.6	71.0	13.7			—	
	Ag-grid/PH1000/ZnO/PM6:L8-BO:PJ1/MoO ₃ /Ag	40/airflow	o-XY	DIO	5.24	3.53	66.0	12.2	30	129	103 % of PCE _i after 6000 h in N ₂	[112]
		85/airflow			0.85	21.3	66.8	12.02	1.0	156	—	
					0.85	24.0	67.3	13.69	1.0		—	
					5.02	4.0	64.8	13.08	30.0		103 % of PCE _i after 250 days in N ₂	

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

Controlling morphology method	Configuration	Temperature (°C)	Solvent	Additive	V_{oc} (V)	J_{sc} (mA cm ⁻²)	FF (%)	PCE (%)	Device area (cm ²)	Thickness (nm)	Stability	Reference	
Ternary & sequential processing	PET-ITO/Ag-grid/PH1000/ZnO/PTQ10:PYF-T-o/MoO ₃ /Ag	30	o-XY:CN	—	0.91	19.9	62.1	11.24	1.0	N/A	95 % of PCE _i after 1000 bend cycles at R= 5 mm	[107]	
	PET-ITO/AZO/PTB7:PC ₇₁ BM/MoO ₃ /Ag	70 30 60	o-XY	CN:DIO	0.88 0.74	16.9 13.9	54.2 61.2	8.10 6.24	8.10 0.3	N/A 85	— —	[114]	
	PET silver-grid/PH1000/ZnO/PM6:L8-BO/MoO _x /Ag	40 80 100	o-XY	—	0.81 0.80 0.80	21.6 21.8 21.9	64.9 67.7 68.9	11.37 11.81 12.17	1.0	N/A	— — —	[193]	
	PET-ITO/ZnO/PBDB-T:ITIC/MoO ₃ /Ag	100 120 140	CB	DIO	0.86 0.87 0.86	12.6 14.8 14.4	56.0 57.0 54.0	7.05 7.34 6.70	0.3	170	— — —	[113]	
	flextrode/P3HT:OIDTBR/PEDOT:PSS/Ag	RT 60	DCB	BrA	0.68 0.72	4.8 7.9	51.9 60.5	1.71 3.45	1.0	480	— —	[194]	
	ITO glass/ZnO/D18:BTR-Cl:Y6/MoO ₃ /Al	RT	CF	—	0.86	26.9	74.4	17.2	0.04	110	—	[127]	
	ITO glass/ZnO:PEI/PM6:Y6/MoO ₃ /Ag	135	CB:CF	—	0.8	25.3	71.3	14.1	0.04	120	—	[195]	
	PET-ITO/ZnO/PTB7-Th:PCBM/MoO _x /Ag	RT	CF	—	0.75	24.5	65.2	11.9	—	—	—	[144]	
	PET-ITO/ZnO/PTB7-Th/PCBM/MoO _x /Ag	—	o-XY	DIO	0.78	13.5	46.6	4.86	0.75	200	—	—	
	PET-ITO/ZnO/PTB7-Th:p-DTS (FBTTH2)2:PCBM/MoO _x /Ag	—	—	—	0.76	14.3	50.3	5.51	—	—	—	—	
	PET-ITO/ZnO/PTB7-Th:p-DTS (FBTTH2)2:PCBM/MoO _x /Ag	—	—	—	0.73	16.4	50.9	6.09	—	—	—	—	
	PET-ITO/ZnO/PTB7-Th/p-DTS (FBTTH2)2:PCBM/MoO _x /Ag	—	—	—	0.73	19.6	51.2	7.32	—	—	—	—	
	ITO glass/ZnO/PM6:BTR-Cl:CH1007/MoO ₃ /Al	100	o-XY	—	0.82 0.79 0.81	27.0 29.0 26.9	74.1 66.7 67.8	16.3 15.4 14.8	0.04 0.04 1	101 303 100	— — —	[126]	
	PET-ITO/ZnO/PM6:BTR-Cl:CH1007/MoO ₃ /Al	—	—	—	0.81	24.0	73.6	14.2	0.04	106	—	—	
	ITO glass/ZnO/PM6:BTR-Cl:Y6/MoO ₃ /Al	—	—	—	0.79	25.4	66.3	13.3	—	303	—	—	
	PET-ITO/ZnO/PM6:BTR-Cl:Y6/MoO ₃ /Al	—	—	—	0.82	26.7	71.0	15.6	0.04	102	—	—	
	PET-ITO/ZnO/PM6:BTR-Cl:Y6/MoO ₃ /Al	—	—	—	0.767	29.2	61.7	13.8	—	297	—	—	
	PET-ITO/ZnO/PM6:BTR-Cl:Y6/MoO ₃ /Al	—	—	—	0.81	26.4	65.9	14.1	1	100	—	—	
	PET-ITO/ZnO/PM6:BTR-Cl:Y6/MoO ₃ /Al	—	—	—	0.81	24.1	70.4	13.7	0.04	101	—	—	
	PET-ITO/ZnO/PM6:BTR-Cl:Y6/MoO ₃ /Al	—	—	—	0.76	25.5	60.2	11.7	—	300	—	—	
	ITO glass/PEDOT:PSS/(PM6/Y6-C12)/PFN-Br/Ag	60/RT	o-XY/o-XY	—	0.8	23.8	56.0	10.6	0.12	65/100	—	40 % of PCE _i after 840 h in N ₂	[143]
	ITO glass/PEDOT:PSS/(PM6/L8-BO)/PDINO/Ag	RT/100	o-XY	—	0.87	25.4	77.2	16.9	0.04	110	—	60 % of PCE _i after 840 h in N ₂	[142]
	ITO glass/PEDOT:PSS/PM6:L8-BO/PDINO/Ag	—	—	—	0.87	24.9	75.6	16.3	—	—	—	—	—

Table 2
Photovoltaic parameters of slot-die-coated charge transport layers for OSCs and submodules. PCE_i = initial PCE.

Charge transport layer	Configuration	Charge transport material	Temperature (°C)	V_{oc} (V)	J_{sc} (mA cm^{-2})	FF (%)	PCE (%)	Device area (cm^2)	Thickness (nm)	Stability	Reference
HTL	ITO/PEDOT:PSS/PTB7-h:IEICO-4F/AZO/Ag	PEDOT:PSS	35/120	0.7	22.3	58.0	9.4	0.1	30	~50 % of PCE_i after 600 h at 85 °C in N_2	[184]
	ITO/ZnO/PTB7-Th:IEICO-4F/PEDOT:PSS&MoO ₃ /Ag	PEDOT:PSS	RT	0.7	24.2	64.0	11.1	0.1	15	~80 % of PCE_i after 600 h at 85 °C in N_2	[184]
	PET-ITO/PBDTTTz:PC ₆₀ BM/V ₂ O ₅ /PEDOT:PSS/Ag	V ₂ O ₅ /PEDOT:PSS	30	0.81	7.64	52.9	3.28	1	20/1200	—	[147]
	ITO glass/ZnO/SMD2:ITIC-Th/WO ₃ /PEDOT:PSS/Ag	WO ₃ /PEDOT:PSS	RT	0.89	17.3	66.0	10.3	0.04	20/30	—	[186]
	PET-ITO/ZnO/SMD2:ITIC-Th/PEDOT:PSS/Ag	PEDOT:PSS		7.76	0.97	26.7	2.02	80	N/A	—	
	PET-ITO/ZnO/SMD2:ITIC-Th/WO ₃ /PEDOT:PSS/Ag	WO ₃ /PEDOT:PSS		8.80	1.12	53.1	5.25		20/30	85 % of PCE_i after 143 h in 85 % RH at 65 °C	
	ITO glass/PEDOT:PSS/ P3HT:PCBM/Al	PEDOT:PSS	RT/140	0.6	8.77	58.0	3.07	1	N/A	—	[187]
	PET/Ag-grid/PEDOT:PSS/ZnO/ PDTSTTz-4:PCBM/PEDOT:PSS/Ag	Back PEDOT:PSS	80	0.56	8.02	51.0	2.29	5			
				0.68	8.9	57.0	3.5	1	250	—	[148]
	PET/Ag-grid/PEDOT:PSS PH1000/ZnO/ P3HT:PCBM/PEDOT:PSS 4083/ PEDOT:PSS F010/Ag	PEDOT:PSS 4083/ PEDOT:PSS F010	70	0.53	6.49	60.0	2.05	0.526	8 * 10 ³ / 23 * 10 ³ (wet thicknesses)	~80 % of PCE_i after 20 h at 80 °C under continuous AM1.5	[149]
	PET/Ag-grid/PEDOT:PSS PH1000/ZnO/ P3HT:PCBM/PEDOT:PSS 5010/Ag	PEDOT:PSS 5010		0.51	6.51	58.6	1.96		1000	~88 % of PCE_i after 20 h at 80 °C under continuous AM1.5	
	ITO-PET/AZO/P3HT:PCBM PEDOT:PSS/Ag	PEDOT:PSS	RT	0.56	9.14	67.0	3.42	0.104	40	—	[151]
	ITO glass/PEDOT:PSS/ P3HT:PCBM/Al	PEDOT:PSS	140	0.57	9.95	55.0	3.12	1	N/A	—	[152]
	PET/Ag/PFN/PTB7-PC ₇₁ BM/PEDOT:PSS	PEDOT:PSS	RT	0.74	12.2	51.5	4.96	0.04	100	~88 % of PCE_i after 5000 bend cycles & ~89 % of PCE_i after 240 h at air	[158]
								R2R			
ITO glass/SnO ₂ /PDIN-H/ PTQ10:BTP-4F-12/PEDOT:PSS/Ag	PEDOT:PSS	40/100	0.81	19.5	60.3	9.55	0.14	N/A	—	[170]	
PET silver-grid/PH1000/ZnO/ PM6:L8-BO/ MoO _x /Ag	PH1000	RT/120	0.80	21.9	68.9	12.17	1.0	N/A	—	[193]	
ITO glass/ZnO/PEIE/PBDBT:ITIC/MoO ₃ /Ag	MoO ₃	120	0.75	11.8	50.9	4.50	0.12	20	—	[231]	
ITO glass/ZnO/P3HT:ICBA/ PEDOT:PSS/Ag	PEDOT:PSS	RT/150	0.80	10.6	48.0	4.06	1.0	1000	—	[179]	
flextrode/P3HT:O-IDTBR/ PEDOT:PSS/Ag	PEDOT:PSS	70	0.72	7.9	60.5	3.45	1.0	1000	—	[194]	
PET-ITO/PEDOT:PSS/PPDT2FBT:PC ₆₁ BM/SnO ₂ /Ag	PEDOT:PSS	60/100	0.73	10.8	49.0	3.9	0.14	N/A	—	[180]	
PET/IML/ZnO/PBTZT-stat-BDIT-8:PC ₆₀ BM/PEDOT:PSS/AgNWs	PEDOT:PSS	40/120	14.9	9.6	57.0	4.3	68.76	100	—	[156]	
ETL	PET-ITO/AZO/PTB7:PC ₇₁ BM/MoO ₃ /Ag	AZO	RT	0.77	14.0	57.0	6.14	0.3	60	—	[105]
	PET-ITO/ZnO/PTB7-Th:PC ₇₁ BM:COi8DFIC /MoO ₃ /Al	ZnO	100/120	0.68	22.2	59.5	9.6	0.14	120	—	[137]
							R2R				
	ITO/PEDOT:PSS/PTB7-h:IEICO-4F/AZO/Ag	AZO	RT	0.7	22.3	58.0	9.4	0.1	20	~50 % of PCE_i after 600 h at 85 °C in N_2	[184]
ITO/ZnO/PTB7-Th:IEICO-4F/PEDOT:PSS&MoO ₃ /Ag	ZnO	35/150	0.7	24.2	64.0	11.1	0.1	25	~80 % of PCE_i after 600 h at 85 °C in N_2		

(continued on next page)

Table 2 (continued)

Charge transport layer	Configuration	Charge transport material	Temperature (°C)	V_{oc} (V)	J_{sc} (mA cm ⁻²)	FF (%)	PCE (%)	Device area (cm ²)	Thickness (nm)	Stability	Reference
	PET/silver-grid/ZnO/PTB7-Th:COi8DFIC:PCBM/MoO ₃ /Ag	ZnO	RT	0.69	26.7	65.8	12.2	1	N/A	~99 % of PCE _i after 1000 bend cycles at R= 10 mm & ~103 % of PCE _i after over 6000 h in N ₂	[185]
	ITO glass/ZnO/SMD2:ITIC-Th/WO ₃ /PEDOT:PSS/Ag PET-ITO/ZnO/SMD2:ITIC-Th/WO ₃ /PEDOT:PSS/Ag	ZnO	RT	3.46	4.93	59.1	10.09	25	N/A	—	[186]
		ZnO	RT	0.89	17.3	66.0	10.3	0.04	N/A	—	
				8.80	1.12	53.1	5.25	80		85 % of PCE _i after 143 h in 85 % RH at 65 °C	
	PET-ITO/ZnO/P3HT:PCBM/ MoO ₃ /Al	ZnO	150	0.59	6.11	54.0	1.95	0.3	60	—	[188]
	PET-ITO/ZnO:PEIE/P3HT:PCBM/ MoO ₃ /Al	ZnO:PEIE		0.59	7.38	55.0	2.40			—	
	PET-ITO/AZO/P3HT:PCBM/ MoO ₃ /Al	AZO		0.60	6.76	0.59	2.39			—	
	PET-ITO/AZO:PEIE/P3HT:PCBM/ MoO ₃ /Al	AZO:PEIE		0.60	7.28	0.61	2.69			—	
	ITO glass/ZnO/PTB7-Th:PC ₇₀ BM /MoO ₃ /Ag	ZnO	40/150	2.36	4.98	62.0	7.3	4.15	N/A	—	[154]
	ITO glass/ ZnO/PCDTBT: PC70BM/MoO ₃ /Al	ZnO	65/120	0.87	10.7	39.6	3.69	5.6	20	—	[189]
	ITO glass/ZnO/PV2000:PCBM/MoO ₃ /Al	ZnO	120	0.81	16.3	74.2	9.80	0.04	N/A	—	[164]
	ITO glass/PEI/ PV2000:PCBM/MoO ₃ /Al	PEI		0.81	16.0	72.4	9.38			—	
	ITO glass/ZnO/PV-X/MoO ₃ /Ag	ZnO	60/120	0.69	22.6	69.0	11.0	0.3	50	—	[174]
	Ag grid/PH1000/ZnO/PM6:L8-BO:PJ1/MoO ₃ /Ag	ZnO	RT	0.85	24.0	67.3	13.69	1.0	N/A	—	[112]
	PET-ITO/Ag-grid/PH1000/ZnO/PTQ10:PYF-T-o/MoO ₃ /Ag	ZnO	RT	0.91	19.9	62.1	11.24	1.0	N/A	95 % of PCE _i after 1000 bend cycles at R= 5 mm	[107]
	PET-ITO/ZnO/PV2000:PC ₇₁ BM/MoO ₃ /Ag	ZnO	150	0.86	3.61	44.5	1.36	90	30	~82 % of PCE _i after 250 h under continuous illumination AM1.5	[175]
	PET-TCO/ZnO/PV-X/MoO _x /Ag	ZnO	50/120	0.69	21.1	61.9	9.07	0.3	50	—	[176]
	ITO glass/PEDOT:PSS/PM6:Y6/F-PDIN-EH/Ag	F-PDIN-EH	30	0.79	24.5	51.3	10.01	0.14	N/A	—	[232]
	PET silver-grid/PH1000/ZnO/PM6:L8-BO/MoO _x /Ag	ZnO	RT	0.80	21.9	68.9	12.17	1.0	N/A	—	[193]
	ITO glass/SnO ₂ /PBI-Y/ PM6/Y6C12/MoO ₃ /Ag	SnO ₂ /PBI-Y	50	0.78	22.3	60.2	10.4	0.12	N/A	—	[177]
	ITO glass/SnO ₂ /PDIN-H/PBDBT:ITIC/PEDOT:PSS/Ag	SnO ₂	50/200	0.82	19.5	60.3	9.55	0.12	N/A	—	[170]
	ITO glass/SnO ₂ /PM6:IT-4F/MoO ₃ /Ag	SnO ₂	50/120	0.85	21.3	78.0	14.1	0.041	10	—	[229]
	PET/IMI/ZnO/PBTZT-stat-BDIT-8:PC ₆₀ BM/PEDOT:PSS /AgNWs	ZnO	40/80	14.9	9.6	57.0	4.3	68.76	50	—	[156]
	ITO glass/PEDOT:PSS/PPDT2FBT:IDIC/SnO ₂ /Ag	SnO ₂	RT/120	0.9	14.6	50.0	6.6	0.14	N/A	—	[180]
	PET-ITO/PEDOT:PSS/PPDT2FBT:PC ₆₁ BM/SnO ₂ /Ag		60/120	0.73	10.8	49.0	3.9			—	

Fig. 5. (a) 2D GIWAXS patterns of the coated film at room temperature (RT) at five different stages (left) [80]. The ring-like signal is attributed to chlorobenzene. By increasing the drying time, the (100) peak of P3HT appeared in later phases and transformed into a more ring-like structure. The schematic depicts (right) an edge-on oriented P3HT crystal, showing the lamellar backbone spacing in the [100] direction and the π - π stacking in the [010] direction. (b) The structure development over time obtained from GIWAXS and GISAXS experiments [80]. The observed stages were labeled, with the most significant changes occurring in the initial to final phases. The solvent, PCBM aggregates, P3HT chains, and crystalline P3HT domains were represented by blue dots, green cylinders, black lines, and rectangles, respectively. For clarity, only a single layer of the bulk film was shown. (c) Schematic diagram of the aggregation status in solution and film for D18:Y6 and PM6:Y6 processed by CF and MX (a mixture of CF and CB) [77]. (d) AFM images of PM6:Y6 blend films and J - V curves of OSCs based on slot-die-coated PM6:Y6 processed by different solvents [78].

(a) (a-b) Printed with permission from Ref [80]. (b) (d) Printed with permission from Ref [78]. (c) (c) Printed with permission from Ref [77].

transitioned to solid, in situ UV-visible absorption and photoluminescence characterization techniques were measured. Thus, they found that D18:Y6 dissolved in CF and MX had the same solution states at the beginning of the film formation. During half a second of the film formation time, it thickened and provided the optimal morphology and higher power conversion efficiencies (PCEs) of 17.38 % and 15.16 %,

respectively. In addition, strong interactions between D18 and Y6 dissolved in CB leads to excessive aggregation and phase separation of D18:Y6, decreasing the device PCE to 13.44 %. On the other hand, the very low dependence of morphology and performance of high miscibility PM6:Y6-based devices processed in CF, CB, and MX solvents led to PCEs of 14.70 %, 14.01 % and 14.23 %, respectively. To further investigate

the role of solvents in the morphology of slot-die-coated PM6:Y6 blend, Wang et al. [78] used different solvents, including CF, the combination of CF with chloronaphthalene (CN), CB, and toluene (TO). It should be taken into accounts that a suitable solvent should not lead to over-crystallization and/or suppress crystallization. Therefore, the results showed that the CN/CF solvent over-crystallized Y6 and made the domain size larger than the exciton diffusion length. On the other hand, the low crystallization rate of Y6 in CB and TO solvents led to the formation of large-scale amorphous aggregates and increased recombination loss (Fig. 5d). In a slot-die coating, they concluded that a solvent should have a high evaporation rate and be well soluble with the blend to achieve the desired crystallization and phase separation. Furthermore, CF with the formation of fibrillar network morphology and improved crystallization facilitated the separation, transfer, and extraction of charge carriers, resulting in an efficiency of 16.22%. Additionally, as shown in Fig. 5d, the devices based on PM6:Y6 active layer prepared in TO, CB, and CF:CN, the PCEs of 3.95%, 6.85%, and 11.89% were attained, respectively.

Using suitable additive agents that show different solubilities towards the donor and acceptor is another effective method that can optimize the crystallization and packing behavior of the blend during film formation[86]. A solvent additive should possess high boiling points (BPs) and selective solubilities for donor and acceptor molecules. The low solvent volatility of the additive provides sufficient time for it to interact with organic molecules, which shows the influential role of the additive, even in small amounts, in changing the nanostructure of the film. Liu et al. [87] added 1,2-dichlorobenzene (DCB; BP: 178 °C; vapor pressure (VP): 1 mmHg) as an additive to the primary CF solvent and investigated the effect of DCB volume percentages on the morphology and performance of the device based on DPPBT:PC₇₁BM blend[88,89]. Here, DCB with a low evaporation rate acts as a suitable solvent for PC₇₁BM and a poor solvent for DPPBT, while CF with a higher vapor pressure (BP: 61.2 °C; VP: 200 mmHg) is a good solvent for both donor and acceptor. They found that a low concentration of DCB leads to phase separation before crystallization, while phase separation and crystallization occur simultaneously for a high concentration. As depicted in Fig. 6a the evolution of morphology occurs in 3 stages. The mixed solvent first dissolves both DPPBT polymer and PC₇₁BM. Further, the rapid evaporation of CF leads to aggregating the polymer chains and ordering locally. By continuous evaporation of the solvent, the aggregations of polymer chains form a fibrillar structure. As a consequence, a PCE of 5.2% for the slot-die-fabricated OSC based on the DPPBT:PC₇₁BM blend dissolved in the mixed solvent with 5 vol% of DBC was attained. Moreover, 1,8-diiodooctane (DIO; BP: 332.5 °C; VP: 0 mmHg) as the most common additive has good solubility in small molecules and partial solubility in conjugated polymers due to its structural characteristics. Since incorporating DIO to the precursor solution increases the time of film formation, adding a small amount of it is adequate along with annealing at high temperatures to prevent oversized crystals formation and phase separation. Similarly, Xu et al. [90] fabricated OSCs based on MP6 conjugated polymer. In another research, Lin et al. fabricated OSCs based on ITIC [91] non-fullerene molecules using slot-die coating method, in which DIO was used as an additive solvent. As shown in Fig. 6b, DIO strengthens the interaction of PM6 side chains and weakens the backbone planarization to optimize the fibril network structure by enhancing its morphology and surface crystallization which leads to forming fragmented crystallites connected by tie chains. ITIC molecules were distributed within this interpenetrated network, where DIO aids to increase charge carriers mobility and extraction probability, and to decrease the nongeminate recombination by manipulating the distribution orientation and reducing the size of the crystallites. This in turn led to an increase in FF and J_{sc} , enhancing the PCE from 8.77% (0% DIO) of 9.59% (3% DIO).

However, the toxic nature of halogenated solvents and the poor reproducibility of large-area device performance based on them have recently prompted researchers to focus on suitable alternatives.

Although hydrophilic solvents have traditionally been known to be harmful to organic devices, several studies have reported promising results using them as solvents or additive solvents to investigate the differences between hydrophilic and organic solvents[92–101]. Han et al.[102] used water as an additive solvent to control the morphology of active layer owing to its suitable vapor pressure and boiling temperature[103] for three different configurations of OSCs, including PTB7-Th:PC₆₁BM, PTB7-Th:EH-IDTBR, and PM6:Y6 (Fig. 6c). The results showed an improvement in the efficiency and stability of the devices regardless of the donor and acceptor materials. By achieving an excellent morphology of the blended film by controlling the content of deionized water (DIW) in the precursor solution, they found that the incorporation of 5–20 μL of water into the precursor solution brings the best performance for the device by suppressing excessive aggregation of the donor and acceptor phases. As shown in the AFM phase images (Fig. 6c), a finer phase separation and a smoother film surface were obtained thanks to the formation of smaller aggregates owing to the water treatment. Accordingly, the water-treated slot-die-coated OSCs based on PTB7-Th:PC₆₁BM, PTB7-Th:EH-IDTBR, and PM6:Y6 active layer achieved PCEs of 5.51%, 8.54%, and 13.06% for the active area of 0.1 cm², respectively. Moreover, these OSCs maintained 96.1%, 46.8%, and 86.2% of their initial PCEs after 450 h in 60% RH at 25 °C, respectively. In addition, the water-treated slot-die-coated OSCs based on PTB7-Th:PC₆₁BM, PTB7-Th:EH-IDTBR, and PM6:Y6 active layer attained PCEs of 4.95%, 6.15%, and 11.9% for the large-area of 10 cm², respectively.

Similar to hydrophilic solvents, hydrocarbon solvents are considered to be better options for the large-scale production of OSCs due to their compatibility with the environment and easy availability from petroleum[87]. The poor solubility of photoactive materials in hydrocarbon solvents and the complex and difficult control of the morphology are among the main reasons for limiting the efficiency of slot-die-coated OSCs processed in hydrocarbon solvents [104–106], which requires new fundamental studies to improve their performance. Accordingly, Zhao et al. [79] used the hot slot-die coating technique to deposit the PM6:Y6 blend dissolved in halogenate solvent of CB and hydrocarbon solvents of orthoxylene (o-XY) and 1,2,4-trimethylbenzene (TMB). In these solvents, the temperature-dependent polymer PM6 exhibited strong aggregation, making large-scale production difficult. They employed a hot solution and hot substrate to overcome this problem, where GIWAXS and transmission electron microscopy (TEM) measurements were used to gain information about the morphology, crystallinity and molecular packing of PM6:Y6 films. As shown in Fig. 7a, films prepared by hot solution on hot substrates at optimal conditions show sharper π - π stacking (010) in out-of-plane directions and lamellar (100) peaks, in in-plane directions, demonstrating face-on preferential orientation and high degree of crystallinity compared to films prepared at RT/RT conditions (precursor solution/substrate temperature), which improves charge extraction. Probing the morphology showed that increasing the temperature of substrate and precursor solution leads to smaller phase separation with larger donor/acceptor interfacial areas, which has a decisive role in photocurrent generation and improves exciton dissociation (Fig. 7b). Accordingly, employing hot precursor solution and hot substrate, the PCEs of 15.2%, 15.6% and 15.4% were achieved for the CB-, o-XY-, and TMB-based OSCs, respectively.

In the context of upscaling, it is paramount to consider that solvents have industrial limitations due to environmental and human health reasons. For large-scale commercialization, it is desirable to replace halogenated solvents with less toxic and more sustainable alternatives. In active layer coating, “green solvent” refers to nonhalogenated solvents. These green solvents tend to reduce the solubility of commonly reported OPV materials. In many cases, this requires structural analogs with tailored solubilizing side chains and solvent additives. In this goal, Shen et al. utilized slot-die coating to deposit the active layer of an all-polymer system using PTQ10 as the donor and PYF-T-o as the acceptor by an o-xylene solvent onto flexible substrates. Due to its scalability and

(caption on next page)

Fig. 6. (a) Diagram illustration of active layer formation (red dots: small molecule and green line: polymer). In the initial stage (I), the bulk heterojunction (BHJ) solution is uniformly dissolved. As chloroform is rapidly removed, polymer content begins to aggregate, forming swelled crystals or other forms of aggregations (II). These aggregations align and connect to form fibrils as more solvent is removed, often accompanied by rapid crystallization (III)[87]. (b) Schematic presentation of the morphology-forming process of PM6: ITIC blend films processing with 0 % or 0.3 % diiodooctane (DIO) (left) and the AFM height (top row) and phase images (bottom row) of slot-die-coated PM6: ITIC blend films provided with 0 % or 0.3 % DIO (right), J - V curves of champion OSCs prepared by 0 % or 0.3 % DIO[90]. (c) AFM images of PTB7-Th:PC₆₁BM (F), PTB7-Th:EH-IDTBR (NF), and PM6:Y6 (H-NF) blend films with and without water treatment (DIW) (top row) J - V curves of champion OSCs prepared by PTB7-Th:PC₆₁BM (F), PTB7-Th:EH-IDTBR (NF), and PM6:Y6 (H-NF) blend films with and without DIW (bottom row) [102]. (a) Printed with permission from Ref [87]. (b) Printed with permission from Ref [90]. (c) Printed with permission from Ref [102].

Fig. 7. (a) 2D GIWAXS data, (b) TEM images (left) and J - V curves of the best OSCs (right) based on PM6:Y6 prepared at different solvents and various processing conditions: CB RT/RT, o-XY RT/RT, TMB RT/RT, CB 80/80 °C, o-XY 100/100 °C, TMB 110/110 °C [79].

(a-b) Printed with permission from Ref [79].

ability to produce uniform films over large areas, this method is particularly suitable for commercial applications. In the case of a flexible device of 1 cm², the power conversion efficiency (PCE) was 11.24 %. After undergoing a 1000-cycle bending test, the all-polymer flexible devices retained over 95 % of their initial efficiency [107].

The active layer of OSCs was coated with o-xylene, an environmentally friendly solvent, by Castro et. al. The active layer was composed of a combination of PM6 (a polymer donor) and Y6 (a non-fullerene acceptor). To improve film quality and performance, this approach not only replaced toxic halogenated solvents but also optimized drying

temperatures and solution concentrations. To achieve scalability and industrial application, a slot-die coating process was conducted under ambient conditions. The resulting devices achieved power conversion efficiencies (PCEs) of 6.3 % for binary PM6:Y6 devices and up to 7.2 %

for ternary devices that included fullerene acceptors. Notably, ternary blends based on other combinations, such as PTB7-Th:COi8DFIC:PC71BM, were reported to have efficiencies surpassing 12 % [108].

In 2024, Mazzolini et al. concentrated on the blend of PM6 (a

Fig. 8. (a) AFM (top row) and TEM images (middle row) of PM6:Qx-1 films at different coating temperature. Chemical structure of Qx-1 (right). *J-V* curves of PM6:Qx-1-based OSCs prepared by slot-die-coating method at different coating temperatures (bottom row), *J-V* curves of the large-area OSCs and OSMs, and long-term stability of flexible OSCs with the active area of 1 cm² in a nitrogen glove box [121]. (b) Digital photographs of PM6:L8-BO:PJ1 active layers fabricated without and with airflow. Schematic illustration of film formation mechanism in slot-die coating process from the top view and side view (top row). Structure of flexible OSCs with PM6:L8-BO:PJ1 active layer. *J-V* curves of 1 cm² flexible OSCs at different temperature under airflow and *J-V* curves of 1 cm² flexible OSCs and 30 cm² OSMs (bottom row) [112].

(a) Printed with permission from Ref [121]. (b) Printed with permission from Ref [112].

polymer donor) and Y12 (a non-fullerene acceptor). This combination is a popular option for OSCs because of its great stability and efficiency. Additionally, they employ *o*-xylene, in the active layer's slot-die coating procedure. The power conversion efficiency (PCE) of the *o*-xylene-fabricated devices was 14 %. According to the study, the processing solvent significantly impacts charge carrier dynamics. *o*-xylene-processed devices showed a 40 % reduction in bimolecular recombination coefficients compared to chlorobenzene (CB). Furthermore, effective mobility increased by 70 %, indicating improved charge transport properties[109].

These studies use slot-die coating technology in combination with non-halogenated green solvents to demonstrate how high-performance organic solar cells can be produced effectively. The achieved efficiencies and improved charge carrier dynamics highlight the potential for these methods to be adopted in commercial applications, promoting more sustainable practices in solar energy technologies.

Physical engineering: temperature controlling

In addition to chemical engineering such as solvent engineering and additive solvent engineering, physical engineering such as thermal annealing and air/N₂ flow have great effects on the active layer morphology and device performance. With this regard, adjusting the temperature of the ink and the substrate is considered one of the important strategies to control the solvent evaporation, suppress the coffee ring effect, affect the active layer morphology, and reach a high performance for OSCs, organic solar modules (OSM) and R2R flexible devices [110–114]. The active layer with molecular alignment can be deposited by slot-die coating method thanks to producing shear stress and creating sufficient crystallization[115]. Therefore, the manufacturing process can be simplified by eliminating additional post-treatment such as additive solvent and/or thermal annealing. However, the precise adjustment of the temperature of the precursor solution in conventional deposition techniques such as spin coating faces many challenges, while in the slot-die coating method, it is possible to easily adjust the temperature of the solution by adjusting the temperature of the slot head from where the active solution is pumped onto the moving substrate. Further, adjusting the temperature of the substrate provides the possibility of controlling the thermodynamic state of the solution, and controlling molecular kinetics during film formation, which is essential to optimize the morphology.

Zhao et al.[79] fabricated slot-die-coated PM6:Y6 OSCs and studied the effect of precursor solution/substrate temperature on the morphology of active layer followed by the device performances. The donor polymer of PM6 can be dissolved and disaggregated at high temperatures of 80 – 110 °C, providing the possibility of controlling the morphology and achieving high crystallization with small phase separation[116–120] (Fig. 7). With this regard, by improving the solubility of PM6 in hydrocarbon solvents of CB, *o*-XY, and TMB at 80 °C/80 °C for precursor solution/substrate temperature, PCEs of 15.9 %, 15.2 %, and 15.2 % for an active area of 0.09 cm² were attained, respectively, which are higher than those of fabricated at RT/RT (7.7 %, 5.3 %, and 6.3 %, respectively). Additionally, a PCE of 13.9 % was achieved for the large-area PM6:Y6 based-OSCs with the active area of 0.56 cm².

Later, Shen et al. [121] employed Qx-1 as an acceptor in a flexible PM6:Qx-1 based-OSCs. They investigated the effect of coating temperature on the domain size of blend film and showed that Qx-1 kept a notable aggregation and crystallization scale. To explore the surface and bulk morphologies of blend films, AFM and TEM characterizations were performed at different temperature and as shown in Fig. 8a, by increasing the temperature from RT to 100 °C, the root-mean-square (RMS) were enhanced from 1.61 to 2.80 nm, increasing the crystallinity. The dark and light regions in TEM images demonstrate the quality of donor and acceptor blend in which at the temperature of 80 °C an enlarged fiber width with a reasonable nanoscale network has been exhibited. Therefore, the charge carrier transport is improved and bimolecular recombination in the active layer is inhibited. As a

consequent, by increasing the coating temperature from RT to 80 °C, the PCE of OSCs was augmented from 11.34 % to 13.70 % for active area of 1 cm² and for the large-area OSM fabricated with the area of 30 cm², a high PCE of 12.2 was achieved. Moreover the encapsulated large-area flexible OSCs with an active area of 1 cm² remained 103 % of its initial PCE after 6000 h in N₂ glove box. In another study, Tian et al. [112]., studied the synergistic effect of hot substrate and airflow on the PM6:L8-BO:PJ1 film morphology. With this regards, by increasing the film-forming kinetics and inhibiting the coffee rings, phase separation, exciton dissociation, and charge transport improved. As shown in Fig. 8b, by enhancing the substrate temperature from 40 to 85 °C along with the airflow, the PCEs of flexible OSCs improved from 12.02 % to 13.69 % for the active area of 1 cm². Moreover, the PCE of 13.08 % was achieved for the flexible OSM with the active area of 30 cm² with keeping 103 % of its initial PCE after 250 days in the N₂-filled glovebox.

Other enhancing performance method: ternary and sequential processing of OSCs as a configuration engineering

To control the morphology, achieve the appropriate domain size, and improve the charge separation and charge transfer, a third component can be added to the precursor solution and become a ternary solution with three part and/or on can deposit a second donor, a second acceptor or a combination thereof on the as-coated active layer and/or (Fig. 9a) method[122–125]. Unlike the additive solvent, this new (third) component remains in the structure of the final active layer and manipulates its morphology.

As an example of ternary solution, Zhao et al.[126] used a mixed solution of PM6:BTR-Cl:Y6 and PM6:BTR-Cl:CH1007 to fabricate active layers with two different thicknesses of 100 and 300 nm and then made rigid and flexible OSCs in air, and compared the aggregation behavior of the acceptor molecules in the presence of BTR-Cl, where the toxic solvent of CF replaced with environmentally friendly non-halogenated *o*-XY solvent (Fig. 9b). The device based on PM6:Y6 did not exhibit enhanced efficiency tolerance by introducing BTR-Cl and OSCs based on PM6:Y6 with and without BTR-Cl exhibited a PCE of 15.4 % while introducing BTR-Cl to the devices based on PM6:CH1007 showed an improved PCE from 15.9 % to 16.3 % for active area of 0.04 cm². On the other hand, by increasing the thickness of OSCs with 0.04 cm² area from 100 to 300 nm, the PCEs of OSCs based on PM6:BTR-Cl:Y6 and PM6:BTR-Cl:CH1007 decreased from 15.6 % to 13.8 % and 16.3–15.4 %, respectively. Moreover, by examining the morphology evolution, they found that the more ordered molecular arrangement with balanced and high CH1007 crystallinity in the presence of BTR-Cl resulted in increased and more balanced charge mobility and reduced charge carrier recombination thanks to earlier aggregation in a longer time compared to Y6. Moreover, the large-area OSCs with an active area of 1 cm² based on PM6:BTR-Cl:Y6 and PM6:BTR-Cl:CH1007 demonstrated PCEs of 14.1 % and 14.8 %, respectively, for the 100 nm thickness of the active layer. Additionally, the flexible OSCs based on PM6:BTR-Cl:Y6 and PM6:BTR-Cl:CH1007 showed PCEs of 13.7 % and 14.2 %, respectively, for the active area of 0.04 cm² and 100 nm thickness of the active layer. In another study by Zhao et al.[127], the hot slot-die coating method was used to fabricate large-area, flexible and thick devices based on the D18:Y6 blend. Then, the BTR-Cl small molecule was coated on the first active layer as the second donor and the PCEs of 17.2 % and 15.5 % were achieved for 110 and 300 nm thicknesses of active layer, respectively. Investigations showed that the improved performance of the OSCs and its higher photoactive thickness tolerance in the presence of BTR-Cl originate from improved molecular crystallization and the continuity of vertical phase separation at high thicknesses. This leads to an increase in the mobility of charge carriers and suppression in interfacial non-radiative recombination. In addition, the BTR-Cl has better miscibility with D18 which leads to the separation of Y6 from the mixed amorphous phase of D18 and its early aggregation, improving the crystallization of the active layer. As a result, the slot-die coated flexible OSC showed a PCE of 15.0 % for the flexible OSCs with area of 0.04 cm²

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Fig. 9. (a) Schematic representation of pre-aggregation of ternary precursor solution during slot-die (SD) and sequential slot-die (SSD) process [144]. (b) *J-V* curves of large-area OSCs with active area of 1 cm² and flexible OSCs with an active area of 0.04 cm² based on PM6:BTR-Cl:Y6 and PM6:BTR-Cl:CH1007 ternary blends with different thicknesses [126]. (c) Contour maps of UV-vis absorption spectra for optimal PM6:L8-BO and PM6/L8-BO films over time. The peak location and normalized intensity of L8-BO and PM6 in PM6:L8-BO and PM6/L8-BO films over time. A schematic illustration of PM6:L8-BO and PM6/L8-BO film formation during normal slot-die coating (top row) and dual-slot-die coating (bottom row). *J-V* curves of OSCs based on PM6:L8-BO and PM6/L8-BO films [142]. (d) Schematic description of sequential slot-die coating method of active layer of PM6/Y6C12. Digital photographs of the patterned ITO glass (10 cm length) and different slot-die-coated films from PEDOT:PSS as bottom layer to PFN-Br as top layer under ambient condition and Digital photograph of the whole OSCs after deposition of Ag. *J-V* curves of OSCs based on PM6/Y6C12 prepared by sequential slot-die coating method and provided in different solvents [143]. (a) Printed with permission from Ref [144]. (b) Printed with permission from Ref [126]. (c) Printed with permission from Ref [142]. (d) Printed with permission from Ref [143].

and active layer thickness of 110 nm.

The conventional bulk heterojunction morphology was designed based on interpenetrating donor-acceptor networks to facilitate charge separation and transfer. However, despite the advances in morphology control and adjustment through solvent engineering, temperature controlling, and ternary strategy processing, the formation of impurity domains is unavoidable, which leads to increased recombination losses [128]. Recently, graded structures and sequential processing have been proposed based on the hypothesis that a larger domain size with higher phase purity indicates better charge transfer [129], where the intermediate acceptor-donor composite is sandwiched between the enriched donor and acceptor layers. Surprisingly, studies showed that sequentially processed devices with graded morphology exhibit higher performances compared to one-step coated bulk heterojunction devices [130–133]. The sequential layer-by-layer deposition technique to create the graded morphology offers great potential to overcome the challenge of unsatisfactory vertical phase distribution in bulk heterojunction active layers [77,87,134–141]. Accordingly, to induce vertical phase separation, Yang et al. [135] deposited the active layer of PM6 dissolved in CB and Y6 dissolved in CF sequentially using the slot-die coating method, sandwiching between ZnO:PEI and MoO₃. They used a thermal annealing strategy to tune the crystal structure by controlling the kinetics of solvent evaporation. First, the PM6 layer was coated and annealed, and then Y6 was deposited. In this regard, the lack of intermixed phase formation led to a PCE of 9.69 % at the optimal annealing temperature of 50 °C. To form an interpenetrated network of PM6 and Y6 between the enriched upper layer of PM6 and lower layer of Y6, they first deposited the layers sequentially and then annealed them. The use of solvents with two different boiling points facilitated the achievement of an ideal vertical phase distribution, where the CB solvent with a high boiling point (132.2 °C) remains inside the wet PM6 film during the coating process of the Y6 layer and provides the condition of sufficient blending of acceptor and donor. By balancing the evaporation of solvents through the optimization of the annealing temperature, a PCE of 14.42 % was attained.

However, sequential processing faces challenges related to non-halogenated solvent solubility and discontinuity. To overcome these challenges, Xue et al. [142] developed a dual-slot-die sequential (DSDS) coating technique where the green solvent o-Xy was used to dissolve the PM6:L8-BO compound in the air environment and the device exhibited high PCE of 17.07 % (Fig. 9c). By using UV-visible absorption and photoluminescence measurements, they demonstrated that in the presented coating technique, the donor and acceptor components have mutual diffusion (the donor moves up and the acceptor moves down) and the aggregation process occurs gradually. Time evolution of UV-visible absorption contour maps of PM6:L8-BO and PM6/L8-BO coated films using a single-step slot-die (BHJ) and DSDS techniques, respectively, have shown in Fig. 9c. The process of film formation is divided into three stages by the L8-BO acceptor absorption peak evolution, where first, the position of acceptor absorption peaks in both BHJ and DSDS films remained unchanged by solvent evaporation. However, the intensity of the absorption peaks of the acceptor and donor gradually increased and decreased, respectively, in BHJ films, which is caused by the increase in the concentration of L8-BO and the change in the aggregation state of PM6, while in the DSDS films, the intensity of

absorption peaks of both PM6 and L8-BO decreased sharply at the beginning of the process. The decrease in performance can be attributed to the immediate deposition of the acceptor layer followed by the formation of the donor layer, which initiated a mutual diffusion process between the donor and acceptor, thereby reducing their absolute concentrations. During the deposition of the acceptor layer, some donor molecules aggregated while the rest remained in the solution, facilitating mutual diffusion. In the subsequent

stage, as the solvent continued to evaporate, the solution reached a supersaturated state, initiating the gradual aggregation of L8-BO molecules, as indicated by the gradual redshift behavior of the absorption peak. The diffusion phenomenon and aggregation of the L8-BO small molecule continue until the completion of the PM6 aggregation process. Removal of all solvents in the final stage resulted in the stabilization of all peak signals. In the DSDS method, thanks to the quicker aggregation of PM6 during the interdiffusion process, small acceptor molecules diffuse relatively independently into the microcrystalline structure of the first-coated donor layer and induce stronger crystallinity compared to the conventional bulk heterojunction structure. Generally, in the case of normal slot-die coating, the donor and acceptor aggregate directly due to the uniform

distribution of the donor-acceptor and the volatilization of the solution. However, in DSDS processing, the donor and acceptor undergo a mutual diffusion process before gradually aggregating. As a consequence, OSCs based on PM6:L8-BO and PM6/L8-BO showed PCEs of

16.32 % and 16.95 % for the active area of 0.04 cm², respectively.

For all slot-die-coated OSCs, Li et al., utilized sequential slot-die coating method to deposit HTL (PEDOT:PSS), active layer (PM6/Y6C12), and ETL (PFN-Br) (Fig. 9d) [143]. For fabrication of active layer, two different kinds of non-halogenated solvents were employed: PM6 (o-

Xy)/Y6C12 (o-Xy) and semi-immiscible solvents of PM6 (o-Xy)/Y6C12 (2-MeTHF; 2-methyltetrahydrofuran) and synergistically studied the effect of different processing solvents on the device performances. With this regard, the OSCs based on PM6 (o-Xy)/Y6C12 (o-Xy) and PM6 (o-Xy)/Y6C12 (2-MeTHF) films showed PCEs of 10.6 % and 7.2 % for a 0.12 cm² area, respectively. Moreover, PM6 (o-Xy)/Y6C12 (o-Xy) and PM6 (o-Xy)/Y6C12 (2-MeTHF) based devices maintained 40 % and 60 % of their initial PCEs after 840 h in N₂ glovebox.

- **PBDB-T-SF or PBDB-T or PM6:** poly[(2,6-(4,8-bis(5-(2-ethylhexylthio)-4-fluorothiophen-2-yl)-benzo [1,2-b:4,5-b']dithiophene))-alt-(5,5-(1',3' -di-2-thienyl-5',7'-bis(2-ethylhexyl) benzo [1',2'-c:4',5'-c']dithiophene-4,8-dione)]
- **i-IEICO-4F:** 2,2'-((2Z,2'Z)-(((4,4,9,9-tetrakis(4-hexylphenyl)-4,9-dihydro-sindaceno[1,2-b:5,6-b']-dithiophene-2,7-diy))bis(4-((2-ethylhexyl)oxy)thiophene-4,3-diy))bis(methanylylidene))bis-(5,6-difluoro-3-oxo-2,3-dihydro-1H-indene-2,1-diy)idene)-dimalononitrile
- **PPDT2FBT:** poly[(2,5-bis(2-hexyldecyloxy)phenylene)-alt-(5,6-difluoro-4,7-di(thiophen-2-yl)benzo[c][1,2,5]thiadiazole)]
- **IT-4F:** 3,9-bis (2-methylene-((3-(1,1-dicyanomethylene)-6,7-difluoro)-indanone))-5,5,11,11-tetrakis (4-hexylphenyl)-dithieno[2,3-d:2',3'-d']-s-indaceno[1,2-b:5,6-b']dithiophene

- **PFN-Br**: Poly[(9,9-bis(3'-(N,N-dimethyl)-N-ethylammonium)-propyl)-2,7-fluorene)-alt-2,7-(9,9-dioctylfluorene)]
- **PFN**: poly[(9,9-bis(3'-(N,N-dimethylamino)propyl)-2,7-fluorene)-alt-2,7-(9,9-dioctylfluorene)]
- **BTP-4F** or **Y6**: 2,2'-((2Z,2'Z)-((12,13-bis(2-ethylhexyl)-3,9-diundecyl-1,12,13-dihydro-[1,2,5]thiadiazolo[3,4-e]thieno[2'',3''':4',5']thieno[2',3':4,5]pyrrolo[3,2-g]thieno[2',3':4,5]thieno[3,2-b]indole-2,10-diyl)bis(methanylylidene))bis(5,6-difluoro-3-oxo-2,3-dihydro-1H-indene-2,1-diylidene))dimalononitrile
- **PTB7**: poly[[4,8-bis(2-ethylhexyl)oxy] benzo[1,2-b:4,5-b'] dithiophene-2,6-diyl] [3-fluoro-2-[(2-ethylhexyl)carbonyl]thieno[3,4-b]thiophenediyl]]
- **PTB7-Th**: Poly[4,8-bis(5-(2-ethylhexyl) thiophen-2-yl)benzo[1,2-b:4,5-b']dithiophene-co-3-fluorothieno [3,4-b]thiophene-2-carboxylate]
- **p-DTS(FBTTH2)2**: 7,7-(4,4-bis(2-ethylhexyl)-4H-silolo[3,2-b:4,5-b']dithiophene-2,6-diyl)bis(6-fluoro-4-(5'-hexyl-[2,2'-bithiophen]-5-yl)benzo[c][1,2,5]thiadiazole)
- **IEICO-4F**: 2,2'-[[4,4,9,9-tetrakis(4-hexylphenyl)-4,9-dihydro-indaceno[1,2-b:5,6-b']dithiophene-2,7-diyl]bis[[4-[(2-ethylhexyl)oxy]-5,2-thiophenediyl]methylydyne(5,6-difluoro-3-oxo-1H-indene-2,1(3 H)-diylidene)]]bis[propanedinitrile]
- **ITIC-Th**: 3,9-bis(2-methylene-(3-(1,1-dicyanomethylene)-indanone))-5,5,11,11-tetrakis(4-hexylphenyl)-dithieno[2,3-d:2',3'-d']-s-indaceno[1,2-b:5,6-b']-dithiophene
- **ITIC**: 2,2'-[[6,6,12,12-Tetrakis(4-hexylphenyl)-6,12-dihydrodithieno[2,3-d:2',3'-d']-s-indaceno[1,2-b:5,6-b']dithiophene-2,8-diyl]bis[methylydyne(3-oxo-1H-indene-2,1(3 H)-diylidene)]]bispropanedinitrile
- **PBDB-T**: poly[(2,6-(4,8-bis(5-(2-ethylhexyl)thiophen-2-yl)-benzo[1,2-b:4,5-b']dithiophene))-alt-(5,5-(1',3'-di-2-thienyl-5',7'-bis(2-ethylhexyl)benzo[1',2'-c:4',5'-c']dithiophene-4,8-dione))]
- **PTzBI-Si**: poly{(4,8-bis(5-(2-ethylhexyl)thiophen-2-yl)benzo[1,2-b:4,5-b']dithiophene-co-4,8-di(thien-2-yl)-2-(6-(1,1,1,3,5,5,5 heptamethyltrisiloxan-3-yl)hexyl)-6-octyl[1–3]triazolo[4,5-f]isoindole-5,7(2H,6H)-dione)}
- **L8-BO**: 2,2'-((2Z,2'Z)-((3,9-bis(2-butylloctyl)-12,13-bis(2-ethylhexyl)-1,12,13-dihydro[1,2,5]thiadiazolo[3,4-e]thieno[2'',3''':4',5']thieno[2',3':4,5]pyrrolo[3,2-g]thieno[2',3':4,5]thieno[3,2-b]indole-2,10 diyl)bis(methanylylidene))bis(5,6-difluoro-3-oxo-2,3-dihydro-1H-indene-2,1-diylidene))dimalononitrile
- **D18**: poly[(2,6-(4,8-bis(5-(2-ethylhexyl-3-fluoro)thiophen-2-yl)-benzo[1,2-b:4,5-b']dithiophene))-alt-(2-butylloctyl) thiophen-2-yl)-8-(4-(2-butylloctyl)-5-methylthiophen-2-yl)dithieno[3,2':3,4;2'',3'':5,6]benzo[1,2-c][1,2,5]thiadiazole)]
- **BTR**: terthiophene rhodamine
- **BTR-Cl**: (2,6-(4,8-bis(5-(2-ethylhexyl-4-chloro-2-thienyl)-benzodithiophene terthiophene rhodamine
- **N2200**: poly{[N,N-9-bis(2-octyldodecyl)-naphthalene-1,4,5,8-bis-(dicarboximide)-2,6-diyl]-alt-5,50-(2,20-bithiophene)}
- **tPDI2N-EH**: N-annulated perylene diimide dimer
- **QX-3**: benzodithiophene-quinoxaline (BDT-QX)
- **IDTBR**: rhodanine-benzothiadiazole-coupled indacenodithiophene
- **PPBPT**: copolymer of diketopyrrolopyrrole and quaterthiophene
- **PEIE**: polyethylenimine etheroxylated
- **PDTSTTz**: copolymer based on DTS and TTz
- **DTS**: dithieno[3,2-b:2',3'-d]silole
- **TTz**: dithienylthiazolo[5,4-d]thiazole
- **AZO**: aluminum-doped zinc oxide
- **PET**: polyethylene terephthalate
- **P3HT**: poly(3-hexylthiophene)
- **PC61BM**: [6,6]-phenyl C61-butyric acid methyl ester
- **PC71BM**: [6,6]-phenyl C71-butyric acid methyl ester
- **DIO**: 1,8-diiodooctane
- **DPE**: diphenyl ether
- **CF**: chloroform
- **DCB**: 1,2-dichlorobenzene
- **o-DCB**: o-dichlorobenzene
- **CN**: 1-chloronaphthalene
- **NMP**: N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone
- **TO**: toluene
- **o-XY**: o-xylene
- **DBE**: dibenzyl ether
- **MTHF**: 2-methyltetrahydrofuran
- **BARB**: 1,3-dimethyl-barbituric acid
- **THN**: tetrahydronaphthalene
- **oMA**: o-methylanisole
- **BrA**: p-bromoanisole
- **2-MeTHF**: 2-methyltetrahydrofuran
- **DIW**: deionized water
- **THF**: tetrahydrofuran

Charge transport layers

Besides the active layer, the interfacial layers between the electrodes and the active layer play a crucial role in large-area device fabrication and commercialization [196]. These layers must possess solution processing capabilities compatible with R2R coating/printing methods [146,184]. Extracting the photogenerated charge carriers within the active layer, transferring and collecting them by electrodes is one of the critical challenges in achieving high-efficiency devices. To overcome this challenge, inserting an interlayer between the electrode and the active layer, which results in creating a better ohmic contact (reducing the energy barrier height) and reducing the leakage currents (blocking the opposite charge) is considered an effective approach [197,198] (Fig. 10a). Improper interfacial energy levels alignment leads to contact resistance and increases the undesirable charge recombination rate. To reduce the voltage loss due to recombination, for the hole transport layer (HTL), its valence band or highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) must be equal to and/or slightly higher than the HOMO of the donor. In contrast, for the electron transport layer (ETL), its conduction band or lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) must be equal to and/or slightly lower than the LUMO of the acceptor [199,200] (Fig. 10b). Since the interlayer thickness is often around 20 – 50 nm, a charge transport layer should have a high thickness tolerance in addition to the appropriate energy level and high conductivity.

Hole transport layer

In general, the role of the transparent electrode as an electron or hole collector divides the structure of OSCs into two categories, inverted or conventional [197,201]. In the conventional and inverted structures, PEDOT:PSS is mainly employed as the HTL on the transparent electrode and the active layer, respectively, thanks to being solution processable, its high transparency, high conductivity, and suitable energy level (work function of ~5.1 eV) aligned with the quasi-Fermi level of the donor materials [202,203]. However, the poor wettability of PEDOT:PSS has made its coating on hydrophobic substrates a challenge, where the formation of an inhomogeneous layer leads to the current loss in the solar cell [204]. As an effective strategy, adding additives or surfactants such as Suynole 104 series [205], Triton X-100 [206,207], isopropyl alcohol [208], Capstone Dupont-FS-31 (CFS-31) [209], and fluorosurfactants [210,211] to the solution can improve the wettability of PEDOT:PSS on hydrophobic surfaces. Unlike the conventional spin coating, leading to rapid evaporation of the solvent and instant film formation due to centrifugal force, slot-die coating does not have any external force for film formation except surface tension, which can provide the formation of a uniform film on hydrophobic surfaces owing to improving the wettability of PEDOT:PSS. With this regard, Yi et al. [179] added non-ionic fluorosurfactants Zonyl FS-300 and FS-31 to different types of commercial PEDOT:PSSs, including Clevis P, N 1005, S 305, and AI 4083 to improve their wetting properties and their

Fig. 10. (a) Working principle of OSCs [217]: (1) exciton generation; (2) exciton diffusion; (3) exciton dissociation; (4) charge transportation; (5) charge extraction; and (6) charge recombination. (b) Energy level diagram of organic solar cells. (c) Chemical structures of Zonyl FS-300 and FS-31 (Capstone® Dupont™). Contact angles and $J-V$ curves of various types of PEDOT:PSS solution with each surfactant on a P3HT:ICBA layer [179]. (d) Schematic presentation of slot-die-coated SnO₂, PDIN-H, BHJ, PEDOT:PSS. $J-V$ curves for toluene:2-MeTHF based-OSCs with solution-processed PEDOT:PSS as an HTL (Glass/ITO/SnO₂/PDIN-H/BHJ/PEDOT:PSS/Ag), and a schematic illustration of the device architecture in the inset. AFM images of pristine and ethanol-treated PTQ10:Y6-C12 BHJ films. Contact-angle measurements for the PEDOT:PSS drops on pristine and ethanol-treated PTQ10:Y6-C12 BHJ films [170]. (e) $J-V$ curves and long-term stability tests of PTB7-Th:IEICO-4F based-OSCs under 85 °C thermal stress for 600 h [184].

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uniform coating on the hydrophobic surface of the P3HT:ICBA active layer using the slot-die method. The results showed that the addition of both surfactants were provided a uniform coating of PEDOT:PSS by reducing the surface tension between the active layer and PEDOT:PSS and the contact angle below 25 °C (Fig. 10c, Table 2). Although using this strategy leads to the formation of a uniform and smooth layer on the surface of the hydrophobic active layer and transparent electrode, it is challenging to remove the used surfactants that limit the device performance. To increase the adhesion between the slot-die-coated PEDOT:PSS and the active layer in the inverted structure, Castro et al.[194] treated the surface of the active layer with butanol and then deposited the sonicated and filtered PEDOT:PSS, whereas Niazi et al.[170] used ethanol to treat the surface of active layer (PTQ-10:Y6-C12). Then, a uniform PEDOT:PSS layer was deposited on the active layer with reduced surface roughness and without changing the morphology and absorption of the active layer, achieving a PCE of 9.55 % for the all slot-die-coated device in comparison with the device without surface treatment (5.5 %) (Fig. 10d). In the conventional configuration, Wang et al. [185] coated PEDOT:PSS solution diluted in isopropyl alcohol on a flexible PET/silver-grid substrate using the R2R slot-die coating technique. As a result, the OSCs and OSMs with the area of 1 and 25 cm² showed PCEs of 12.16 % and 10.09 %, respectively. Moreover, the flexible OSCs kept 99 % and 103 % of its initial PCE after 1000 bending cycles at a radius of 10 mm and after over 6000 h in N₂ glovebox.

However, the acidic and hygroscopic nature of PEDOT:PSS leads to the degradation of device performance in the long-term stability tests [184,212]. Therefore, promising alternatives based on transition metal oxides such as MoO₃, V₂O₅, NiO_x, and WO₃ have emerged with stable solution-processable capabilities that prevent the degradation of OSCs as buffer layers [147,213–216]. Accordingly, Beliatz et al.[147] used slot-die-coated V₂O₅ as a substitute for PEDOT:PSS in flexible OSCs based on P3HT:PC₆₀BM and PBDDTTz-4:PC₆₀BM. The V₂O₅-based OSCs exhibited a very low performance compared to those fabricated by PEDOT:PSS which is due to the flexible nature of the samples that endure mechanical stresses (bending) during the fabrication process. In fact, this leads to creating cracks on the coated-V₂O₅ and degrades the device performance by allowing silver ink solvents to penetrate into the active layer. After adding PEDOT:PSS between V₂O₅ and silver electrode, the conductivity at the interface, improving the device's electrical characteristics. Also, the flexible nature of PEDOT:PSS significantly increased the mechanical robustness of the V₂O₅ layer, where the PEDOT:PSS layer no longer faced the problem of wettability. Instead of the dual-layer configuration for HTL, Chaturvedi et al. [184] used a distribution of MoO₃ nanoparticles inside the PEDOT:PSS solution diluted with isopropyl alcohol to reduce the liquid surface tension. Taking advantage of the inorganic properties of MoO₃, not only provided a uniform layer of PEDOT:PSS on the PTB7-Th:IEICO-4F active layer but also made the device resistant to degradation by suppressing the hydrophilic and hygroscopic nature of PEDOT:PSS (Fig. 10e). They achieved a high PCE of 11 % for a 1 cm² large-area device fabricated using the slot-die coating method. In general, it can be expected that these hybrid materials with beneficial properties of both organic and inorganic materials, can be a good replacement of commonly-used PEDOT:PSS.

Electron transport layer

In OSCs and OSMs, electron transport layers (ETLs) can be also deposited by solution-processed methods like slot-die coating. In conventional structures, since the ETL is deposited on the active layer, the deposition method should be solution-processable and does not destroy the active layer. Therefore, using water- and/or alcohol-soluble electron transport materials that are immiscible with the organic active layer and provide the possibility of coating on the hydrophobic surfaces can be an efficient strategy. In recent years, although many ETLs with the said properties have been employed based on inorganic alkali salts, organic molecules, amino-containing polymers, and perylene diimide-based

compounds, their low charge carrier mobility has led to poor thickness tolerance and limited thicker coating [218–223]. Interestingly, the emergence of interlayers based on n-type metal oxides with high electron mobility and deep valence bands, such as ZnO, TiO₂ and SnO₂, not only facilitates electron transporting and block hole transferring properties but also enables thicker coating layer [224–227]. ZnO is extensively employed as an ETL in OSCs because of its optical transparency in the visible region, its suitable work function of ~4.3 eV, and its amenability to process via sol-gel and nanoparticle solutions [228]. In this regard, Wang et al. [185] applied sol-gel ZnO in isopropyl alcohol solvent on a PET/silver-grid substrate using the R2R slot-die method in flexible inverted OSCs. Here, the ZnO-coated substrates were first heated to 80 °C, and then the ternary active layer PTB7-Th:COI8DFIC:PCBM was also slot-die-coated. Investigations showed that to achieve a high PCE based on sol-gel-processed ZnO layer, it should be annealed at a temperature above 200 °C but using a high temperature prevents its use in the conventional structures (on the active layer) and on flexible substrates. For example, PET that is a common transparent conducting electrode in devices can tolerate a temperature range of up to 140 – 150 °C. Therefore, a coating method was developed based on ZnO nanoparticles solution. Consequently, slot-die-coated OSCs with 1 cm² active area displayed a PCE of 12.16 % which is comparable to those fabricated by spin coating method on rigid substrates with the small-area of 0.04 cm² (12.37 %).

In another study, Han et al.[186] utilized a commercial solution containing ZnO nanoparticles to deposit the ZnO layer onto a patterned ITO-PET film using the slot-die method. They achieved a PCE of 11.3 % for the small lab-scale device without any post-treatment such as annealing. However, the inherent instability of ZnO when exposed to ultraviolet radiation, leading to interactions with the acceptor component of the active layer, limits its reliability and uses as an efficient ETL in OSCs. Following this, some studies have proposed using an interlayer between ZnO and the active layer to prevent interactions and enhance device stability, this approach is temporary, and degradation of device performance remains unavoidable. Another more reliable strategy is to replace ZnO with less UV-reactive and chemically more stable materials such as SnO₂ [170,180]. Compared to ZnO, films based on SnO₂ nanoparticles with higher conductivity, better optical transmission, wider bandgap, low-temperature solution processing are more compatible with large-scale fabrication, and R2R production. [170,180,229,230] Moreover, with alcohol- or water-based solutions a uniform film can be formed, which leads to better collecting electrons from organic active layers and transferring them to the electrode thanks to its proper conduction energy band level. Jiang et al. [229] used both ZnO and SnO₂ ETLs in an inverted OSCs with ITO/ETL/PM6:IT4F/MoO₃/Ag configuration to investigate their photo stability (Fig. 11a). They discovered that under UV irradiation, the ZnO layer causes the decomposition of the electron acceptor nano-fullerene IT4F by disrupting the C=C linkage that connects the donor and acceptor, resulting in vanishing the absorption bands associated with intramolecular charge transfer. The replacement of ZnO with SnO₂ improved the illumination stability of the device by mitigating the photocatalytic effect owing to a wider bandgap that does not absorb photons of the AM 1.5 irradiation spectrum, and also provided a higher PCE. Moreover, The slot-die-coated SnO₂ layer showed an ignorable dependence on the annealing temperature and the thickness, where the efficiencies of 12.1 % and 13.9 % were realized, respectively, for the device without thermal annealing and annealed at 100 °C. They achieved a PCE of 11.5 % for the large-area device of 1 cm². In addition, the low-temperature processability of SnO₂ also enables its use in conventional structures. In another study, Hoff et al. [180] used a commercial solution of SnO₂ nanoparticles in butanol: ethanol and then the ETL was deposited on PBDBT:PC₆₁BM, PPDT2FBT:PC₆₁BM, and PTQ10:IDIC active layers, obtaining PCEs of 3.7 %, 5.7 %, and 7.1 %, respectively. Later, Ginesi et al.[177] employed a tyrosine appended perylene bisimide (PBI-Y) as an electron transport interlayer to passivate the surface traps of SnO₂ in inverted PM6/Y6C12-based

Fig. 11. (a) Digital photos of IT-4F thin films on glass, glass/ZnO, and glass/SnO₂ substrates under different-time continuous UV illumination (365 nm, 5 mWcm⁻²). The UV-vis absorption spectra of ZnO/IT-4F and SnO₂/IT-4F samples were recorded while being illuminated under AM 1.5 light in a N₂ environment (top row). J-V curves of PM6:IT4F-based OSCs prepared by ZnO and SnO₂ J-V curves of the SnO₂ based-OSCs fabricated at various temperatures and with different thicknesses [229]. (b) Digital photos of Patterned ITO/glass (10 cm strip), slot-die-coated SnO₂, PBI-Y, PM6, and Y6C12 films. Absorption spectra of SnO₂/PBI-Y films deposited by spin coating and slot-die coating methods. J-V curves of SnO₂ and SnO₂/PBI-Y based OSCs made by slot-die coating method. AFM images of SnO₂/PBI-Y films deposited by spin coating and slot-die coating methods [177].

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OSCs (Fig. 11b). The electrical characterization demonstrated that a PBI modification developed the conductivity of the slot-die-coated SnO₂. Additionally, the slot-die-coated SnO₂ showed higher light absorption than that of spin-coated SnO₂ layer which is due more deposited material on the substrate during slot-die coating. Furthermore, the OSCs based on slot-die-coated SnO₂ and SnO₂/PBI-Y demonstrated PCEs of 9.4 % and 10.4 % for 0.14 cm² active areas, respectively.

- **PBDB-T-SF or PM6**: poly[(2,6-(4,8-bis(5-(2-ethylhexylthio)-4-fluorothiophen-2-yl)-benzo [1,2-b:4,5-b']dithiophene))-alt-(5,5-(1',3' -d i-2-thienyl-5',7'-bis(2-ethylhexyl) benzo [1',2'-c:4',5'-c']dithiophene-4,8-dione)]
- **PBDB-T**: poly[(2,6-(4,8-bis(5-(2-ethylhexyl)thiophen-2-yl)-benzo[1, 2-b:4,5-b']dithiophene))-alt-(5,5-(1',3'-di-2-thienyl-5',7'-bis(2-ethylhexyl)benzo[1',2'-c:4',5'-c']dithiophene-4,8-dione))]
- **PPDT2FBT**: poly[(2,5-bis(2-hexyldecyloxy)phenylene)-alt-(5,6-difluoro-4,7-di(thiophen-2-yl)benzo[c][1,2,5]thiadiazole)]
- **BTP-4F or Y6**: 2,2'-((2Z,2'Z)-((12,13-bis(2-ethylhexyl)-3,9-diundecyl-12,13-dihydro-[1,2,5]thiadiazolo[3,4-e]thieno[2'',3'':4',5']thieno [2',3':4,5]pyrrolo[3,2-g]thieno[2',3':4,5]thieno[3,2-b]indole-2,10-diyl)bis(methanylylidene))bis(5,6-difluoro-3-oxo-2,3-dihydro-1H-indene-2,1-diy-lidene))dimalononitrile
- **PTB7**: poly[[4,8-bis(2-ethylhexyl)oxy] benzo[1,2-b:4,5-b'] dithiophene-2,6-diyl] [3-fluoro-2-[(2-ethylhexyl)carbonyl]thieno[3,4-b]thiophenediyl]]
- **PTB7-Th**: Poly[4,8-bis(5-(2-ethylhexyl) thiophen-2-yl)benzo[1,2-b: 4,5-b']dithiophene-co-3-fluorothieno [3,4-b]thiophene-2-carboxyla te]
- **ITIC-Th**: 3,9-bis(2-methylene-(3-(1,1-dicyanomethylene)-indanone)-5,5,11,11-tetrakis(4-hexylphenyl)-dithieno[2,3-d:2',3'-d']-s-indaceno[1,2-b:5,6-b']-dithiophene
- **ITIC**: 2,2'-[[6,6,12,12-Tetrakis(4-hexylphenyl)-6,12-dihydrodithien o[2,3-d:2',3'-d']-s-indaceno[1,2-b:5,6-b']dithiophene-2,8-diyl]bis [methylidyne(3-oxo-1H-indene-2,1(3 H)-diylidene))] bispropanedinitrile
- **L8-BO**: 2,2'-((2Z,2'Z)-((3,9-bis(2-butyloctyl)-12,13-bis(2-ethylhexyl)-12,13-dihydro[1,2,5]thiadiazolo[3,4-e]thieno[2'',3'':4',5']thieno [2',3':4,5]pyrrolo[3,2-g]thieno[2',3':4,5]thieno[3,2-b]indole-2,10 diyl)bis(methanylylidene))bis(5,6-difluoro-3-oxo-2,3-dihydro-1H-indene-2,1-diy-lidene))dimalononitrile
- **PFN**: poly[(9,9-bis(3'-(N,N-dimethylamino)propyl)-2,7-fluorene)-alt-2,7-(9,9-dioctylfluorene)]
- **IDTBR**: rhodanine-benzothiadiazole-coupled indacenodithiophene
- **PEIE**: polyethylenimine ethoxylated
- **PDTSTTz**: copolymer based on DTS and TTz
- **DTS**: dithieno[3,2-b:2',3'-d]silole
- **TTz**: dithienylthiazolo[5,4- d]thiazole
- **AZO**: aluminum-doped zinc oxide
- **PET**: polyethylene terephthalate
- **P3HT**: poly(3-hexylthiophene)
- **PC61BM**: [6,6]-phenyl C61-butyric acid methyl ester
- **PC71BM**: [6,6]-phenyl C71-butyric acid methyl ester
- **PBI-Y**: perylene bisimide appended with l-tyrosine

Encapsulation of slot-die-coated OSCs

In addition to utilizing low-cost materials and ambient R2R coating on flexible substrates, a common approach to commercialize solar cells and reduce the cost of fabrication is replacing the spin-coating methods with other printing methods such as blade coating and slot-die coating [233]. Besides attaining high performances, a significant bottleneck of OSC commercialization is the stability. The degradation mechanisms of OSCs can be categorized as follows: (I) physical degradation mechanisms and (II) chemical degradation mechanisms.[175] Shear and interfacial stresses and the tension are considered as physical

degradation mechanisms. Chemical degradation mechanisms are categorized in three parts: ① extrinsic degradation including chemical reaction with oxygen and water from ambient environment, ② intrinsic degradation including heating or temperature in the dark condition, and ③ intrinsic degradation including light illumination. Generally, to improve the stability three strategies can be performed: (1) materials and electrodes engineering, (2) device architecture engineering, and (3) encapsulation in which the last one, i.e. the encapsulation, plays a critical role in inhibiting degradation or improving the stability of slot-die-coated OSCs and OSMs.[121,149,156,163,164,168,173,175, 176] Firstly, Zawacka et al.[149] studied the effect of different additives on the performance of inverted OSCs. Then, to improve the stability of R2R slot-die-coated devices, the OSCs were encapsulated between two glass slides using a UV curable epoxy resin adhesive and exposed to light of solar simulator (1000 W m⁻², AM1.5) for 1 min, followed by annealing at 130 °C for 3 min. The encapsulated devices were explored according to the ISOS-L2 protocol (continuous illumination, 1000 W m⁻² at 85 °C) for over 20 h. The OSCs with CN additive reached 80 % of its initial PCE (2.05 %) after 20 h. Later, Lucera et al.[156] fabricated all slot-die-coated semi-transparent large-area OSMs (Fig. 12a). With this regard, they deposited ZnO, PBTZT-stat-BDIT-8:PCBM, PEDOT:PSS, and AgNWs as ETL, active layer, HTL, and back electrode on the flexible ITO-Metal-ITO (IMI)/PET substrates by slot-die coating method, respectively. Before any measurements, the modules were encapsulated by PET barrier foils. Therefore, the fabricated devices reached PCEs of 4.1 % and 4.3 % for the active areas of 0.1 and 68.76 cm², respectively. In a similar study, Arredondo et al.[168] fabricated inverted OSCs with the architecture of PET/Ag/ZnO/PBDB-T:ITIC/PEDOT:PSS/CP105D PEDOT:PSS in which ZnO, PBDB-T:ITIC, PEDOT:PSS, CP105D PEDOT:PSS were all slot-die-coated and the entire slot-die coating process was done by R2R in ambient air. As the final step, the devices were cut, glued on a glass substrate and then encapsulated with a round glass cover, followed by curing under UV light (Fig. 12b). The OSCs with 3.24 cm² active area demonstrated a PCE of 3.18 %. Then, the effect of different light spectra on the ideality factors was investigated. They found that the degradation is happening near the anode, where the red wavelength is being strongly absorbed. Similarly, Chang et al.[164] slot-die-coated PEI, PV2000:PCBM, and PEDOT:PSS on glass to make inverted OSMs, followed by encapsulating by cavity glass with UV curable sealant applied around the edge of the cavity glass. The encapsulation was finalized by pressing and then curing the sealant by a 400 W metal halide lamp for 20 s. The module with an active area of 23.7 cm² demonstrated a certified PCE of 7.56 %. As shown in Fig. 12c, the encapsulated modules using slot-die-coated PEDOT:PSS kept 91.7 % of its initial PCE after 1000 h under light-soaking exposure while the encapsulated modules using thermal evaporated MoO₃ lost its PCE immediately after light-soaking. In another study, Lee et al. [175]deposited ZnO and PV2000:PC₇₁BM on ITO/PET by R2R slot-die coating method to fabricate flexible OSMs in an architecture of PET/ITO/ZnO/PV2000:PC₇₁BM/MoO₃/Ag with the area of 90 cm², achieving 2.2 % PCE (Fig. 12d). To encapsulate, the modules were sandwiched between the 3 M™ FTB3–50 films as the plastic barrier films, followed by laminating[234] the pressure sensitive adhesive on the barrier films and then exposed them to vacuum at 100 °C for 8 h to remove the residual moisture and oxygen. As the final step, the UV adhesive was used around the gap between fastener and barrier film for sealing. The modules without and with encapsulation maintained 35 % and 50 % of their initial PCEs after 2000 h under an accelerated test at 65 °C/65 % RH. Also, the modules without and with encapsulation under continuous illumination of AM 1.5 kept 20 % and 60 % of their initial PCEs after 100 h and 650 h, respectively. Later, in 2023, they made semitransparent flexible module with an inverted structure[176] of PET-TCO/ZnO/PV-X/MoO₃/Ag. In the first step, the effect of active layer thickness on the overall module transparency and PCE was investigated. Thus, for the optimum thickness of 150 nm, the overall module transparency and PCE were ~ 17 % and 6.2 % for the active area

Fig. 12. (a) Digital photo of a flexible semi-transparent module with an inverted architecture of PET/IMI/ZnO/PBTZT-stat/BDTT-8:PCBM/PEDOT:PSS/AgNWs with an active area 68.76 cm² and encapsulated with glass slides using a UV curable epoxy resin. *J-V* curves of the semi-transparent modules on PET/IMI and FTO glass with active areas of 68.76 cm² and 197.40 cm², respectively [156]. (b) Encapsulated OSCs. The fabricated device on PET foil. *J-V* curve of a flexible module encapsulated with round glass cover [168]. (c) Digital photo of slot-die coating of PV2000:PCBM/PEDOT:PSS. Light soaking stability tests of Modules prepared by thermal evaporated MoO₃ (black square) and slot-die-coated PEDOT:PSS (red circle), encapsulated by glass with UV curable sealant [164]. (d) Cross-sectional view of a module with 6 serially connected and encapsulated with 3 MTM FTB3-50 film. Long-term stability tests of OSCs without and with encapsulation with MoO₃ as HTL under the continuous illumination of AM1.5. Digital photo of flexible encapsulated OSCs [175]. (e) Digital photos of modules employed on the roof, modules connected serially by metal fasteners as terminal for each panel, and DCDC convert with MPPT function labeled as 1, Lead-acid battery labeled as 2, and current recorder labeled as 3. Energy output per active area of OPV and Si-based modules measured during Oct 2, 2021 to May 2, 2022. Diurnal behavior of PMPP output per active area of OPV and Si-based modules on Oct 6, 2021 (left) and Oct 7, 2021 [176] (right).

(a) Printed with permission from Ref [156]. (b) Printed with permission from Ref [168]. (c) Printed with permission from Ref [164]. (d) Printed with permission from Ref [175]. (e) Printed with permission from Ref. [176].

of 45 cm², respectively. As demonstrated in Fig. 12e, all sheet-to-sheet (S2S) modules were connected serially together via metal fasteners as terminal contact to make panels and used on the curved roof. In addition, the day-time behavior of P_{MPP} output per active area of organic- and Si-based panels with PCEs of 5.47 % and 18.5 %, respectively, on 6th and 7th of Oct 2021 were measured as a function of time (time

interval: 1 min). Due to rapidly increasing the PCE of OSM with decreasing the solar radiation and overnight recovery characteristic, the (P_{MPP})_{OSM}/(P_{MPP})_{Si} in the morning is much higher than that at midday. On the other hand, due to the eastern orientation of organic solar panel the (P_{MPP})_{OSM}/(P_{MPP})_{Si} in the afternoon is much lower than that at midday. The daily energy outputs per active area of organic- and

Si-based panels from Oct 2, 2021 to May 2, 2022 were measured and the data showed that from 1 to 200 days the $(P_{MPP})_{OSM}/(P_{MPP})_{Si}$ decreases and this reduction suggests the beginning of rapid degradation and failure of flexible organic solar panels.

Overall, to increase the stability of OSCs and OSMs, encapsulation is considered a promising approach. For all slot-die-coated devices, the highest PCE of 6.2 % for the active area of 45 cm² have been achieved.

Perovskite solar cells

In perovskite solar cell fabrication, a slot die allows homogeneous wet layers of perovskite to be deposited from a soluble material onto various substrates, rigid or flexible, with a maximum yield of 25.2 % [235]. In this process, it is possible to measure the desired layer profile in advance since the slot-die head width, the print area width, flow rate, and substrate speed can determine the thickness. In slot dies, the cover size is unlimited, even 2-meter lengths that are typical in industrial settings [236].

The structure of a perovskite solar cell (PSC) consists of several layers: a transparent conductive oxide serving as the front electrode, a perovskite absorber situated between the electron transport layer (ETL) and hole transport layer (HTL), and a back electrode [237–242]. The ETL, HTL, and perovskite layers can be deposited using the slot die layer method. For instance, the ETL, comprising zinc oxide and phenyl-C61-butyric acid methyl ester (PCBM), as well as the HTL consisting of spiro-MeOTAD and poly-3-hexylthiophene (P3HT), along with the TiO₂ mesoporous film, can all be deposited using the slot die method. PSCs are generally categorized into two types, one of which is mesoscopic PSCs. These solar cells utilize a mesoporous TiO₂ layer as the charge transport layer for the first time, resulting in improved device performance [236,243]. Mesoporous TiO₂ layers are not compatible with conventional flexible substrates used in the R2R process due to their preparation requiring high-temperature baking. In contrast, planar perovskite PSC solar cells can be manufactured at relatively lower temperatures, making them more suitable for the slot-die process. However, mesoporous TiO₂ layers serve a dual purpose: they facilitate charge transport and act as supports, preventing the formation of excessively large crystals [244]. HTLs are crucial for effective hole extraction and reducing charge recombination [238]. While small molecule HTMs are common, polymers and p-type inorganic semiconductors are gaining attention. Dopant-free HTMs can enhance PSC stability, with designs focusing on intermolecular interactions, solubility, energy alignment, and defect passivation. The counter electrode also impacts device efficiency and stability. Noble metals like Au or Ag are common but costly and prone to metal diffusion. Non-noble metals are being explored, with copper and its alloys showing promise due to low cost and stability. Carbon electrodes, including graphites, graphenes, and carbon nanotubes, serve as effective counter electrodes and HTLs, offering high carrier mobility, suitable band alignment, and stability in harsh conditions [237].

Perovskite solar cells are made with different structures depending on the role of perovskite in the cell or the nature of the upper and lower electrodes. These PSCs are generally divided into direct, N-I-P (negative-intrinsic-positive)[245] and inverted, P-I-N (positive-intrinsic-negative) [246]. Although most of the research so far has focused on perovskite coated using one-step slot-die in P-I-N device, The issue of instability in the P-I-N stack is causing significant concern about its commercialization [247]. One of the most frequently utilized hole transport layer in P-I-N, PEDOT: PSS, is susceptible to H₂O and fast degrade due to the instability of interfaces, the acidic feature of PEDOT, and the release of PSS [248]. Contrary to the N-I-P configuration, which typically ought to undergo high-temperature to form the metal oxide film, the P-I-N configuration is composed of organic films that can be treated at low temperatures. Consequently, this configuration is well-suited for plastic substrates. Recent advancements in processing metal oxide ETLs at low temperature, specifically tin(IV) oxide, have made it possible to use

N-I-P stacks with flexible plastic substrates [249]. But for an efficient R2R approach, all the layers forming the PSCs need to be printable.

The deposition method employed for the layers plays a crucial role in determining their formation and morphology, as well as how they are stacked, their surface properties, and the type and quantity of defects. For example, the size of grains and the presence of grain boundaries in the perovskite layer can influence the formation of electron trap states, consequently impacting the performance of the device. In addition, any connecting holes or other defects through the layer can lead to a short circuit [249]. Especially for the TiO₂ blocking layer, cracks or defects can increase charge recombination, expose some areas to the underlying electrode, and create a path for shunt leakage [250]. The formulation of the material utilized is paramount in achieving high-quality coating with the slot die method and in circumventing the use of toxic and undesirable substances, thereby ensuring optimal performance. It is essential for all solvents employed in the fabrication of each layer to be non-toxic, particularly for large-scale processes. Moreover, steps involving high temperatures, such as the baking of titanium dioxide layers, should be eliminated to lower production costs and enable the utilization of a broader range of substrates, including plastic foils [251].

The slot die coating method offers the advantage of allowing the size and thickness of the desired layer to be predetermined by adjusting parameters such as the slot width, length, feed pump pressure, precursor solution viscosity, and coating speed. Achieving a higher line speed capacity and minimum solution waste is also because the raw materials are not lost, all the injected solution is transferred to the substrate, and controlled distribution by controlling the coat weight. Achieving a high-performance slot-die PSC is critical for fabricating and commercializing large-scale perovskite halide solar cells. Perovskite layers can be made without defects using the slot-die technique, and the production speed can also be increased. This method is a scalable and industrially applicable technique for large-scale PSCs that produces uniform tape with sharp edges, which is essential in layer design [252].

The slot die method has certain drawbacks. Minor disruptions in the height of the gap or the presence of contaminations have the potential to disturb or decompose the layer of the liquid, known as the meniscus. Additionally, perovskite coated with the slot die has a high roughness in the obtained layers. PSC devices prepared at substrate temperatures above 110 °C have a lower PCE due to the loss of MAI [253,254]. In addition, the risk of partial delamination of the perovskite layer is higher than that of the spin coating layers [254]. The slot die method has made great strides in large-scale manufacturing processes over the past few years. However, some parameters still need to be optimized:

It is important to emphasize the substrate treatment because the substrate temperature, wettability, and cleanliness can affect the perovskite film obtained.

It is crucial to delve into the significance of the perovskite precursor solution, as the crystallization process is profoundly impacted by various factors including the composition, concentration, and types of solvent utilized. To obtain high-quality perovskite films, it is crucial to optimize the fabrication process of large-scale devices by extensively investigating and carefully adjusting the fabrication parameters.

By expanding the large-scale fabrication process to encompass various functional layers, it becomes feasible to decrease the preparation time of the entire device[255].

According to the available reports, slot die-coated PSCs have been shown to have good PCEs. However, this has mainly been seen for devices that use small aperture masks during testing. To evaluate large-area PSCs' power generation potential, it is equally important to demonstrate their performance.

To mitigate the detrimental effects of ambient air humidity on the growth of perovskite layers, the slot die process is conducted within a glove box filled with nitrogen gas [256–258]. To employ the slot-die

method in ambient air conditions, a blend of solvent and additives is introduced into the perovskite precursor solution. This mixture enhances the water-repellent properties or extends the crystallization process of the PVS_k layer, efficiently impeding moisture infiltration and resulting in a dense perovskite layer devoid of voids. Furthermore, techniques such as heated substrate and inert gas blowing are often utilized during the manufacturing process to shield the perovskite layer from moisture and promote the formation of dense and uniform layers [259].

Gao et al. [253] utilized slot die coating under ambient conditions (40 % humidity) to achieve planar heterogeneous PSCs through a sequential deposition process. They ensured a uniform film by maintaining the substrate temperature through in situ heating during the slot-die processes. To enhance the quality of perovskite films, they used a mixed solvent of DMF and DMSO in a volume ratio of 9:1 and additives such as cesium iodide (CsI), formamidinium iodide (HC(NH₂)₂I, FAI), methylammonium bromide (CH₃NH₃Br, MABr), and methylammonium chloride (CH₃NH₃Cl, MACl) with a weight ratio of 27: 23: 2.3: 2.3 in milligrams. The coated PSCs achieved PCE of 14.55 %.

Perovskite layers produced via slot die tend to exhibit overgrown crystals compared to those produced via spin coating. Due to the inherent instability of perovskites, PSCs exhibit poor long-term stability. The lifetime of perovskite solar cell is significantly shortened by the experience of water, heat, oxygen, and light. Moreover, the PCE of perovskite solar cell is typically less than that of traditional silicon solar cells and decreases as the dimensions of the cell increases, posing a significant limitation for commercialization efforts. Furthermore, the PCE of PSCs is influenced by PVS_k film quality, which, is contingent upon the synthesis approach utilized. The development of efficient and stable PSCs has been greatly influenced by the attainment of high-quality perovskite layers. Additionally, the morphology of the perovskite layer plays a pivotal role in determining the device's lifespan. Devices with larger perovskite grains exhibit slower degradation compared to those with smaller grains [260]. However, PSCs stability remains a critical challenge for commercialization. The deposition method plays an important role in determining the stability of PSCs. Slot die coating ensures a uniform film thickness, which is crucial for the stability of PSCs. Uniform layers reduce the likelihood of defect formation, which can act as sites for moisture entry and ion migration. This method allows for controlled drying of the perovskite layer, which can prevent pinholes and other defects that compromise stability. The slot die coating is compatible with various encapsulation techniques, which protects PSCs from environmental factors such as moisture and oxygen and increases their stability. Residual solvents from the slot die coating process can affect the stability of the perovskite layer. Proper solvent management and post-deposition treatments are essential to reduce this problem. [261] While spin-coated PSCs often exhibit good initial performance, they can quickly degrade under environmental stress due to residual solvent and poor film uniformity. [261,262] Vapor deposition techniques, such as thermal evaporation and chemical vapor deposition (CVD), provide excellent control over film composition and thickness. Vapor-deposited PSCs generally exhibit high stability due to the purity and uniformity of the layers. The absence of solvent residues increases stability [263]. However, these methods are usually more expensive and more complex than solution-based methods such as slot die coating, which affects their scalability. The stability of slot die coated PSCs can be enhanced through careful control of the deposition process and post-treatment steps, and they typically exhibit stability comparable to or superior to other solution-based methods.

In the slot die method, the thickness of the wet layer is determined by the amount of solution placed on the substrate. This technique can handle solutions with high or low viscosity and deposit a wide range of thicknesses. One of the primary benefits of slot coverage is its scalability, which allows it to be used on an industrial scale. It produces excellent uniform films, and the solution flow is well-controlled, resulting in minimal soluble waste. However, compared to other methods, this

technique has a very high initial setup cost [264].

Spin coating is a method where a liquid solution is spread on a flat surface that is either already spinning or subsequently begins to rotate. The centripetal force evenly distributes the solution as a thin layer across the surface, allowing for uniform thin films with varying thicknesses (from nm to μm). Post-deposition heat treatment is not always necessary, as the airflow generated by the spin can quickly dry the layer due to the substrate spin. Compared to other methods, spin coating is the most cost-effective since it doesn't require any high-energy processes. However, it has limitations: it's only effective for coating small substrates and unsuitable for large-scale production. Devices made by spin-coating are typically created inside glove boxes, which makes it challenging to prepare large-area modules of PSCs [253]. Moreover, this technique results in significant solution wastage due to the large amount of solution that is discarded. Additionally, it can pose challenges when coating with low-concentration solutions. It is not suitable for curved surfaces and presents difficulties when covering flexible surfaces.

In Doctor Blading's method, the final thickness of the wet layer is affected by the viscoelastic properties of the solution and the coating speed. This process is scalable, so it can be used to create uniform thin layers on large surfaces on an industrial scale. The solution is precipitated from the tank in a controlled manner. Therefore, the loss of solution during deposition (compared to dip coating and spin coating) is less. It can also produce films from solutions with a wide range of viscosities and cover rigid or flexible substrates. Among its disadvantages is that it is not possible to create films with a thickness of less than 10 microns. Conversely, this method is less precise compared to other techniques like spin coating. It is also challenging to attain uniform surfaces using this approach. The presence of any impurities in the system can result in streaks forming in the wet film as the blade approaches the substrate [265].

Active layer

Achieving a dry layer with adequate coverage is crucial for perovskite nucleation and crystal growth from the wet layer of the precursor solution. This poses a particular challenge when employing highly polar aprotic solvents, which are usually utilized in perovskite precursor inks. These inks have low volatility on numerous conventional substrates, potentially leading to substrate dewetting and large crystals growth with significant voids. This, in turn, can result in shunt leakages and shorts, adversely impacting the performance of PSCs. In the spin coating method, this challenge is addressed through the use of techniques such as "anti-solvent" or "solvent quench," wherein the layer is quickly faced to a solvent that effectively dissolves the precursors and promotes a fast nucleation of the perovskite. This method can produce high-quality layers and it is challenging for slot die coating, but feasible as recently demonstrated on sub-module size. As a result, many early studies on slot-die-coated perovskite layers used a two-step process since it can result in high surface coverage [266].

Another important point is that achieving an even and defect-free slot die-coated layer relies heavily on maintaining a stable meniscus between the slot head and the substrate. The rupture of this stable meniscus during slot die coating often results in various defects, including incomplete coating, uneven thickness, grooving, streaking, and the formation of bubbles [262,263]. To make a slot die-coated layer that is even and without defects, it is important to match the solution supply (precursor flow rate) and demand (coating rate). The coating speed and flow rate of the precursor solution should be adjusted until a uniform thin layer is obtained. If the precursor solution's flow rate is insufficient, the meniscus starts to break and get stuck. As the meniscus breaks down, the layer gradually thins in the direction of the coating. According to reports, the layer thickness measured by profilometry decreased from over 600 nm, where the coating started, to less than 400 nm, where the meniscus broke at the end of the coating [213].

Conversely, when the flow rate was too high, the meniscus began to

swell, leading to drastic thickness changes and overall thickening of the layer. The layer thickness increased from approximately 680 nm at the start of the coating to over 1 μm in the coating direction. At layer thicknesses greater than 1 μm , the layer begins to crack and bubble during annealing.

The layer becomes thicker when the gap height between the slot-die head and the substrate is increased. This was shown by putting perovskite layers with a slow increase in gap height from 40 μm to 50 μm to 60 μm and keeping other parameters the same. The thickness of the film that came out increased from 457 ± 7 nm to 563 ± 5 nm to 647 ± 5 nm. The average PCE started to go down from about 15.7–12.5–9.4 % as the perovskite layer became thicker [223].

Active layer morphology

The morphology of the perovskite layer in solar cells fabricated using the slot-die coating method is very important for the performance and efficiency of the devices. The morphology of the perovskite layer, including its crystallinity and grain size, is influenced by several factors that will be discussed below.

Two-step perovskite deposition. In this method, a lead halide layer that has been pre-deposited using the slot die method is exposed to a positive ion and a compound containing a halide ion, such as methyl ammonium iodide or cesium iodide. These substances react with each other to create the final perovskite. Typically, this is accomplished in one of two ways: either the slot die coating acquires a lead(II) iodide (PbI_2) layer, which then dries before the MAI solution is applied using the slot die method, or the PbI_2 that was coated using the slot die method is dipped into MAI solutions to form a layer. While the dipping process is often compatible with R2R processes, slot die technique is a more applicable and widely favored method for mass production due to its speed and minimal material wastage. The slot die method is often used as a replacement for the dip coating process. After injecting the MAI solution into the slot-die head and coating it onto the PbI_2 layer, the layer's color quickly changes to dark brown, indicating successful perovskite formation [266].

The slot-die process was first applied to fabricating PSCs through two-step deposition by Vak and co-workers in 2014 [153]. The shift from spin-coating to slot-die method was challenging due to the distinct layer formation mechanisms employed by each technique. Unlike spin coating, slot die coating does not necessitate rapid drying. The initial layer formed during slot die coating is usually wet and dries gradually when exposed to the surrounding environment. On the other hand, the layer deposited by spin coating dries rapidly through spinning. In the slot die system, the slow and natural drying process enables the perovskite, which contains small ions and has low solution viscosity, to remain mobile within the wet layer for an extended duration. This allows for mass transfer and solvent flow, leading to uncontrolled growth crystals and the formation of multiple pinholes within the lead(II) iodide layer in its final form. Consequently, the resulting layer exhibits a rough and non-uniform appearance. To avoid creating extreme crystals and pinholes, an aeration system was externally implemented throughout the slot die coating process. This system involved connecting the slot die head to both high-pressure N_2 gas and dry air. Employing this method resulted in a faster drying process of the lead(II) iodide layer and exhibited a uniform morphology without any pinholes in comparison with the naturally dried PbI_2 layers. Despite this, Vak et al. discovered that the lead(II) iodide layers, which were dried using this method, exhibited a density that was excessive, thus hindering the effective penetration of the methylammonium iodide solution into these layers and therefore prevented the conversion of the layers into MAPbI_3 perovskites at the second step. They discovered that subjecting the dried lead(II) iodide layers to annealing in an enclosed environment for 10 min results in crystal rearrangement and the creation of more opaque and lead(II) iodide porous layers. Subsequently, immersing these

opaque PbI_2 layers in the MAI solution facilitates their straightforward transformation into the desired black perovskite layers. Conversely, reddish-brown layers indicate incomplete conversion to perovskites. The two-step deposition process requires very uniform PbI_2 layers with high surface coverage and layers that convert easily to perovskites. In addition to being uniform, it is necessary for the PbI_2 layer to possess an adequately porous microstructure after the initial step. Moreover, they provided a detailed account of how the morphology of the layers was affected by the soaking of solvent vapor. The PbI_2 layer was deposited by slot die in the presence of N_2 blowing, which made it porous and opaque after soaking in solvent vapor. As a consequence, the PbI_2 demonstrated a heightened level of reactivity upon being exposed to methylammonium iodide in the second immersion stage, resulting in complete conversion to perovskite. The initial PCE of slot-die-coated PSCs was measured at 11.6 %, a value that can be compared to the performance of devices created using the spin coating method. Researchers also noted that increasing the temperature of the substrate while the slot-die coating is being carried out could enhance the conversion rate to perovskite. The substrate temperature during the coating of the MAI solution played a pivotal role in achieving high-quality perovskite layers. As the temperature of the substrate enhanced from its initial room temperature to 70°C, there was a significant increase in crystal size, resulting in a corresponding rise of PCE for the devices coated by slot-die, with a 4.2 % efficiency at room temperature and an 11.96 % efficiency at 70°C [153].

Heo et al. [244] discovered that the rate of crystallization for lead(II) iodide layers coated by slot-die can be slowed down by introducing a specific quantity of methylammonium iodide to the solution of lead(II) iodide ($\text{PbI}_2:\text{MAI} = 1:0.4$). This leads to the formation of a more reactive intermediate phase, which accelerates the transformation to the perovskite phase compared to a layer of pure PbI_2 . This method's PCE of slot die coated PSC devices was reported to be 10 % and 14.4 %, respectively.

A two-step deposition process is not ideal for large-scale production due to the rising intricacy, longer duration for coating, and decreased efficiency. Therefore, a one-step process is preferred.

One-step perovskite deposition. Compared to two-step coating methods, one-step coating methods are simpler, save time, and minimize solvent waste while providing better control over the final composition of perovskites. One-step methods have a significant disadvantage of fast crystallization that takes place immediately following the perovskite precursor solution deposition. This requires more complex strategies to control the crystallization than the two-step methods. Also, for deposition, perovskite precursor inks have low viscosity and lower volume fraction of adhesives, and more viscous pastes are more suitable. This creates serious challenges in the multi-layer printing process in terms of dehumidification during drying [267].

In 2015, Schmidt et al. [268] achieved a yield of 4.9 % using a one-step slot die coating of a precursor solution, which consisted of lead (II) chloride and methylammonium iodide (stoichiometric ratio 1:3) in DMF solvent. They used a polyethylene terephthalate/indium tin oxide (PET/ITO) flexible substrate and an Ag electrode. The reduced power conversion efficiency (PCE) compared to a similar device coated by spin coating on a glass/ITO substrate was attributed to the low quality of the PET/ITO substrate and the variation in the PVS layers morphology. To obtain a better film morphology, Cotella et al. [245] applied a perovskite solution to a preheated substrate using a one-step slot die method. They then rapidly dried the solution using N_2 blowing to regulate the crystallization process. This rapid drying technique led to decreased surface roughness, precise control over the crystallinity of perovskite, and the creation of uniformly coated devices using slot-die technology on a small scale. with a substantial increase in PCE up to 9.2 %. However, it isn't easy to control the reproducibility of device performance in the R2R process by blowing. Humid air has a significant effect on the quality of

the perovskite layer. For this reason, most high-performance devices are built in an N₂-filled glovebox or in humidity-controlled environments. In addition, the addition of a suitable polymer additive increases the compatibility of the process against moisture in the air.

Recently, Vesce et al. [269] reported the scaling up of the perovskite solar cell technology up to a sub-module (320 cm²) by a meniscus coating process for the full stack supported by air drying and with antisolvent quenching out of glove-box. They passivated the PVSk layer to reduce the nonradiative recombination and engineered the PVSk formulation to control the nuclei formation. They achieved an of 16.13 %, with only 7 % losses compared to small area cells and a 93 % GFF (Geometric Fill Factor), along with a stabilized efficiency of 15.5 % at the maximum power point under 1 SUN illumination. The sub-module remained stable during ISOS-D-1 testing for over 3000 hours. Additionally, they conducted a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) to showcase the economic and environmental advantages of the module scaling up. They demonstrated that the process of scaled antisolvent washing does not pose any substantial problems that would hinder the economic and environmental viability of scaling up.

Briefly, while the one-step method using slot die is theoretically simpler than the two-step method, achieving optimal coating parameters is heavily influenced by various factors such as the perovskite precursor solution's composition, device architecture, the type of material used for the charge transport layer, and the wetting features of both the surface and deposition environment. Additionally, in the single-step method, the naturally crystallized perovskite layer often exhibits anisotropic growth, resulting in poor uniformity and coating quality. This lack of uniformity restricts the use of perovskite solar cells in large-scale mass production. Two-stage slot die coating, on the other hand, is highly dependent on the deposition conditions and requires additional steps in the process, including enclosed chamber annealing [270] and mediator extraction treatment [271], to form a Pbl₂ porous layer. The nucleation and crystallization of various perovskite precursor solutions, whether in one-step or two-step methods, are influenced by the properties of the underlying layers onto which the perovskite is deposited, as well as the substrate surface characteristics.

To bring perovskite solar cells produced via the slot die method to the market, addressing the challenge of scaling up to module size is essential. Slot die offers a non-contact approach for depositing homogeneous and defect-free wet layers with high uniformity. The thickness of the wet layer can be controlled by adjusting the fluid flow rate and coating speed. However, challenges arise in controlling the formation of larger layers, perovskite crystallization, and achieving high-quality interfaces as the device area increases. This leads to a significant decrease in maximum efficiency and poses significant challenges for the research community.

Moreover, with the increase in substrate area, parameters such as the precise chemical composition of each layer, solvent quantity, and the development of an efficient ambient air processing system from both scientific and engineering perspectives become crucial. Additionally, factors influencing layer morphology need to be optimized according to the substrate dimensions. Furthermore, the poor thermal conductivity of large glass substrates leads to a lengthy process of several minutes for the substrate to uniformly attain the temperature of the larger layer. In order to solve this problem, Huang et al. [272] used near-infrared radiation (NIR) heating to rapidly heat the substrate. Fluorine-doped tin oxide (FTO) exhibits high absorption in the NIR region. Therefore, high temperatures can be achieved in seconds, compared to conventional heating. Poor module design can cause efficiency drops at larger dimensions in solar modules [273]. The coating process is influenced by various competing forces, including capillary, viscous, inertial, and elastic forces [274,275].

Approaches for manipulating crystal growth. Slot die coatings can fail in multiple ways. These are (i) 'low-flow' failures, where the downstream

meniscus splits, creating gaps in the wet film; (ii) the coating divides into several smaller bands with spaces along the width of the substrate; (iii) totally discontinuous films where the coating pauses and resumes along the length of the substrate; (iv) air-entrainment defects, related to the breakup of the upstream meniscus causing 'bubbles' in the wet film and areas of bare substrate; and (v) 'flooding' or 'dripping', where the ink flow to the head is too high compared to the coating speed and leads to the gradual accumulation of ink at the coating head and loss of pre-metering and the desired film thickness. The low-flow limit is a critical operational constraint, as it can result in the splitting of the downstream meniscus and the formation of a discontinuous film. To enhance the efficiency of perovskite solar cells, it is crucial to optimize the structure of perovskite layers. The morphology of this layer directly influences its optical and electrical properties, including light absorption, carrier emission length, charge transfer, and recombination rate. Crystal defects and grain boundaries can hinder charge transfer and negatively impact device performance. To mitigate these issues, it is desirable to maximize the grain size parallel to the substrate, thereby reducing the number of grain boundaries. Additionally, creating a compact morphology with minimal voids and void bridges is essential to minimize shunt losses and establish an optimal interface with adjacent charge collector layers [276,277]. Photoactive perovskite thin films are created through a disordered self-assembly process from the precursor solution, resulting in a series of polycrystals. This process necessitates precise regulation of environmental conditions (temperature and humidity) and solvents. The morphology of the perovskite layer is dictated by the rate of solvent evaporation and crystallization. The crystallization process is primarily affected by heating temperature, peeling speed, and precursor compositions [278]. The evaporation rate of slot die solvent is lower compared to spin coating. To enhance the solvent evaporation rate, various strategies are employed, including anti-solvent bath, gas quenching, and preheat substrate method. When the substrate area increases, it is necessary to optimize the processing parameters accordingly [261,279].

In the following, the factors affecting the morphology of the perovskite layer will be discussed briefly. These factors include stoichiometric ratios, the effect of the delay time between immersion and slot-die, the effect of airflow rate and solution feeding rate, the effect of ink concentration, and factors affecting the meniscus and its results.

In the two-step preparation of perovskite layers, the amount of materials deposited in the first step should be equal to the amount of halide materials in the second step, in terms of molarity. Any deviation from the optimal amount of cationic solution added during the second coating step can result in non-stoichiometric ratios, leading to poor crystallization or the formation of non-perovskite phases. In a one-step process, precise ink formulation is crucial to ensure high uniformity over a wide area and achieve large, defect-free, and well-crystallized perovskite grains, thereby maximizing device performance [280].

For devices that were coated with the two-step slot die method, a delay time between coating and immersion or the next slot die coating was necessary. However, the spin coating method does not require this delay time because the solvent rapidly evaporates during substrate rotation. Increasing the delay between coating and immersion from less than 15 seconds to 5 minutes resulted in an increase in the PCE of the perovskite layer coated with the slot die from less than 6–18 %. The duration of this lag time can be influenced by various factors that can affect the rate of solvent evaporation for the gap-coated precursor layer and thus affect the perovskite grain size, like the precursor's concentration, the size of the substrate, and the temperature at which the deposition takes place [261].

According to Gong et al. [281], the morphology and surface roughness of the perovskite layer has a strong relationship with the airflow rate (Q_{air}) and the rate of solution feeding (Q_{sol}), both of which are crucial for controlling the nucleation and growth of the perovskite layer. Perovskite crystal nucleation and growth were controlled by changing parameters such as airflow rate (Q_{air} ; from 5 to 30 L/min) in the dryer

and solution feeding rate (Q_{sol} ; from 0.01 to 0.05 mL/min) in the slot-die. Uniform perovskite layers of MAPbI₃ were fabricated by antisolvent-induced crystallization under optimal conditions, and thus, in optimized Q_{air} and Q_{sol} , the resulting PSCs exhibited a PCE of 9.68 % with low charge recombination and high absorption.

During the layer formation process in the one-step method, achieving well-optimized conditions for perovskite crystal nucleation and growth is crucial for obtaining a uniform and hole-free perovskite layer. This layer significantly influences the photovoltaic performance of PSCs. When the solution concentration reaches a critical level and becomes supersaturated, the solute colloid initiates nucleation and transforms into a crystal. If the solvent evaporation rate is slow, the solution concentration remains close to the critical level for an extended period. Consequently, the nucleus concentration remains low, allowing primary nuclei ample time and space to develop into large crystals. However, low nucleus concentration results in local solute accumulation on the substrate, leading to a perovskite film with inadequate surface coverage. Conversely, if the solvent evaporation rate is fast, the solution concentration rapidly surpasses the critical level. In this scenario, the nucleus concentration becomes high, and there is limited time and space for nucleus growth. The elevated nucleus concentration facilitates the formation of a fully covered perovskite layer with uniform yet fine grains. Therefore, precise control over solvent evaporation is essential to achieve a perovskite layer with high coverage, coarse-graining, and uniformity.

Drying conditions. Most highly scalable coating methods result in a wet layer of deposited ink. If this wet layer is allowed to dry uncontrollably, it often results in the formation of an inhomogeneous layer with poor surface coverage due to solute diffusion to several nucleation centers at random. However, high-quality perovskite layers are typically obtained by rapid nucleation followed by slow crystal growth [280].

Efforts to regulate the formation of perovskite layers using drying techniques have demonstrated the significance of enhancing the nucleation rate to achieve layers with extensive surface coverage. Rapid solvent drying can stop the crystallites and voids creation. Additionally, heating the coated mesoporous titania layer to 100 °C promotes a more pronounced reaction between PbI₂ layers and MAI, resulting in an increased number of surfaces available for conversion to perovskite. However, layers coated with slot die are more prone to defect formation compared to spin coating due to the absence of an inherent drying mechanism. Consequently, blowing and substrate heating were introduced in the slot die process to expedite solvent evaporation. Another promising deposition method that eliminates the need for N₂ gas blowing is hot deposition. This technique facilitates the growth of large grain sizes while minimizing rearrangement [282]. In the one-step method, the mixed precursor solution is placed on the heated substrate. A high substrate temperature (close to the boiling point of the solvent) ensures rapid evaporation of the solvent. As the solvent rapidly evaporates, PbI₂ and MAI react to form perovskite crystals. The high temperature promotes efficient crystallization, resulting in a uniform perovskite layer. Rapid evaporation reduces the possibility of defects such as very small pores or uncoated areas, resulting in high quality films with minimal defects. In the two-step method, by accelerating the evaporation of the solvent, a uniform PbI₂ layer is created. The high temperature facilitates the reaction between PbI₂ and MAI to form perovskite crystals and also ensures the rapid and uniform formation of the perovskite layer. Similar to the one-step method, rapid evaporation helps minimize defects and produces a high-quality perovskite layer. [283,284]

Raising the substrate temperature near the boiling point of the solvents has a beneficial effect of accelerating the solvent's evaporation to form perovskite crystals and reducing the removal time for mass transfer, which leads to the formation of ultrafine pores or uncoated areas. By using this method, researchers have demonstrated that power conversion efficiencies can reach as high as 14.7 % when using a rigid substrate, and 11.7 % when using a flexible substrate[285].

Cotella et al. [245] employed a combination of both a heated substrate and air-knife blowing in the slot die process. This was done to effectively control and regulate the drying speed of the perovskite precursor solution in a one-step method. When the perovskite layer was coated with slot die at room temperature, it exhibited poor layer morphology characterized by high surface roughness and pinholes, resulting in reduced efficiency and PSC breakdown. To expedite the evaporation of the solvent, they heated the substrate to an optimal value of 65 °C before initiating the perovskite solution coating. A system that blows air from a knife-like device was positioned at a certain distance away from the head that applies the coating to ensure uniform drying of the perovskite precursor solution. By heating the substrate to 65 °C before initiating the perovskite coating, the solvent from the wet perovskite layer was rapidly evaporated, leading to an increased concentration of the PVSk precursor and the formation of heterogeneous nucleation sites on the surface of the heated substrate. Consequently, this process facilitated accelerated crystal growth, with anisotropic crystal growth orientation parallel to the surface of the substrate, reducing surface roughness. The presence of airflow created a higher temperature gradient in the wet layer, thereby enhancing crystallization control due to the flattening effect. The fabricated perovskite solar cell yielded a power conversion efficiency (PCE) of 9.2 %, which is significantly higher than that of non-heated substrate and air-knife devices (2.4 %). Rong et al. [278] made PSCs with a 3D printer-based slot die coater strategy, which can also control x, y, and z positions by using a 3D printer and controlling acceleration and speed. They used slot die coating with a gas quenching process to produce a pinhole-free PbI₂ layer. Compared to the natural drying process, a more uniform and denser layer was formed in the gas quench process. The naturally dried layer had poor surface coverage. At room temperature, fine and round particles were formed, indicating that the perovskites were incomplete. Also, this process was accelerated by heating the substrates at a temperature of 50 °C. Cubic crystals were observed, and the perovskite layer was completely formed, and at a temperature of 70 °C, the size of the cubic crystals increased to about 1 mm.

Furthermore, to safeguard the PVSk layer from moisture when it is being made, heated substrates and inert gas-blowing techniques are extensively employed. These methods contribute to the formation of dense and uniform perovskite layers[258,259].

Researchers noted substantial enhancements in quasi-Fermi level splitting (QFLS) and charge carrier lifetimes through the optimization of drying and annealing conditions, ranging from 100 to 170 °C for 20 minutes. This optimization was evidenced by absolute and transient photoluminescence (P.L.) measurements. An optimized trade-off was attained between sample crystallinity and the formation of large PbI₂ aggregates on the film's surface during annealing at 150 °C. However, achieving uniform and dense perovskite layers typically necessitates longer annealing times (exceeding 10 min). This requirement poses a limitation for the rapid mass production process [280].

To address the mentioned problems in the direction of commercializing perovskite solar cells, Huang et al. [246] suggested an alternative approach for perovskite layer annealing in a two-step method. This method reduces the normally long annealing time to less than 30 seconds while maintaining the PCE. Also, they used near-infrared (NIR) radiation to form the perovskite layer rapidly. They developed a method of making a perovskite solar cell with a two-step synthesis method in the ambient atmosphere (for example, humid air, R.H. 60 % or more). This is the first study of the combination of NIR annealing and fabrication of slot-die PSCs based on the p-i-n structure at low temperatures. Shin-Han Huang et al. used a combined method of rapid NIR heating and slot die with the addition of n-butanol to increase NIR absorption and wettability of the perovskite precursor solution. They were able to fabricate a uniform perovskite layer with a large area (12 cm × 12 cm) in less than 20 seconds. PSCs coated with NIR slot die had a comparable PCE of 14.30 % compared to PSCs coated with H.P.-slot-die coated PSCs. The size of the crystals had a more uniform size

distribution, which indicated that the NIR heating process is more suitable for PSC in a wider area. High-efficiency PSCs can be produced over a wide area in ambient air without post-annealing by coating four layers with slot die. These layers include NiO_x as HTL, MAPbI_3 as perovskite layer, PCBM as ETL, and tetrabutylammonium hydroxide (TBAOH) as WFL. This facile process provides opportunities for rapid and energy-saving mass production of high-efficiency PSCs.

Precursor engineering. Precisely selecting perovskite precursors is an additional approach to regulate the nucleation and crystallization speed of perovskite layers, thereby enhancing coverage and surface morphology. When combined with techniques for controlling the drying process of the layers, this approach can facilitate the production of high-performance cells and modules [266]. In the one-step method, the proper balance of precursors ensures that nucleation occurs uniformly throughout the substrate and prevents the formation of large crystal grains and voids. Precursors that promote controlled crystallization produce smooth, defect-free layers. In the two-step method, precursors with very uniform and well-packed PbI_2 layers facilitate better reaction kinetics and more complete conversion to perovskite. The organic precursor (e.g., MAI or FAI) must effectively penetrate the PbI_2 layer. The solvent system and additives used with the organic precursor can significantly affect this penetration and perovskite phase formation. [283,284,286]

In recent years, many perovskite materials with excellent optoelectronic properties have been introduced for use in photovoltaics. Due to their high power conversion efficiency, methylammonium lead triiodide and its related compounds are good candidates for deposition using slot dies [246]. Consequently, slot dies use waste little ink and are capable of depositing a range of ink rheologies, including low-viscosity perovskites [287].

Lee et al. [285] reported the addition of lead acetate (PbAc_2) to a main solution consists of MAI and PbI_2 in 2-methoxy ethanol (2ME) in a one-step procedure, which resulted in the formation of MAPbI_3 and the byproduct methylammonium acetate (MAAc). In the presence of MAAc, crystal growth can be controlled while drying the wet layer, and crystallization can be increased. Probably the delayed crystallization is caused by MAAc, which controls the intermediate perovskite phase transition and/or the evaporation of the solvent but improves layer quality. It is believed that the remaining solvent and by-products are trapped inside the layer and are causing holes in the perovskite layer as a result. The lead chloride, along with the lead acetate, was added in order to prevent this from happening. Crystallization is delayed by the combined Lewis acid-base intermediate induced by the acetate anion. This leads to increased crystallinity and prevents cavities [287]. They reported an efficiency of 15.14 %, whereas in the absence of PbAc_2 , the quality of the perovskite layer is out of control and leads to a PCE of 2.63 %. Rapid crystallization may cause uncontrollable defects resulting in low yields. This problem can be solved by adding guanidinium cation (G.A.), which reduces the defects. In order to further improve the optoelectronic property of the MAPbI_3 layer and increase the lifetime of the carrier, by 0.12 mol% of guanidinium iodide incorporation, the precursor solution including PbAc_2 is improved by about 46 %. In a 46 cm^2 module result in a PCE of 19.44 %, and in the 16 cm^2 module based on $\text{GA}_{0.12}\text{MA}_{0.88}\text{PbI}_3$ perovskites, PCE is improved by 13.85 %. Crystallization and photovoltaic performance are remarkably depending on MAAc concentration, and the optimal concentration of 0.8 leads to the best photovoltaic performance. The perovskite layer's ability to cover and stick to the substrate is enhanced by increasing the concentration content from 0 to 0.8, while it is intensified by further increasing the concentration from 1.2 to 1.6. However, pores form between the perovskite layer and the substrate due to trapped MAAc evaporating. Fig. 10a–c shows the optical microscope images of the perovskite layer, the SEM images in two states without annealing, and the layers annealed at 130°C.

Non-halide lead sources have been used as viable candidates for perovskite precursors, in addition to conventional lead halide materials.

Lee et al. [285] reported new PSCs with PCE of 12.58 % based on a $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ precursor. However, the system containing $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ exhibited poor morphology due to spherical crystal growth. To address this issue, they introduced another non-halide Pb source, PbAc_2 , resulting in a relatively smooth perovskite morphology with fewer holes due to the easy removal of the unstable organic byproduct, MAAc. Nevertheless, the rapid crystallization of PbAc_2 led to small-sized perovskite layers, thereby limiting solar cell performance. To overcome this limitation, they designed a new precursor system based on PbAc_2 and PbCl_2 for solar modules using the slot die method. The addition of a small amount of PbCl_2 improved grain size and layer morphology. As a result, they obtained a PCE of 13.3 % in a module with an area of 10 cm^2 .

Whitaker et al. [261] observed that the thickness of the perovskite film increases with an increase in the concentration of perovskite precursor. They used MAI: PbI_2 :MAcI materials in NMP: DMF solvents to prepare five different concentrations of perovskite precursor with the same compositions: 20 % w/w, 23 % w/w, 25 % w/w, 30 % w/w, and 40 % w/w. These five different precursor concentrations were used to coat the slot die of five different layers using the same flow rate and gap height in a one-step method. The thickness of these layers was measured with a profilometer and was determined to be about 336 ± 14 nm, 431 ± 9 nm, 455 ± 6 nm, 549 ± 7 nm, and > 1 μm , respectively. Devices prepared from 20 % w/w showed a lower average J_{sc} of 18.6 ± 0.4 mA/cm^2 compared to thicker devices prepared from 25 % w/w with an average of 21.7 ± 0.3 mA/cm^2 . The current density of devices prepared from 23 % w/w, 25 % w/w, and 30 % w/w is the same at a 99 % confidence interval. However, increasing the precursor concentration to 40 % w/w resulted in a thick layer with numerous cracks, pinholes, and low efficiency.

Bisconti et al. [289] proposed the use of polymer materials for the deposition of perovskite layers by the slot die method in a single straightforward step. A polymer with suitable functional groups can interact with perovskite precursors, which helps form perovskite material with suitable morphology. Hydroxyl groups on the starch chain facilitate hydrogen interactions with methylammonium. Additionally, starch gelation in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) solvent enables adjustment of the viscosity of the perovskite precursor solution, adapting it to the slot die coating conditions. In this regard, a starch-polymer/perovskite composite (starch-polymer/perovskite composite) was made completely in accordance with the requirements of the slot die technique, which allows perovskite hybrid halide materials deposited in a simple step without using toxic solvents in an Uncontrolled (RH above 70 %) humid environment. The use of starch-polymer in perovskite precursor solutions increases their viscosity and slows down the crystallization of perovskite. This process yields perovskite layers at a moderate temperature (60°C) with favorable morphology. The material possesses a high light absorption coefficient across a broad spectrum of wavelengths, efficient dipole charge conduction, and suitable solution processing capabilities. Consequently, it is regarded as one of the most promising materials for advanced solar cells. [290].

Solvent engineering. The growth of perovskite layers can be adversely affected by humidity in the ambient air, which negatively impacts the device's performance [256]. Adding a small quantity of solvent and additives to the PVSk precursor solution can increase the hydrophobicity, prolong the crystallization process, and effectively prevent moisture penetration on the perovskite layer. Therefore, a dense perovskite layer without voids is created [281,291]. The use of highly polar aprotic organic solvents with elevated boiling points and toxicity levels poses considerable challenges in the large-scale commercialization of PSCs. These solvents not only have adverse effects on the environment but also substantially inflate the manufacturing costs of PSCs, thereby slowing down their commercialization. Therefore, it is imperative to adopt a solvent system with low toxicity or even non-toxicity to formulate the perovskite layer solution [292]. The formation process and quality of the perovskite layer are significantly influenced by the characteristics of the solvent, including boiling point, viscosity, vapor

pressure, polarity, and coordination ability. In general, the solvent provides an environment for the dissolution of perovskite precursors. Additionally, the solvent's functional group significantly affects its coordination with perovskite. For instance, common organic solvents like dimethylformamide (DMF) or dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) possess Lewis basic properties due to the presence of lone pairs of electrons. These solvents can coordinate with the Lewis acid Pb^{2+} to form a Lewis acid-base compound. Moreover, solvent polarity determines its coordination ability, which significantly impacts perovskite crystallization and consequently governs nucleation, crystal growth, and deposited perovskite layer morphology. Boiling point, viscosity, and vapor pressure can also influence film formation and resulting film morphology. Solvents with excessively high or low volatility yield poor-quality perovskite layers with suboptimal optoelectronic properties.

The evaporation rates of solvents are influenced by their boiling points, vapor pressure, and viscosity, as well as the interactions between the solvent and the solute. In the one-step method, solvents such as DMF and DMSO coordinate with Pb^{2+} ions and form dissolved complexes. This coordination helps to completely dissolve the precursors and ensures a homogeneous mixture. The formation of these complexes also stabilizes the precursor solution and prevents premature crystallization. In the two-step method, the solvent used to apply the MAI solution must effectively penetrate the PbI_2 layer and react to form the perovskite phase. Solvent polarity and coordination ability are very important here. For example, a solvent that forms weaker complexes with Pb^{2+} can facilitate faster reaction kinetics and increase the efficient conversion to perovskite. The solvent affects the recrystallization of PbI_2 when reacting with MAI. A solvent that enhances controlled evaporation and reaction kinetics results in uniform crystal growth and a high-quality perovskite film. The interaction between the specific functional group of the solvent and the perovskite colloidal precursor plays a crucial role in influencing the nucleation, crystal growth, and morphology of the perovskite layer [293]. For instance, DMF interacts with PbI_2 through the C=O functional group of DMF and Pb^{2+} in PbI_2 , while DMSO interacts with PbI_2 through the S=O group [294]. The ability of solvent coordination with solutes is demonstrated using D_N . Solvents with higher D_N values have a greater ability to donate electrons to coordinate with the Pb^{2+} electron acceptor, while solvents with low D_N values have a weak affinity for Pb^{2+} . As a result, solvents with high D_N values evaporate more slowly during the annealing process of the perovskite layer, which delays perovskite crystal growth. Conversely, solvents with low D_N values evaporate faster during the annealing process of the perovskite layer, which accelerates perovskite crystal nucleation.

Most solvents commonly employed in large-scale deposition techniques are either unable to dissolve or only partially dissolve inorganic lead halide salts, which serve as one of the precursors for perovskite [295]. The use of lead halide salts significantly limits the choice of solvent to achieve a uniform perovskite precursor solution. In the slot die method, some polar and aprotic solvents with high D_N values for coordination with lead halide salts, such as DMF, DMSO, N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP), dimethylacetamide (DMA), and γ -butyrolactone (GBL), are commonly employed [296–298]. The solvents used in the perovskite precursor solution are potent electron donors that can coordinate with the Pb^{2+} electron acceptor to form a uniform colloidal solution. However, DMF has a lower coordination ability with Pb^{2+} than I⁻, which leads to the formation of small needle-shaped MAPbI_3 perovskite colloidal clusters in the precursor solution, especially when the MAI: PbI_2 molar ratio is less than 1:1. Furthermore, DMF has a low coordination ability with Pb^{2+} , which results in the rapid evaporation of DMF and the rapid nucleation rate of perovskite crystals during the layer formation process. Consequently, when using DMF as a solvent, the resulting perovskite layer frequently displays a rough morphology with numerous pinholes, which ultimately compromises the performance of PSCs [299, 300].

Perovskite layers with smooth and even surfaces can be obtained by using DMSO. The S=O group in DMSO has more electrons than the C=O

group in DMF, which makes it a stronger Lewis base than DMF. When MAI and PbI_2 mix in the precursor solution during the layer formation, a stable intermediate phase of MAI- PbI_2 -DMSO is formed. This intermediate phase helps to delay the nucleation and growth of perovskite crystals. The perovskite layer had a more uniform shape without pinholes when the amount of DMSO in the precursor solution was increased. The crystals also had larger sizes, better contact with the substrate, and better vertical alignment. However, if the crystallization rate is too slow (in high DMSO concentration, i.e. PbI_2 :DMSO ratios of 1:4.2, 1:10, and 1:14.1), the perovskite layer has different sizes of perovskite crystal grains and high surface roughness. Fig. 12 shows the SEM spectrum with different ratios of PbI_2 :DMSO [275]. The toxicity of different solvents typically used in making PVSks films was compared by Solliance Solar Research, a research consortium based in the Netherlands. They found that DMSO was the least toxic among them. DMSO has low toxicity, but it can easily pass through the skin with any solutes it dissolves in. However, when large areas are dried, dewetting happens because DMSO has an extremely high surface energy and a boiling point that is also high. This leads to a PVSks film that is not uniform. Moreover, DMSO has relatively low volatility, and it does not wet most substrates well. This makes good layer coverage very hard. Geels et al. [301] suggested the addition of 2-butoxyethanol in DMSO to decrease the surface tension of the solvent mixture, which improved the humidity and increased the crystal size due to excellent coating.

Using X-ray scattering, Lee et al. [303] showed that a small amount of DMSO can prevent the formation of colloidal structures in the intermediate phase of solution and crystal related to MAPbI_3 and ME-2 (MAPbI_3 -2-ME). Instead, MAPbI_3 crystals and a small amount of DMSO ($2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_8$) intermediate phase are produced, which have a positive impact on the thin film formation. The coating results and device performance are also greatly influenced by the exact amount of DMSO and the age of the precursor solution, and their increase is harmful to perovskite thin film morphology [304].

Perovskite ink was dissolved by Jung et al. [305] using a mixture of CHP with DMSO and DMF. The FTIR results revealed the formation of an adduct between PbI_2 and DMSO. DMF and CHP are less polar and basic than DMSO, which accounts for this behavior. The crystallization rate of perovskites was slowed down by the formation of the extra compound with DMSO. Interestingly, CHP with a low vapor pressure and high boiling point likely stayed in the layer and helped to uniform core growth. These factors together resulted in a uniform, homogeneous perovskite layer that performs better.

Other solvents with higher Donor Number (DN) than DMF, such as DMA, NMP, GBL, HMPA, etc., have also been used as solvents to make the perovskite precursor solution besides DMSO. These solvents have similar chemical and physical properties [306,307].

To avoid the drawbacks of organic solvents, various methods that do not use any solvent have been invented. Hao et al. [308] used a gas-solid crystallization method without solvent at low temperatures to make the perovskite layer by one-step method. They applied solid PbI_2 and MAI vapor one after another to make a perovskite layer with no holes and high quality. This technique stops the creation of intermediate products and helps to make a perovskite layer with large grain size, low surface roughness, and high surface coverage. The perovskite solar cell device made by the gas-solid method reached PCE of 10.6 % with high consistency. Recently, Noel et al. [309] chose acetonitrile (ACN) as a solvent to make the perovskite precursor solution instead of traditional solvents. ACN has a low viscosity and boiling point, which makes the ACN-based formula crystallize quickly at room temperature. This formula is good for large-area production because it has less toxicity than DMF and can achieve high slot die speeds with its low viscosity. But, the high toxicity and flammability of this solvent system may stop its commercial use. Cs^+ and Br^- cannot be put in the precursor inks because they do not dissolve well in ACN, which means that the band gap cannot be changed. Perovskite precursors do not mix well in ACN but make a black solid of MAPbI_3 . To fix this problem, MA gas was used as an extra solvent and

passed into the black solid. This made the precursor mix well and get a stable, colorless, and clear solution. The new ACN/MA solvent was used to make a thick, even, hole-free perovskite layer with high accuracy in an area of 125 cm^2 . The PSCs had a PCE of more than 19 % for the film heated at 100°C and more than 17 % for the film without heating.

Although non-toxic solvents (e.g., alcohols, ACN, MA, and MMA) effectively reduce the precursor solution's toxicity, these solvents are flammable and explosive, posing a risk to device manufacturing safety. Researchers have used a much cleaner and safer solvent like H_2O to eliminate toxicity and safety issues. They added a little H_2O to DMF as a solvent to make PbI_2 dissolve and form a uniform solution [310]. PbI_2 dissolves in DMF at a concentration of 0.8, but it forms a colloidal suspension rather than a homogeneous solution because of its low solubility in dried DMF. The researchers found that adding a little H_2O to the PbI_2 /DMF suspension can alter the polarity parameters, dielectric constant, and solubility of DMF, making the solution homogeneous. Moreover, adding a little H_2O can improve the quality of the perovskite layer. Especially, the perovskite layer showed remarkable purity and density, with no pinholes, when the H_2O amount was 2 %. To prepare the precursor solution $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_{3-x}\text{Cl}_x$, Liu et al. [311] raised the water content to above 20 %. They discovered that the H_2O /DMF solvent can decrease the drying rate of the layer in the layer formation process, which lowers the nucleation rate of perovskite grains, and a perovskite layer with coarse grains and high density can be achieved. The PSCs they made had good reproducibility with a PCE of 20.1 %/70. Fig. 13 displays images of PbI_2 /DMF suspensions with different volume ratios of H_2O and SEM images of perovskite layers made with different volume ratios of H_2O to DMF.

The most commonly used solvents for fabricating high-performance PSCs are polar solvents like DMF, DMSO, NMP, GBL, DMA, or their mixtures with tunable coordination capabilities. However, these solvents are toxic and flammable, posing serious risks to human health and the environment. Recently, researchers have developed an alcohol-water solvent that offers a promising "green" alternative for PSCs.

Additives and surface modification. The stability and efficiency of PSCs have been improved by additives and surface modification, which affect the growth of crystal and the morphology of PVSk layers. Properly preparing the surface of a substrate is a vital part of manufacturing that guarantees optimal production efficiency. Contaminants that are not removed during the preparation of the substrate can influence each layer

of the cell. Additionally, ensuring uniform surface conditions across a large area is crucial for achieving uniform solution coating. Fast processing is also essential as prolonged process times can escalate manufacturing costs [312]. Surface modifications mainly aim at cleaning surfaces and increasing surface energy. Surface energy arises from the uneven surroundings of surface atoms by dissimilar atoms, unlike atoms within a solid or liquid, resulting in a higher energy state. The uniformity of the coating depends on the contact angle between the liquid ink and the substrate, which is a vital parameter. A high contact angle makes the ink wet the substrate unevenly, instead of coating it uniformly. Even if full coating is achieved, a high contact angle can cause slow ink equilibration in the flat wet layer. This slow equilibration can lead to ink solids settling before a smooth wet film is formed, which harms the coating uniformity. To solve this problem, different surface modifications are used to increase surface energy and ensure fast equilibration of the wet layer.

The surface energy can be increased by partially oxidizing the surface and removing pollutants from it. This can be done by using three common methods: UV-Ozone, oxygen plasma, and corona discharge. However, these approaches can also create an oxide layer on the surface, which can interfere with the transport of charge carriers across the layer interface. This can have an effect on how well the device works.

The sample is put in a closed chamber and exposed to UV light for the UV-Ozone process. A mercury discharge light that gives out UV light at 185 nm and 254 nm wavelengths is used in a typical UV-ozone system. The oxygen in the air takes in the 185 nm light, but not the 254 nm light. This makes atomic oxygen and ozone form [313]. The sample surface and the pollutants on it are oxidized by very active atomic oxygen. Organic molecules that become volatile under oxidation go away from the surface, making it clean. The sample surface also forms oxide and hydroxide groups with oxygen, which have higher surface energy and make the surface more wettable. The surface may take in UV radiation that the air does not absorb, which makes the surface contaminants break down. The surface cleaning is slow when only UV light (wavelength $< 242 \text{ nm}$, bearing enough photon energy to make ozone (O_3)) or only O_3 is used, but it is about 100 times faster when both are used [314]. UV-Ozone treatment is popular because of its simple operation.

The sample surface is passed near the arc discharge in the air between two electrodes with high voltage. The high voltage changes between the electrodes and makes the free charges move faster and collide

Fig. 13. (a) illustrates the process of applying a D-bar coating, which involves spreading the precursor solution over the D-bar and moving the TCO substrate at a speed of 5 mm/s. To dry the wet film, an air knife is utilized to blow Ar gas. Subsequently, the as-casted film undergoes a final heating process at a temperature of 130°C for a duration of 20 minutes. (b) The photographs depict perovskite films that were created using different solutions. The first solution consisted of a mixture of MAI and PbI_2 in DMF, while the second solution contained MAI and PbI_2 in 2-methoxy ethanol. The third solution was made up of 1.8MAI, 0.6 PbI_2 , and 0.4 PbAc_2 in 2-methoxy ethanol. (c) displays optical microscopic images of perovskite films at different times of Ar gas blowing. The films were prepared by applying the precursor solution on a SnO_2 -coated FTO substrate ($5 \times 5 \text{ cm}^2$), and then blowing Ar gas over it. The reference time, t_0 , is 47 seconds after the coating solution was loaded. Printed with permission from Ref. [288].

Fig. 14. Top-view and cross-sectional scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of MAPbI₃ films deposited on a NiO/FTO substrate using precursor solutions with varying PbI₂:DMSO ratios. (From 1[#] to 5[#] is related to 0:1, 1.0:1, 4.2:1, 10.0:1, and 14.1:1 ratios).

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with high energy and make more ionization of the air. This discharge makes a lot of atomic oxygen, which makes surface pollutants oxidize. Oxidized organic molecules that become volatile go away. The sample surface also forms oxide and hydroxide groups with oxygen, which make the surface energy higher and the surface more wettable. This process also makes ozone, but it does not help much in cleaning the surface without UV rays. There is no danger of UV rays going through and hurting the substrate because there are no UV rays in the process. Corona discharge is usually used for smooth surfaces or layers that are continuous because the correction needs the same distance (very small precision) between the sample and the electrode. There are different kinds of corona discharge tools that use airflow to guide the plasma, which can correct surfaces that are not smooth [312].

The sample is put in a closed chamber with oxygen at a low pressure from 1000 mTorr to 10 mTorr for oxygen plasma treatment. A changing electric field of frequency from KHz to MHz is used to make the natural ions move faster and make more ionization until most of the gas is ionized. The ionized atomic oxygen that comes out is very active and will oxidize any species that are not oxidized. Organic compounds and other compounds with carbon usually become volatile and are taken out of the chamber by the vacuum system. Plasma treatment is the strongest method out of the three methods. This is the only way to remove a lot of organic materials fast. So, it is not good for cleaning substrates that have organic materials that are meant to be there. All organic parts that are exposed to plasma are hurt or removed completely.

Reimeika et al. [312] studied how to replace UV-Ozone with Corona in a Slot-die for Perovskite solar cells. They did not test oxygen plasma because of the high cost and slow processing. UV-Ozone treatment is often low compatibility with rapid processing due to an exposure time of 5–15 minutes. Corona is a fast technique (treatment time less than seconds) that is widely used in the industry (for example, to print on plastic layers) and is compatible with R2R processing. In this study, PET coated with ITO was cleaned via UV-Ozone (15 minutes) or Corona (1000 Ws/m²). The researchers used a slot-die to put a suspension of zinc oxide nanoparticles (Nanograde N-10, 2.5 % by weight in IPA, particle size 10–15 nm) on a substrate moving at 0.6 cm/s. They also used the slot-die technique to put a PbI₂ precursor solution in DMSO on a substrate moving at 0.6 cm/s, with a temperature of 70°C and an ink pump speed of 20 μl/min. A stream of N₂ was used to make the dimethyl sulfoxide evaporate faster during the PbI₂ coating. The researchers looked at the PbI₂ coating on ZnO surfaces with 15 minutes of UV-Ozone and Corona (1000 Ws/m²) modification. PbI₂ on films treated with UV-Ozone had a uniform, clear texture. Surprisingly, ZnO films cleaned with corona often had a non-uniform cloudy texture of PbI₂ films. This effect might be because of the photocatalytic making of O²⁻ (superoxide ion) on the ZnO surface from UV light. The superoxide ions make the surface adsorbed organic species break down faster.

The use of mixed solvents and cationic additives of FA/MA/Cs has proven beneficial for the slot die process, resulting in the formation of uniform and compact perovskite layers. This approach has enabled the

successful slot-die coating of ETL, perovskite, and HTL layers, achieving an efficiency of up to 14.55 %. These findings are significant in advancing the industrialization and commercialization of perovskite solar cells through large-scale slot-die coating processes and R2R [249]. Zhu et al. [31] used NH₄Cl additive to improve the quality of the PVSk layer in a P-I-N structure with PEDOT:PSS as hole transport layer and PCBM as electron transport layer. Absorption spectroscopy showed the high light absorption of the active layer with NH₄Cl. Also, layers with NH₄Cl had higher photoluminescence intensity, which means less non-radiative recombination and layer defects. The making process was done at 45 % relative humidity, which gave PCE of 15.57 % for PSCs coated by Sheet-to-Sheet coating approach and 11.16 % for PSCs coated by R2R coating approach.

The perovskite layers have a lot of defects, especially at surfaces and grain boundaries, because of uneven stoichiometric compositions on surfaces, different polycrystalline nature, and losing organic components when heated. These defects make electronic states in the perovskite band gap and are non-radiative recombination centers, which make the carrier lifetime shorter and photovoltaic performance worse. Also, these defects make local charge build up, ion migration faster, and moisture or oxygen get in at first, which finally make device instability problems. These defects also prevent PSCs from being scaled up into modules and thus limit commercialization. An alternative strategy to enhance the morphology of the perovskite layer and mitigate defects involves the use of interlayers. Typically, an additional two-dimensional (2D) perovskite layer, such as PEAI, is employed. [315], OAI [316], and PDEAI [317] is formed on top of the primary perovskite absorber, which improves device stability. The 2D surface perovskite layer is often characterized by a persistent in-plane orientation and high exciton binding energy. These properties can potentially hinder charge transfer and diminish the passivation effect, particularly when employing bulky spacer cations.

Gu et al. [318], 3-amino propanoic acid as an ambipolar self-assembled monolayer (C3-SAM) was introduced to modify PEDOT:PSS. This approach, C3-SAM, was used on the PEDOT:PSS layer in a P-I-N configuration with the PEDOT:PSS (HTL)/CH₃NH₃PbI_{3-x}Cl_x/PCBM/ZnO (ETL) configuration. The modified PEDOT:PSS contributed to the better growth of the PVSk layer and positively affected the energy band alignment (0.2 eV) by inducing an additional permanent dipole. Lately, Koech et al. [319] introduced utilizing a polyethylene oxide (PEO) polymer additive in perovskite layers coated with slot-die in a P-I-N device with PEDOT:PSS (HTL), PEIE (ETL), (CH₃NH₃)_{0.6} (HC(NH₂)₂)_{0.38} Cs_{0.2} PbI_{2.975} Br_{0.025} perovskite and Ag top electrode and found to be useful for improving high humidity tolerance. The device with high humidity (55 ± 5 % RH) worked as well as the best device made in a dry environment (30 ± 5 % RH), but the device without polymer additive worked much worse. These results show a cheap making method for flexible perovskite solar cells that can be used for business purposes. This new method for making PSC in environmental conditions has the potential further to reduce production

costs, an important step towards commercialization. Notably, this fully R2R-processed PSC (except for the top contact) has been described so far, displaying an efficiency of 11.7 %.

Vapor-solution process

The solution-based coating process typically depends on harmful solvents like dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) and N, N-dimethylformamide (DMF) to dissolve PbI_2 [320]. Additionally, achieving uniform thin films on uneven or textured surfaces poses a significant challenge, particularly for perovskite/textured silicon tandem solar cells. On the other hand, various all-vapor deposition techniques have been explored, including thermal evaporation (TE), chemical vapor deposition (CVD), and magnetron sputtering [321–323]. These methods are compatible with a wide array of charge transport materials on the substrate and do not depend on the hydrophilicity or surface characteristics of the transport layer. Furthermore, they offer the significant advantage of avoiding toxic solvents. Among these vapor-based techniques, TE is particularly popular for fabricating large-area perovskite solar cells [324,325]. Controlling the composition and uniform deposition of organic salts is challenging due to their high vapor pressure, which causes the deposition process to be non-directional, filling the entire chamber during the thermal process. Additionally, the shuttle cover for the substrate and quartz crystal microbalance often fails to function properly. Moreover, achieving precise mixed cation and anion compositions, doping, material structure design, and additive engineering is difficult with the all-vapor deposition process. The mixed thermal evaporation-solution sequential two-step coating process has been explored to produce high-quality, surface-conformal perovskite thin films by integrating the benefits of both vapor and solution methods [326]. In this approach, the inorganic component PbI_2 is deposited using thermal evaporation, thereby eliminating the need for toxic solvents like DMSO and DMF. The second step involves depositing the organic component through various solution processes, which mitigates challenges related to controlling the evaporation rate and composition of the organic material. Additionally, this method facilitates the use of solvent engineering, additive engineering, and passivation strategies to enhance performance. It is also advantageous for depositing conformal, band-gap tunable perovskite layers on textured silicon, making it suitable for efficient tandem solar cells [327]. Yu et al. described a two-step sequential process combining thermal evaporation and spray-coating to produce high-quality perovskite films [328] with 19.17 % efficiency cell. They modified the solvent used for the FAI/Br solution, switching from isopropanol (IPA) to n-butyl alcohol. This change helps to reduce capillary flow and speeds up the reaction between the inorganic component and organic salts. Siegrist et al. employed a two-step sequential process combining thermal evaporation and blade coating to achieve high-quality, uniform perovskite films [329]. The resulting perovskite solar cells demonstrated an impressive PCE of 18.7 %, marking one of the highest efficiencies reported for the thermal evaporation-blade coating two-step process. The TE PbI_2 film exhibited a compact surface, which led to suboptimal morphology and the formation of undesirable 2D structures in the perovskite films when reacted with organic salts at room temperature, due to limited diffusion. To address this issue, Fang et al. developed a temperature-assisted crystal growth process was developed to regulate crystal growth and the morphology of the perovskite layer [320]. By employing the two-step sequential TE-blade coating method and controlling the substrate temperature, high-quality perovskite films with improved interdiffusion could be achieved. This approach resulted in a champion power conversion efficiency of 19.8 %.

Charge transport layers

Although the deposition process of the perovskite layer is critical, the charge transport layers also play a vital role. Defects in these layers can hurt the device's efficiency via numerous processes. Cavities and pinholes can result in the occurrence of shunt leakages, short circuits, and

charge blocking, leading to increased charge carrier recombination [254]. After the light hits the perovskite, electrons, and holes are created, the negative charges are extracted by the electron transport layer, and the holes are extracted by the hole transport layer, and flow in the external circuit.

Electron transport layer

The light receiving area for photosensitive materials must be increased to see improved device performance, and since mesoporous materials have a large specific surface area of up to $1000 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ and high porosity, these materials are the best for device performance [330]. Several mesoporous materials, including TiO_2 and SnO_2 , are the most common ETLs used in slot dies. The mesoporous layer facilitates the penetration of perovskite precursors, allowing for the formation of a sufficiently thick perovskite active layer. Mesoscopic perovskite solar cells (PSCs) also feature a compact TiO_2 layer deposited onto a fluorine-doped tin oxide (FTO) substrate. Following the compact layer, a mesoporous TiO_2 film is applied, enabling complete penetration of the perovskite material. However, TiO_2 is susceptible to degrading the perovskite structure upon exposure to UV light, presenting a notable challenge in the commercialization of PSCs [331]. On the other hand, these materials require an annealing temperature much higher than $300 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Temperature restrictions pose challenges when coating temperature-sensitive substrates like PET, which require a maximum processing temperature of $140 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [332]. The ETL layer is typically very thin, with a thickness ranging from a few nanometers to tens of nanometers. A significant challenge lies in producing a thin film of ETL without any pinholes over a plastic flexible substrate including rough surface in a large-area device... [333]. Defects and unbalanced charge transfers at perovskite/ETL or HTL interfaces are significant issues that can cause poor performance, instability, and hysteresis [334–338]. SnO_2 is a promising ETL for PSCs due to its favorable optoelectronic properties. It eliminates hysteresis, which is a common issue in PSCs based on TiO_2 ETLs. SnO_2 has energy band levels that match better with perovskite, faster electron mobility than TiO_2 , deep conduction band, and better transparency compared to titania. Additionally, SnO_2 does not cause significant damage to PVSks materials under exposure to UV radiation. Tin(IV) oxide is a good choice for electron transport layer in PSCs because it has good performance and stability. SnO_2 is widely used in small-area devices. Most reports make SnO_2 from tin(IV) chloride, which needs annealing at $180 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ with low temperature but long time of around an hour [339].

Bo et al. [340] used KOH stabilizing agent in SnO_2 NPs solution (15 % of colloidal dispersion in H_2O , Alfa Aesar). In this regard, potassium cations help in the growth of PVSks crystals, passivate the perovskite/ SnO_2 interface, and increase efficiency and stability. SnO_2 solution with the slot-die process has produced high-efficiency devices with a PCE of 17.18 % and flexible modules ($5 \times 6 \text{ cm}^2$) with an efficiency of more than 15 %. Researchers used an air knife with heated air connected to the slot-die head to dry the wet SnO_2 layers printed on the ITO/PET substrates. This strategy prevented the accumulation of SnO_2 nanocrystals in wet layers, which creates an uneven surface and connects the holes. The SnO_2 layers coated by slot-die, which dried fast by hot air blowing, had a flat and tight surface with a much smaller roughness (0.95 nm) than the layers dried naturally (5.3 nm). Potassium hydroxide was used as a stabilizer for SnO_2 nanocrystals, and potassium ions mostly stay in the tin(IV) oxide electron transport layer and at the perovskite/ SnO_2 interface, making the perovskite/ SnO_2 interface better.

Potassium ions at the SnO_2 /perovskite interface significantly influence the nucleation and growth of PVSks layers. When the PVSks precursor is deposited on various substrates without annealing and anti-solvent quenching, large grains form on the substrate modified with a low concentration of potassium. However, when the KOH concentration on the substrate surface is very high, many nuclei form, consuming a lot of solutes to grow and leading to small grains in the final microstructure of the perovskite layer. Consequently, a non-annealed porous layer

Fig. 15. (a) Images of PbI₂/DMF suspensions with different volume ratio of H₂O to DMF. (b) SEM images of PVSk layers made from different volume ratio of H₂O to DMF (Prov-0, 0.5, 1, 2, 3, and 4 are the volume ratio of 0, 0.5, 1, 2, 3, and 4 wt%, respectively). (c) The current density-voltage (J-V) curves of the best perovskite solar cell measured in both dark and light conditions. (d) Photo of (CH₃NH₃PbI_{3-x}Cl_x) PVSk precursor solutions with different H₂O contents. (e,f) Top-view SEM images of PVSk film created using a precursor without water and a precursor containing water, respectively. (g) The current density-voltage (J-V) curves of the best perovskite solar cell, which utilized a precursor solution consisting of 20% H₂O measured in both reverse and forward scans. (d-g) Reproduced under the CC-BY Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license terms.

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containing small PVSk grains forms on the non-treated ETL SnO₂, while a dense non-annealed layer with large grains forms on the KOH-treated SnO₂. After thermal annealing of the SnO₂ layer at 120 °C, the former exhibits many PbI₂ crystals on the surface of the perovskite layer, whereas the latter displays a very clear and smooth surface with larger grains.

On the other hand, ZnO is an alternative ETL that was prepared through the slot-die method on 3-axis CNC by Khambunkoed et al. [341] They achieved to a PCE of 10.8 % by the use of FTO/ZnO/Cs_{0.17}FA_{0.83}Pb(I_{0.83}Br_{0.17})₃/spiro-OMeTAD/carbo device configuration. Fig. 16 shows the top view and cross-section FE-SEM images of ZnO layers coated by slot-die on the FTO substrate with different coating speeds. In the ZnO thin film, many pinholes were caused by the non-smooth surface of the FTO substrate. The presence of pinholes can lead to direct contact between the FTO and the perovskite layer, resulting in charge recombination and poor device performance. However, the thick layer of ZnO can stop the direct contact of FTO and perovskite and prevent interfacial charge recombination. The thickness and morphology of the layer can be considered to be affected by the temperature of the substrate because the increase in temperature during deposition causes a decrease in the viscosity of the solution and, as a result, a decrease in the thickness of the final layer.

Li et al. used PCBM (40 nm) and BCP (11 nm) electron transport thin films by the slot-die way in NiO_x/perovskite/PCBM/BCP structure and

got a power conversion efficiency of 16 % for MAPbI₃ and 17 % for CsFAPbI₃. In this way, the PCBM layer was put with a slot die at a printing rate of 25 mm/s and an ink injection rate of 10 μL/s. The put layer was dried fast in a vacuum for 5 s. Then the BCP layer was put with slot die. They put the perovskite layer with the spin coating way. PCBM and BCP layers have amorphous shape and do not need special changes for crystallization after putting, but such organic ETLs need the use of good solvents and certain concentrations to make smooth and thick layers. Also, the slot-die way is affected by the inhomogeneities in the ETL surface, so different kinds of ETL mostly change the crystallization of the perovskite material [342].

Hole transport layer

The hole transport layer (HTL) on PSCs for both P-I-N and N-I-P devices has been coated by the slot-die method. PEDOT: PSS is the most usual hole transport layer for P-I-N structure, and it has been shown to make energy level alignment with perovskite better by slot die method [194]. But, PEDOT: PSS is still not a good HTL because of stability problems [303]. Zuo et al. [31] used reduced graphene oxide instead of PEDOT: PSS in the slot die method, which made performance better and a good HTL for big-scale PSCs. Metal oxide hole transport layers, like nickel oxide (NiO_x), exhibit greater stability in comparison to PEDOT: PSS. Le et al. [343] made a NiO_x layer from Ni-based salts and complexes in some steps. They put the HTL precursor on ITO glass layers at some

Fig. 16. (a) The utilization of PVsk absorber through slot-die coating. After putting the methylammonium iodide solution on lead(II) iodide, the slot-die head is immediately lifted. The red stripes that are observed are actually perovskite strips that are made right after putting lead (II) iodide by methylammonium iodide. (b) In this illustration, we can observe a slot die head depicted in two different variations. On the left side, we see the slot die head without the inclusion of a nitrogen flow nozzle, while on the right side, the slot die head is equipped with the nitrogen flow nozzle. The purpose of this nozzle is to expedite the drying process specifically for PbI_2 immediately after the slot die coating. (c) cross-sectional SEM image of the slot-die coated PSC on a flexible PET. (d) J-V feature of the best PSC measured under AM1.5 light. The voltage scans in both forward and reverse directions show little hysteresis. (e) A strip of flexible solar cells made by slot-die coating technique. Each individual cell possesses 1 cm^2 active area. (f) A depiction of a water droplet resting on a solid surface can be observed in the drawing. The surface/interface tension forces between the solid and liquid (γ_{LS}), the liquid and gas (γ_{LG}), and the solid and gas (γ_{SG}) phases play a crucial role in this scenario. When these three forces are in equilibrium and equal to one another, it leads to the formation of a specific contact angle denoted as θ . On the left side of the drop, you can observe the directions in which the liquid edge is moving forward (advancing) or backward (receding). (g) A photo of a water droplet taken on an untreated indium tin oxide surface. (h) After being exposed to UV-Ozone treatment for 15 minutes, a water droplet profile picture was taken on an indium tin oxide substrate. (i) A flat Lead(II) iodide obtained on a deposited zinc oxide treated with UV-Ozone. (j) Transmission optical microscope picture of the flat lead(II) iodide obtained on the zinc oxide treated with UV-Ozone. (k) A rough texture of lead(II) iodide obtained on a not enough Corona treated zinc oxide, the scale bar is identical to (i). (l) Transmission optical microscope picture of lead(II) iodide got by coating not enough Corona-treated Lead(II) iodide, the scale bar is identical to (j). Printed with permission from Ref. [312].

substrate temperatures (85, 100, 105, and $110 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) using slot-die. The substrate temperature is very important for the NiO_x layer's thickness and affects the device's performance a lot. The put NiO_x layer has a nanocrystalline grain structure, and slot-die putting does not change the surface shape of the put NiO_x layers, but it makes different thicknesses of the put layers.

One of the most widely used HTLs for N-I-P devices with slot-die coating is the layer of Spiro-OMeTAD, but its stability problems make it unsuitable for large-scale applications. Heo et al. [211] showed that

they used a π -conjugated compound called Bifluo-OMeTAD instead of spiro MeOTAD. This change led to the creation of amorphous layers that stopped the growth of big crystals that could lower the quality of spiro-OMeTAD layers. The researchers obtained a high efficiency of 14.7 % for a device with electron transport layer, perovskite, and hole transport layer coated by slot-die. Spiro-OMeTAD's wettability is a key factor in making perovskite solar cells, especially in slot-die coated solar cells that dry slowly [267]. Spiro-OMeTAD has a high symmetry and tends to crystallize and produce a very uneven surface on the perovskite

layer [344].

In summary, BifluoOMeTAD offers several advantages over Spiro-OMeTAD for use in PSCs. Firstly, it has a simple synthesis route. Secondly, its HOMO energy level is better matched with organic halide perovskites, resulting in more efficient hole transport and higher open circuit voltage. Most importantly, BifluoOMeTAD exhibits good thin film formation, which ensures better coating on the underlying perovskite layer, suppresses charge recombination, and facilitates higher short-circuit current density. Additionally, BifluoOMeTAD has good solubility and an amorphous morphology, allowing the creation of thicker layers with high quality. It can be readily synthesized in a single step using commercially available materials, rendering it an ideal candidate for large-scale production of perovskite solar cells employing the slot-die method [285].

In some cases, we see the removal of the hole transporting layer in the mesoscopic carbon perovskite solar cell (C-PSC), which is considered a structure with high potential for commercialization due to its high stability. Carbon electrodes are chemically neutral and highly compatible with scalable deposition methods [345]. Also, the lack of materials and difficulties in extracting metal ores that are usually used as back electrodes have caused carbon-based electrodes to be widely utilized in perovskite solar cells. Bogachuk et al. [346] suggested the use of carbon electrodes with low temperature because it causes high stability of the device, low production costs and low environmental impact. These electrodes have several advantages over electrodes fabricated at high temperature: Firstly, they offer a wider range of selective layers to choose from. Secondly, they can be used in conjunction with all methods of perovskite crystallization. Additionally, these electrodes are compatible with flexible substrates. Lastly, the deposition process for these electrodes is quicker compared to those fabricated at high temperatures, saving valuable time. Vesce et al. [347] also reported a PVSk solar module based on a low temperature carbon electrode by slot die method.

Verma et al. [273] deposited compact and mesoporous TiO_2 , ZrO_2 , and carbon layers on FTO using a slot-die coating process. All the layers were sequentially stacked on top of each other by slot-die coating until the complete solar cell device was obtained. They showed that the layers coated via the slot die did not need to be annealed separately. The prepared C-PSCs showed excellent stability and a long lifetime. In this mesoscopic C-PSC, MAPbI_3 perovskite created the cationic perovskite crystal structure of $(5\text{-AVAI})_x(\text{MA})_{1-x}\text{PbI}_3$ by adding 5-ammonium valeric acid iodide (5-AVAI) solvent and was entered into the carbon structure through co-firing and infiltration. Infiltration of perovskite ink was performed through an automated system to ensure controlled volume, timing, droplet releasing height, and reproducibility. They reached a PCE of 12 % in this approach. Fig. 17. indicates the SEM images of all the layers coated with slot-die and then compares the topographic images of FTO and compact TiO_2 deposited on FTO by spray pyrolysis, screen printing, and slot-die coating. Table 3 summarizes the performance and stability of slot die coated perovskite solar cells.

Outlook and perspectives

Significant progress has been made in developing organic and perovskite solar cells since the advent of the scalable slot-die deposition technique, achieving photovoltaic performance close to that of laboratory devices fabricated by spin-coating. Benefiting from morphology controlling by solvent engineering, temperature control, triple strategy, and sequential process, slot-die coated organic solar cells have shown significant potential for large-scale R2R production, achieving efficiencies over 14 % in large-area devices ($\geq 1 \text{ cm}^2$) with high photoactive thickness tolerance and processed with non-toxic solvents (Fig. 20). The hot slot-die technique allows the possibility of controlling the morphology and achieving high crystallization with small phase separation through the precise adjustment of the active solution temperature, even for solutions processed in green hydrocarbon solvents

that have low solubility without any additive solvent. In addition, high and balanced carrier mobility are the keys to high photoactive thickness tolerance that the hot slot-die technique can provide along with ternary strategy through increasing and balancing donor and acceptor crystallinity and improving face-on orientation. Furthermore, sequentially processed graded structures developed by the dual-slot-die coating technique have shown increased photoactive thickness tolerance by improving the vertical phase separation of donor and acceptor and subsequently improving exciton separation, charge transfer, and extraction.

These results are significant and encouraging developments that have been achieved in recent years. However, more research is needed on the vertical phase separation of organic active layers in order to reduce the efficiency gap between thick and thin layers, where sequential processing has shown great potential. In addition, manufacturing these efficient devices includes non-scalable vacuum- and solution-based processes for coating charge transport layers. Therefore, research should be carried out on transferring the advances in vacuum-coated MoO_3 and spin-coated ZnO/SnO_2 charge transport layers to the promising scalable slot-die coating technique. Moreover, to create a desired connection between the active layer and the charge transport layers and reduce interfacial charge recombination, the development of charge transport materials with suitable energy levels and coating methods that can deposit uniform layers with good adhesion at the interfaces is necessary. To address this, using the newly developed dual-slot die technique to create a graded structure between the active layer and the charge transport layers can be worth investigating. So that employing this technique can not only result in good adhesion between the active layer and charge transport layers but can also help transfer the charge carriers by creating a graded structure at the interfaces.

Slot-die coating of PSCs is a powerful technique to deposit perovskite and other layers in case of miniaturized and large-scale devices with high performance, providing the best opportunities for making large PSCs with high PCE. Slot-die is simpler than other one-way coating methods and has the most economical deposition that is suitable for large-scale applications. The slot-die coating has achieved the highest efficiency for large perovskite solar cells in recent studies. Many strategies have been devised to control the formation of PVSk layer, both in terms of increasing the nucleation rates to create uniform layers and in regulating the crystal growth of perovskite to obtain large grains with strong bonding and good alignment. In the slot die coating method, efforts have been made to optimize the process parameters in order to achieve a perovskite layer with desirable properties such as larger grain size and reduced pinhole density. A larger grain size in the PVSk layer is desirable because it can improve the charge transport properties and overall device performance of the solar cell. Larger grains allow for better charge carrier mobility and reduce the likelihood of recombination events, leading to higher efficiency. Reducing pinhole density is also important because pinholes can act as pathways for charge recombination and can lead to device degradation over time. By minimizing pinhole density, the overall device stability and performance can be improved. Various techniques and process optimizations, such as controlling the precursor composition, deposition speed, and post-treatment processes, are employed to achieve these goals in the slot die coating method for perovskite solar cell fabrication. In this regard, efforts to produce doped layers with additives by forming chemical bonds with self-assembled monolayers or by adding a strongly coordinating solvent have improved surface connections between the interface of ETL/perovskite, HTL/perovskite, and HTM/electrode interface. Also, some efforts are being made to achieve a solvent system with low viscosity and fast drying that has low toxicity.

The selection of solvents, whether pure or mixed, and perovskite precursor formulations is critical for achieving factors such as solubility, crystallization rate, and PVSk conversion efficiency. Considerations such as viscosity, boiling point, and toxicity of solvents, as well as other chemical components of the PVSk ink, must be considered to ensure

Fig. 17. (a) How to make SnO_2 films by slot-die coating. (b) Atomic force microscopy (AFM) pictures of the tin(IV) oxide layers made without hot air help and (c) with hot air blowing. (d) The structure of the six sections series connected big-area flexible PSCMs. (e) A picture of the flexible PSCM and (f) the Performance of the big-area flexible PSCMs made by slot-die-coated SnO_2 substrates (f) shown by the J-V curves of the best flexible PSCM. (g) KOH-treated Water Alfa- SnO_2 -based CsFAMA PVSk layer. (h) SEM picture (Cross-section view) of the PSC. (i) The Top-view SEM pictures of Alfa- SnO_2 based CsFAMA PVSk layer, (j) Water Alfa- SnO_2 -based CsFAMA PVSk layer and (k) KOH-treated Water Alfa- SnO_2 -based CsFAMA PVSk layer.

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Table 3
Photovoltaic parameters and stability of slot die coated perovskite solar cells and submodules fabricated by different controlling morphology method.

Controlling morphology method	Steps	Configurations	Slot die coated layers	Solvent	Thickness (nm)	Deposition condition	Stability	Area (cm ²)	PCE (%)	Ref.		
Drying condition	Two-step	Glass/ITO/NiO NPs/ Cs _{0.17} FA _{0.83} Pb(I _{0.87} Br _{0.13}) ₃ /PCBM/ ZnO NPs/Ag	Active Layer	DMSO	-	ambient air	Maintained 85 % of their initial PCE in six months of storage in dark ambient air with covered glass.	1	17.05	[348]		
			Full layers	DMF: 650 nm DMSO (perovskite laeyr)	optimizing nitrogen blowing and controlling substrate temperature	-	1	15.1 R2R 13.0 R2R	[30]			
	One-step	Glass/ITO/PEDOT:PSS/ MA _{0.6} FA _{0.38} Cs _{0.02} PbI _{2.975} Br _{0.025} /PCBM/PEIE/Ag PET/ITO/PEDOT:PSS/MAPbI _{3-x} Cl _x /PCBM/Ag Glass/ITO/ZnO/MAPbI ₃ / Bifluo-OMeTAD/MoO ₃ /Ag Glass/ITO/PEDOT:PSS/CH ₃ NH ₃ PbI ₃ /PCM/PEI/Ag Glass/FTO/ZnO/ CH ₃ NH ₃ PbI ₃ /Carbon Glass/FTO/TiO ₂ /MAPbI _{3-x} Cl _x /Spiro-OMeTAD/Au	Active Layer	DMF	50 μm	ambient air	long-term stability without any sealing in humid air	0.1	14.7 R2R	[279]		
			HTL	DMF	280	ambient air	-	0.12	2.91 R2R	[349]		
			Active Layer	DMF: 100 DMSO	ambient air	-	0.1	12.7 R2R	[244]			
			Active Layer	DMF	310	ambient air	-	0.3	12.3 S2S	[246]		
			Active Layer	DMF	-	Coating under a Gas pump system	140 days	17.6	10.6	[350]		
			Active Layer	DMF	100	A class 10,000 clean room maintained at an average relative humidity below 50 %	-	0.0625	9.2	[245]		
			Precursor engineering	Two-step	Glass/FTO/ c-TiO ₂ /SnO ₂ / CsI-PbI ₂ / Spiro-OMeTAD Glass/ITO / ZnO / MAPbI ₃ / Bifluo-OMeTAD /MoO _x / Ag	Active Layer	DMF: 300 DMSO	Coating in a nitrogen-filled glovebox	-	12	15.2	[280]
						HTL	DMF	300	Coating in ambient air, Drying by N ₂ in an enclosed sample carrier	-	0.1	14.7 R2R
Active Layer	DMF	100				All device fabrication was carried out in air	-	0.1	14.4 R2R	[351]		
One-step	Glass/ITO/SnO ₂ / MAPbI ₃ /Spiro-OMeTAD/Au Glass/FTO/c-TiO ₂ /m-TiO ₂ /Cs _{0.17} FA _{0.83} Pb(I _{0.83} Br _{0.17}) ₃ / Spiro-OMeTAD/Au Glass/IZO/SnO ₂ /CH ₃ NH ₃ PbI ₃ /Spiro-OMeTAD/Au Glass/ITO/PEDOT:PSS/MAPbI ₃ /PCBM/Ca/Al Glass/ITO/PEDOT:PSS/MAPbI ₃ /PCBM/BCP/Ag Glass/ITO/PEDOT:PSS/MAPbI ₃ /C ₆₀ /PCBM/BCP/Ag Glass/ITO/PEDOT:PSS/(BA) ₂ (MA) ₃ PbI ₄ /PCBM/PEIE/Ag	Ag/HTL		DMF: 100 DMSO (Ag)	ambient air	-	1.2	11 R2R	[352]			
		Active Layer		NMP: 600 DMF	ambient air	-	0.06	18.0 R2R	[261]			
		Active Layer		DMF: 450 NMP	Coating at room temperature in a glovebox	A good stability after 180 h continuous illumination	0.09	17.5	[353]			
		ETL/ Active Layer		ACN:MA	-	ambient air	-	0.15	17.31	[354]		
		Active Layer		DMF	515	ambient air	Maintained 70 % of the initial PCE in a glovebox for 93 days	0.1	15.56 R2R	[31]		
		Active Layer		DMF	100	Coating in helium atmosphere	-	0.09	15.1	[355]		
		Active Layer		DMF	-	ambient air	A slow drop in PCE until 100 hours	0.1	13.3 R2R	[285]		
Active Layer	DMF	389	coating in air with surrounding humidity between 30 % and 50 % and substrate temperature of 50 °C	More than 5 months stored in a nitrogen glovebox	0.1	12.5 R2R	[356]					

(continued on next page)

Table 3 (continued)

Controlling morphology method	Steps	Configurations	Slot die coated layers	Solvent	Thickness (nm)	Deposition condition	Stability	Area (cm ²)	PCE (%)	Ref.
Solvent engineering	Two-step	Glass/ITO/PEDOT:PSS/CH ₃ NH ₃ PbI _{3-x} Cl _x /PCBM/BCP/Ag	Active Layer	DMF: DMSO	550	ambient air	Maintained 86 % of initial PCE after 200 s continuous illuminations	0.1	11.4 R2R	[281]
		Glass/ITO/PEDOT:PSS/MAPbI ₃ /PCBM/BCP/Ag	Active Layer	CHP: DMSO	-	ambient air	-	0.1	9.57 R2R	[305]
		PET/ITO/PEDOT:PSS/MAPbI _{3-x} Cl _x /PCBM/ZnO/Ag	ETL	DMF	350–500	ambient air	-	0.5	5.1 R2R	[318]
		PET/ITO/PEDOT:PSS/MAPbI _{3-x} Cl _x /PCBM/ZnO/Ag	ETL	DMF	6 μm	ambient air	-	0.2–0.5	4.9 R2R	[268]
		Glass/ITO/Cs _{0.22} FA _{0.78} Pb(I _{0.85} Br _{0.15}) ₃ /C ₆₀ /SnO ₂ /Ag (Tandem With Silicon Solar Cells)	Active Layer	DMF: DMSO	800	Coating in a nitrogen atmosphere without exposure to air	over 14 days	1	25.2	[235]
		Glass/FTO/SnO ₂ /PVK/ Spiro-OMeTAD/ Au	Active Layer	DMSO	310	coating in a glovebox under a nitrogen atmosphere with H ₂ O and O ₂ levels below 10 ppm	Maintained 96 % of initial PCE for over 3 min	12	19.8 S2S	[357]
		Glass/FTO/SnO ₂ /MAPbI ₃ /Spiro-OMeTAD/Au	Active Layer	DMSO	-	ambient air	-	10	18.3 R2R	[271]
		Glass/ITO/SnO ₂ / MAPbI ₃ /Spiro-OMeTAD/Ag	Active Layer	DMF: DMSO	700	ambient air	160 s	0.07	14.55 R2R	[253]
		Glass/ITO/2PACz/MAPbI ₃ /C ₆₀ /BCP/Cu	Active Layer	2-ME: DMSO	800	ambient air	-	2.2	20.8	[304]
		Glass/FTO/SnO ₂ / MAPbI ₃ /HTL/Au	HTL	DMF: DMSO	-	Coating in controllable evaporation rate condition	Maintained 85 % of PCE after aging under dark ambient conditions for 1000 h	10	17.7 R2R	[358]
additive engineering	Two-step	Glass/ITO / MeO–2PACz / FAPbI ₃ / LiF / C ₆₀ /SnO _x / Cu	Active Layer	NMP:2-ME:ACN	853–1415	ambient air	9 months of outdoor exposure in the cold days of the year	12.7	17.1 and 22.3 achieved in small-area (2.2 cm ²) devices	[359]
		Glass/FTO/NiO _x / MAPbI ₃ /PCBM/PEI/Ag	Active Layer	GBL: DMSO	700	ambient air	-	0.09	10.96	[272]
		Glass/FTO/SnO ₂ / FAPbI ₃ /Spiro-OMeTAD/Au	Active Layer	DMF: DMSO	500	coating in an enclosed environment with humidity control of 30–40 % RH	-	0.09	18 S2S	[360]
		Glass/FTO/SnO ₂ /CsPbBr ₃ /Spiro-OMeTAD/Au	Active Layer	DMF: DMSO	550	Enclosed environment with a RH ≈ 30–40 %	Maintained ≈ 72 % of its initial PCE after 426 days (10 224 h) in 30 % RH, while they retain 82 % and 54 % of initial PCE over 1150 and 958 h at 65 and 85 °C, respectively	100	18.94 R2R	[361]
		Glass/ITO/ NiO NPs / MAPbI ₃ /PCBM/ ZnO NPs/Ag	Active Layer	DMF: DMSO	100	ambient air	95 days in ambient air	0.1	16.08	[362]
		Glass/ITO/NiO _x /CsFAPbI ₃ /PCBM/BCP	Active Layer	DMF: NMP	430	ambient air	1000 h	2.1	17.33	[343]
		Glass/ITO/NiO _x /MAPbI ₃ /PCBM/BCP	Active Layer	NMP	450				16.06	
		Glass/ITO/SnO ₂ / CsFAPbI ₃ /Spiro-OMeTAD/Ag	Active Layer	DMF: NMP	20	ambient air	-	2.1	14.9	[18]

Fig. 18. Top-view (a–d), cross-sectional (e–h) FE-SEM pictures and AFM data (i–l) of ZnO films coated by slot-die on FTO at different coating speeds: (a, e, i) 9.8, (b, f, j) 14.8, (c, g, k) 18.0, (d, h, l) 26.5 mm/s. The film defects are shown by red circles. (To understand the meaning of the color in this figure legend, the reader should look at the Web version of this article).

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Fig. 19. SEM images (Cross-sectional view) of full slot die-coated MPSCs. (a) Cross-section of the full stack. (b) Zoom into the m-TiO₂ and m-ZrO₂ films. (c) The interface between FTO and mesoporous TiO₂ layers. The layer of compact TiO₂ cannot be seen.

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both device performance and compliance with health and environmental regulations. The quality of the perovskite film is influenced by factors like coating temperature and ambient humidity levels, which should be adjusted accordingly. In the context of slot die application, several aspects are essential for advancing PSCs. Apart from toxicity concerns, solvents should possess stable physical and chemical properties to enhance the long-term stability of the perovskite precursor solution and the resulting perovskite film. However, finding a non-toxic and reliable solvent with suitable boiling point, viscosity, vapor pressure, polarity, and coordination ability remains a challenge for future research efforts. When making large PSCs using the slot-die method, several factors that are not relevant for small cells can become a significant problem. For example, increasing costs in the trial-and-error process to produce an ideal large-scale module by the slot-die method become a new challenge.

In general, to achieve the most efficient large-area perovskite solar cells using the slot-die method, several important factors need to be

explored in the future. First, perovskite inks should be properly formulated and designed with optimal parameters to produce high-quality, defect-free and smooth crystalline perovskite layers that can minimize recombination due to flaws. Second, perovskite composition engineering should be advanced to enhance band alignment with carrier transport layers and the stability of printed PSCs. Third, the slot-die method (or a mix of different printing methods) should be applied to all device layers, including the perovskite layer, ETL, HTL, and electrodes, to make perovskite PV modules marketable. In addition, inorganic charge transport layers (CTLs) such as SnO₂, ZnO, NiOx, CuO, CuSCN, CuI, In₂S₃, and MoS₂ can be better choices than organic CTLs due to their superior stability against heat and moisture. Thus, it is necessary to research the deposition of these CTLs by the slot-die method. Future research should also investigate the effects of the type and density of defects created in the slot die method. With the successes achieved in fabricating large-area PSCs using techniques such as slot die, the dream of commercializing this type of solar cell is becoming a reality.

Fig. 20. Power conversion efficiency records of champion PSCs on (a) low-scale and (b) large-scale fabrication. The numbers mentioned in the brackets are the device area.

Although, with laminated PSC devices, the instability and toxicity of these cells have been largely overcome, these issues still remain as challenges that laboratory researchers are trying to solve.

Indeed, the scaling up of PSC technology has been a topic of significant research and development. Various coating and printing methods have been investigated for this purpose, both in controlled environments like glove boxes and in ambient air settings. However, achieving highly efficient and stable devices requires proper optimization of perovskite precursor solutions and coating parameters for each method. The coating conditions and the rheology of the ink, including its surface tension and viscosity, play a crucial role in determining the quality of the deposition as well as the occurrence of defects. While efforts have been made to scale up PVSk technology, few works have focused on very large area module fabrication. This is partly because traditional methods like spin coating, while still used for mini-modules, are not considered scalable and often require manual intervention to achieve uniform coatings without pinholes. Additionally, processes conducted in glove boxes are costly compared to those in ambient air environments and may not be easily replicable in large-scale manufacturing plants. Therefore, the manufacturing process for PVSk technology should ideally meet several requirements: it should be environmentally sustainable, cost-effective, can produce large quantities in a short time., and able to produce devices with good performance and stability. Achieving these goals remains a focus of ongoing research and development in the field of perovskite solar cells. The sustainability evaluation of the perovskite energy conversion technology can be done by the life cycle assessment (LCA) method [363]. This analytical approach enables the depiction of the environmental footprint of the entire process by calculating emissions and releases to the environment [364]. The utilization of LCA is widely considered as the most effective method for studying emerging technologies in small-scale, provided that reliable and comprehensive primary data can be accessed [365–369]. In the literature, authors have emphasized how achieving competitive environmental performance relies heavily on the ability to scale manufacturing processes effectively [364,370].

The successful commercialization of perovskite photovoltaic (PVSk PV) technology hinges on the ability to scale up laboratory-scale cells to large area modules [269,371].

In the scaling-up process, several key factors are crucial for achieving high-efficiency modules that are both reproducible and reliable [372, 373]:

1. High-quality large-area PVSk films: Ensuring the deposition of high-quality perovskite films by slot-die coating technique over larger areas is essential for maintaining device performance and efficiency.
2. Minimization of losses induced by front contact: Optimizing the design and materials used for the front contact layers is important to minimize losses and maximize light absorption.
3. Effective cells interconnections: Proper interconnection between individual cells within the module is essential for efficient current collection and reducing overall losses.

However, as the technology transitions from small-scale laboratory cells to larger module devices, challenges arise. Layers may become more heterogeneous, and the optimized processes and material compositions for small-area cells may not directly translate to larger areas [374]. Additionally, the polycrystalline nature of perovskite films created through solution processing can lead to defects at grain boundaries and vacancies during fabrication, further complicating the scaling-up process [375].

Addressing these challenges requires continued research and development efforts to optimize processes, materials, and interconnection techniques specifically for large-area module devices, ensuring the reproducibility, reliability, and high efficiency of perovskite PVSk technology at the commercial scale.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Reza Keshavarzi: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Conceptualization. **Mojtaba Abdi-Jalebi:** Writing – review & editing. **Niloufar Afzali:** Writing – original draft. **Aldo Di Carlo:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Luigi Vesce:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition. **Zahra Saki:** Writing – review & editing. **Farzaneh Hajisharifi:** Writing – original draft. **Reza Sheibani:** Writing – review & editing. **Mirkazem Omrani:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data Availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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